

DELVING USER TRUST IN UTILIZING OF CHATGPT IN LEARNING AMONG ELEMENTARY EDUCATION STUDENTS: A MIXED METHODS STUDY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 1

Pages: 1-56

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2837

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14582068

Manuscript Accepted: 12-04-2024

Delving User Trust in Utilizing of ChatGPT in Learning Among Elementary Education Students: A Mixed Methods Study

Christian Jay B. Martinez,* Onorio P. Cagoco Jr.
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this undertaking was to investigate the level of user trust among elementary education students at Kapalong College, Davao del Norte, as they integrate ChatGPT into their learning experiences. Also, the study aimed to explore the lived experiences of elementary education students in the utilization of ChatGPT in the preparation and creation of their learning tasks and assignments. This study engaged mixed method design, utilizing parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the elementary education students from all year levels. There were 188 students who were randomly selected for quantitative and 14 for the qualitative: seven for in-depth interview and seven for focus group discussion which were purposively selected. Results revealed a high level of trust in ChatGPT's competence, reliability, and integrity, along with a strong intent among students to utilize it for various educational purposes. Actual usage encompassed tasks such as translation, creative writing, and academic discussions. The study underscores the positive perceptions and significant engagement with ChatGPT among students, indicating its potential as a valuable educational tool. By blending quantitative and qualitative methods, the research provides comprehensive insights into integration strategies, challenges, and recommendations, thereby enhancing the validity of its findings. Situated within the local context of Kapalong, Davao del Norte, the study offers actionable insights to improve teaching and learning, while also contributing to the global discourse on AI's role in education, enriching our understanding of its pedagogical implications.

Keywords: *User trust, elementary education students, mixed method, Convergent-parallel, local college*

Introduction

ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer) has gained popularity for its ability to generate human-like responses. Many users find this technology convenient and efficient, especially in various applications like chatbots, virtual assistants, and conversational agents (Agarwal et al., 2022). It is essential to note that overreliance or blind trust in ChatGPT, especially in high-stakes decision-making contexts, can have severe consequences. Correspondingly, lacking trust in the technology can lead to underuse, resulting in missed opportunities. To be specific, one of these concerns revolves around its potential exploitation for malicious purposes (de Angelis et al., 2023). Lastly, the ability of ChatGPT is to produce highly convincing fake text which has sparked unease as to its potential misuse in disinformation campaigns, deep fakes, and other malicious activities (Howard et al., 2023).

In the global context, particularly in the United States, there is a growing concern regarding the use of ChatGPT. Issues have arisen, including academic misconduct and cheating, leading to actions such as bans and regulations in academic institutions. These actions extend beyond immediate concerns, touching upon a deeper issue like the trustworthiness of ChatGPT and similar AI programs. The question at the core of this matter is why we should trust the outputs generated by ChatGPT given the potential influence of these tools on information sources in academia and journalism (Sachs, 2023).

In the Philippines, there is a pressing issue surrounding the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the academic context, particularly within the University of the Philippines (UP). This concern has led UP to establish ten principles aimed at guiding the responsible use of AI in educational settings. The catalyst for this initiative stems from growing apprehensions related to AI-driven chatbots like ChatGPT, which have raised questions among educators about their potential to facilitate cheating, provide incorrect information and disrupt the traditional learning process (Chi, 2023). Furthermore, Manrique (2023) mentioned and emphasized that susceptibility of ChatGPT to logical errors is a concern as it sometimes struggles to provide correct answers to even relatively straightforward logical questions or riddles. This not only damages the credibility of AI but also raises questions about its reliability.

Based on the problematic situation presented above, it is observable that the influence of ChatGPT is rampant in global, national, and local setting. By which, it was explained that this AI tool has been elucidated as a source of challenges and difficulties for teacher's within the teaching and learning process. Hence, there is a pressing need to conduct this study to generate new body of knowledge regarding on user trust about the utilization of AI most specifically, ChatGPT. On the other hand, studying user trust on the utilization of ChatGPT in learning among elementary education students holds significant social relevance in today's educational landscape. In an increasingly digitized world, technology is playing a pivotal role in reshaping how students access information and learn. Understanding how elementary education students perceive and trust AI-driven tools like ChatGPT can have profound implications for their learning experiences. This study can directly benefit several stakeholders, including students, educators, parents, and educational institutions.

Additionally, in the literature reviews included in this study, there are related studies on the present study such as the study of Mogavi et al., (2023) entitled, "Exploring User Perspectives on ChatGPT: Applications, Perceptions, and Implications for AI-Integrated Education," and Choudhury and Shamszare (2023) entitled, "Investigating the Impact of User Trust on the Adoption and Use of

ChatGPT: Survey Analysis," which discusses and explored the broad spectrum of AI and ChatGPT's applications in education. However, these studies primarily focused on understanding how users view and utilize ChatGPT particularly in the context of education and the impact of user trust decisions to adopt and use AI systems like ChatGPT. These studies are in fact, different from the present study given the fact that this research is geographically specific, conducted in the Philippines, and this interest primarily the elementary education students in the Province of Davao del Norte using a mixed methods research approach.

This work will be shared at research conferences and through relevant agencies to create a lively exchange among scholars and government authorities, promoting the sharing of research discoveries. The main objective of spreading these findings publicly is to stimulate thoughtful discussions, spark joint projects, and make it easier to apply the research in practical ways within public service and knowledge fields. The focus is on a well-thought-out dissemination plan to ensure that the information reaches and benefits a wider audience.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the level of user trust in the utilization of ChatGPT for learning among elementary education students. To be more specific, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of user trust in the use of ChatGPT in learning?
2. What are the lived experiences and coping mechanism of the elementary students on the usage of ChatGPT in their own learning?
3. To what extent do quantitative data corroborate with qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a mixed methods research design in a convergent parallel approach, which combines both quantitative and qualitative methods concurrently. According to Schoonenboom and Johnson (2017), mixed methods involve the use of quantitative and qualitative methods in a single or multiphase study. It is an inquiry or an approach that investigates the social world, ideally involving more than one methodological tradition and thus more than one way of knowing. Additionally, it employs more than one kind of technique for gathering, analyzing, and representing human phenomena, all for the purpose of better understanding.

In this study, a mixed methods approach was used, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The quantitative phase involved the use of a custom survey questionnaire to evaluate the level of trust in the usage of ChatGPT in the learning process among elementary education students at a local college. In the qualitative phase, the researcher explored participants' viewpoints regarding the significant findings from the quantitative phase through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

The chosen research design for this study was a convergent parallel mixed/ triangulation design. In this approach, both types of data were collected simultaneously, with equal importance given to each. The survey data were collected first, followed by focus group or one-on-one interviews. These two sets of data were analyzed independently, and then their results were combined and interpreted. This design is suitable for the study as it seeks to investigate the alignment, disparities, discrepancies, or connections between the two data sources (Hanson et al., 2005).

In the context of this study, data from qualitative sources, such as online interviews, screen recordings, and transcriptions, were collected alongside quantitative data from a survey questionnaire. These data were analyzed concurrently to uncover patterns and insights about user trust in the use of ChatGPT for learning. For the qualitative phase, thematic analysis was employed to examine the experiences of elementary education students regarding the usage of ChatGPT in learning. As for the quantitative data, statistical analysis, specifically means, was utilized to identify the level of user trust in the usage of ChatGPT in the learning process of the students.

Specifically, the quantitative component involved descriptive approach. Descriptive approach is a study designed to depict the participants in an accurate way. More simply putting descriptive approach is all about describing people who take part on the study. It is used to describe characteristics of a population phenomenon being studied. These kinds of categorical scheme also known as descriptive categories.

In the context of this study, it was categorized under the umbrella of descriptive research as it aimed to describe the level of user trust in the usage of ChatGPT. Specifically, the users involved in this study were elementary education students who used ChatGPT in the preparation of their learning tasks and lessons. The level of user trust was measured through the use of a survey questionnaire utilizing a five-point Likert scale.

On the qualitative side, a phenomenological approach was employed. As defined by Forris (2015), phenomenology research delves into details by pinpointing events based on participants' perceptions. This often involves gathering comprehensive data and perceptions using inferential, qualitative techniques such as participant observation, conversations, and interviews. Additionally, according to Delve (2022), phenomenology is an approach that seeks to understand and describe the universal essence of a phenomenon. It investigates

the everyday experiences of human beings while suspending the researchers' fixed assumptions about the phenomenon. In other words, phenomenological research studies lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences.

In the study, a phenomenological approach was used as it included studying one specific phenomenon, which was the variable of the study, focusing on the user trust in the usage of ChatGPT. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted to hear and unveil the standpoints, insights, and perceptions of the participants relative to the significant findings and results of the quantitative phase. This was conducted to confirm the data and to thoroughly explain the results found in the study.

Participants

The participants of the study, both in quantitative and qualitative phase, were described in this section. The participants were essential in conducting this study as they were the primary sources of data needed. With their involvement, the goal of the study was achieved and realized.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents in the quantitative phase were the elementary education students from all year levels in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology during the second semester of S.Y. 2022-2023. Meanwhile, the study only included a total of 108 respondents as the research samples, which were equally taken from first year to fourth year elementary education students.

Additionally, in choosing and selecting the samples from the given population of the study, stratified random sampling was used. As explained by Simkus (2023), stratified random sampling is a method of selecting a sample in which researchers first divide a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared characteristics of the members, and then randomly select among each stratum to form the final sample. In the study, the shared characteristics of the samples included their education level, degree or program, age, and gender.

Lastly, in selecting and choosing the qualified respondents in the study, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as basis and guide in the selection process. This includes: (1) must be enrolled in any Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in Bachelor of Elementary Education - Generalist; (3) must be currently enrolled in the current and previous academic year 2023-2024; (4) can be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study. All participants must be 1st to 4th -year BEED-Generalist students, and it is crucial to note that those involved in the qualitative phase should not have taken part in the data collection of the quantitative phase.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Sample</i>
Fourth Year	16	2%	9
Third Year	65	9%	33
Second Year	98	14%	50
First Year	187	26%	96
Total	366	51%	188

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, just like the quantitative phase, the participants were the elementary education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology. These participants were included and involved in in-depth interviews and focus-group discussions. Specifically, the study was included 7 informants for the in-depth interview and another 7 participants for the focus group discussion. This conformed to the suggestion and recommendation of Creswell and Creswell (2018) which pointed out that a researcher may have between 10 to 50 participants as being sufficient in qualitative research depending on the type of research and research questions, and it is crucial to note that those involved in the qualitative phase should not have taken part in the data collection of the quantitative phase.

Consequently, the researcher used purposive sampling techniques in selecting and choosing the participants to be included and involved in both the IDI and FGD. As explained by Nikolopoulou (2022), purposive sampling refers to a sampling technique in which participants are selected because they have characteristics that are needed in the samples for the study. In other words, participants are selected on purpose in purposive sampling.

Lastly, for the selection process, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as basis. This includes: (1) must be enrolled in any Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in Bachelor of Elementary Education-Generalist; (3) must be currently enrolled in the present and previous academic year 2023-2024; (4) can be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study. 2023-2024; (4) can be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

The exclusion criteria are as follows: (1) students who are not enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology; (2) students who are not enrolled in the Bachelor of Elementary Education-Generalist program; (3) students who were not enrolled in both the present and previous academic year 2023-2024; and (4) students who do not consent to participate in the study.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

Assigned Code	Sex	Year-Level
IDI-01	Female	1st Year
IDI-02	Male	1st Year
IDI-03	Female	2nd Year
IDI-04	Female	2nd Year
IDI-05	Female	3rd Year
IDI-06	Male	3rd Year
IDI-07	Female	4th Year
FGD-01	Female	1st Year
FGD-02	Female	1st Year
FGD-03	Male	2nd Year
FGD-04	Male	2nd Year
FGD-05	Male	3rd Year
FGD-06	Female	3rd Year
FGD-07	Female	4th Year

Instrument

In this section, the research tools in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed. This is in purpose to directly state the valid and reliable sources of the research materials to be used in this undertaking.

Quantitative Phase

In identifying the level of user trust in the usage of ChatGPT, a questionnaire adopted from a previously published study by Choudhury and Shamszare (2023) was used. The said questionnaire used a Five-point Likert Scale which has the following indicators: Trust, Intent to Use, and Actual Use. The 5-point Likert scale was utilized to determine the frequency of the indicators. The scale will range from 5 with strongly agree to 1 with strongly disagree. The survey questionnaire will be made to corroborate the results which will be gathered in the recorded interview.

Moreover, likert scale was good for measuring constructs, attitudes and stimuli which are not readily perceivable by human senses. Despite the questionnaire being adapted, it was further validated and evaluated by panelists who are all experts in the field of research. The suggestions and recommendations of the panelists were followed thoroughly to make the research tool more reliable. Additionally, the researcher ensured that the questions stipulated in the questionnaire used basic English so that the respondents could easily answer each question and comprehend the purpose of the research.

For user Trust on the usage of ChatGPT, the instrument that was used to measure the status of the participants consists of three indicators: Trust, Intent to Use, and Actual Use, where participants respond using a 5-point Likert scale. Moreover, the participants rated the statements on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 indicating rarely and 5 indicating always. To interpret the level of students' user trust in the usage of ChatGPT in their learning experience, the range of means, description, and presentation shown below will be used. The constructed survey questionnaire had prior reliability values that range from ---- which indicated that the instruments are reliable to measure the variables.

User Trust. The questionnaire for this variable was adapted from Choudhury and Shamszare (2023) and includes 3 indicators: trust, actual use, and intent to use. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used in the reliability test. The test's reliability score of .5 to .7 which indicated that these variables are well-defined and reliable. The instrument is a 17-item construct distributed unevenly over the three mentioned indicators.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, an interview guide was used which contained the grand core questions along with probing and supporting questions, which were employed both in the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. This guide was also validated by panelists to check the construction of the questions, ensuring they measured what they were intended to measure, and whether they would gather the needed data for the study. Furthermore, in this strand, the researcher utilized this validated interview guide to validate the results found in the quantitative phase of the study. Lastly, the interview guide consisted of two parts: the first for the letter of permission for the participants, and the second for the interview proper.

Procedure

From the time when the researcher is done with the routing of the manuscript to its panelists, the research manuscript was submitted to the Research Ethics of Kapalong College of Agriculture Science and Technology to check whether the study follows the mandated protocol needed for the ethical consideration and trustworthiness of the study. Also, the researcher requested for the Ethics Clearance to conduct the study. Then, after conforming to the recommendations as per protocol evaluation given by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the institution, the following are the stages were undertaken by the researcher in gathering the data needed in the

study.

First, the researcher wrote a letter asking for permission to conduct the study. A request letter was signed by the adviser and attached with an endorsement letter signed by the College President of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science and Technology. Then, this signed letter was forwarded to the Acting Dean of the Institute of Teacher Education (ITED) to inform her that the study would be conducted under her program, specifically with the elementary education students. After receiving the approval from the college president and the acting dean, the researcher was able to start gathering data by distributing the survey questionnaire to the respondents.

Meanwhile, before gathering data from the respondents, the researcher sought assistance from individuals within the institute, such as subject teachers or the program coordinator, to help facilitate the study. The researcher conducted an orientation to ensure they were fully aware of the nature and purpose of the study. Additionally, the researcher provided informed consent forms, which were given to the respondents. Afterward, the researcher personally discussed and oriented the respondents about the study's goals and purpose, as outlined in the informed consent form. The researcher also explained the role of the respondents in the study. After the orientation, the respondents signed the form, indicating that they fully understood the purpose and volunteered to participate in the study as research respondents.

After completing the necessary preliminaries in conducting the study, the researcher implemented various essential and significant measures in gathering data for both the qualitative and quantitative phases of the study. These measures ensured the confidentiality of the data during the data gathering process.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, the researcher conducted the study on a face-to-face basis. This meant that the researcher personally distributed the survey questionnaire to the respondents. To be specific with data gathering processes, the researcher followed these steps:

First, after the respondents signed the informed consent form, they were given the survey questionnaire which contained different questions about user trust on the utilization of ChatGPT. In the questionnaire, the respondents were not required to include their name as it was optional. They were given ample time to complete answering the questions to ensure that valid and reliable answers were obtained.

Second, after the respondents had completely answered all the stipulated questions in the survey questionnaire, the researcher completely retrieved the questionnaire in preparation for the tallying process. Subsequently, the respondents were given tokens of appreciation as a form of gratitude for their voluntary participation in the study. Additionally, the researcher provided the statistician with a format for tallying the data to ensure easy treatment of the data afterwards.

Third, after tallying the research data, the analysis and treatment of the data followed. The tallied data was provided to the research statistician, who possessed the necessary expertise in data analysis and treatment.

Fourth, upon receiving the results of the data analysis and treatment from the statistician, the researcher analyzed and interpreted the findings, with guidance from the research adviser. This collaborative effort ensured the accuracy and integrity of the analysis.

Lastly, throughout the entire process of data gathering, treatment, analysis, and interpretation, strict measures were implemented to maintain the confidentiality of the data obtained from the research respondents. All completed survey questionnaires were securely stored in a locked box with a unique and strong pin code, ensuring that only the researcher could access them. These measures guaranteed that no unauthorized individuals could gain access to the gathered data.

Qualitative Phase

In gathering the needed data for the qualitative phase, the researcher followed the following procedures:

First, the researcher selected 14 participants for the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. These participants were chosen based on a set of inclusion criteria established by the researcher to ensure that they met the necessary qualifications for the study.

Second, after selecting the participants during the quantitative phase of the study, the researcher conducted another orientation to inform and educate the participants about the next stage of the research. During this session, the participants were fully briefed about their role in the study. If any participants decided to withdraw during the orientation, their decision was respected, and new volunteers were selected as replacements.

Third, during the qualitative phase of the study, after the orientation, the researcher conducted a separate one-on-one interview with the first 7 informants via face-to-face. After the in-depth interview with the 7 informants, the researcher facilitated a focus group discussion with the remaining 7 participants using an online platform that was convenient for them and via face-to-face.

Fourth, after the interview process, the researcher transcribed all of the individual responses of the 7 informants in verbatim form. Additionally, a separate transcript was prepared for the 7 participants in the focus group discussion.

Fifth, when the individual transcripts of all the 7 informants were available as well as the transcript for the focus group discussion, the

researcher gave each informant and participant a copy of these. This was for them to check and verify whether the transcripts were accurate. Additionally, if any of the participants wished to delete part of the transcript or add more responses, the researcher confirmed and followed their requests.

Lastly, when the verified copies of the individual transcripts from the 7 informants and one from the focus group discussion were ready, the analysis of data, which is the thematic analysis, followed.

Ethical Considerations

These principles guided the conduct of the study in both qualitative and quantitative in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005). Hence, measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed throughout the course of a mixed method study. Further, the research of the study adhered with the elements of ethics which was stated from the International Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research Involving Humans 2016. The following includes: social value, informed consent, vulnerability of the research participants, justice, transparency, qualifications of the researcher, adequacy of facilities and community involvement the risk, benefits and safety, privacy and confidentiality of information. With that, before the study had been conducted the Research Ethics Committee validated the manuscript multiple times to ensure that the study adhered with the ethical principles.

Respect for persons was upheld as an ethical principle that underscored the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in the study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitated providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they had a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent was a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signified voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted ethically and in a manner that honored the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arranged the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This ensured that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and avoided the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

Before conducting the study, I established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. I allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, the participants had the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. By establishing rapport and acting with courtesy towards the participants, I was able to conduct the study in an ethical and respectful manner.

Consent was established as the first core principle of ethical considerations. Participants were fully informed about the study's requirements, how their data would be used, and any possible consequences. They gave their clear, active, and written consent to take part in the research. They also knew that they could access their information and could withdraw their consent whenever they wanted. The researcher and the participants came to an agreement when seeking this informed consent (Denzin & Lincoln 2011).

In this approach, the researcher added a question to the consent letter, asking participants if they agreed to take part in the study after understanding any potential risks involved. Participants had the choice to decline if they were unsure or not comfortable with it. The key emphasis was on making sure that participants were fully informed and willing to participate voluntarily. The researcher ensured that all respondents were enthusiastic and willing to be part of the study. Additionally, during data collection, it was essential to ensure that participants' responses were based on the provided questionnaire.

Benevolence as an ethical principle, was emphasized to underscore the commitment to minimizing risks and maximizing the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees was maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of benevolence, steps were taken to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants' responses and personal identities. These measures were implemented to ensure that the well-being and interests of the participants were demonstrated through a commitment to ethical research practices.

Furthermore, the data collected from this research study was used only for the purposes outlined in the study. However, the results of the study may also be shared or disseminated through channels such as presentations to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentations at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the results of the study, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. In upholding confidentiality for data, results, and findings while safeguarding participants, various techniques were employed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007). This involved concealing the personal identities of the participants, ensuring that no such information was disclosed. All materials, including audio records, coded transcripts, notes, as well as digital and

physical data copies, will be securely disposed of once the data analysis is completed.

To protect participants’ identities and adhere to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researcher utilized discrete coding to represent each participant’s responses. This approach entails carefully phrasing any information that might potentially reveal the participants’ identity, such as their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location, to maintain their anonymity. Through the use of effective coding and other precautionary measures, the researcher safeguarded participants’ identities and respect their privacy.

Justice. Justice in conducting this study revolved around respecting the rights of participants who identified themselves as BEED-Generalist students. Since the study aimed to investigate the level of user trust among elementary education students. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher employed both random and purposive sampling techniques. BEED- Generalist students were not coerced into participation and retained the freedom to decline at their discretion.

As a recognition of their valuable contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, duly acknowledging their involvement in the research and contributing to the overall success of the study. Moreover, justice was maintained by including only relevant remarks from the participants related to the research objectives and ensuring accurate transcription (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the quantitative and qualitative data of the investigation. In the quantitative phase, response of the participants from the survey questionnaire was used to identify the level of user trust among elementary education students on the usage of ChatGPT in learning. Meanwhile, in the qualitative phase, it includes the emerging themes relating to the lived experiences of elementary education students on the usage of ChatGPT in learning. It analyzes the uncover patterns and insights among the elementary education students with regards user trust with the use of ChatGPT in learning. Lastly, it measures the extent of corroboration between the quantitative data and qualitative data.

Level of user trust among Elementary Education Students on the usage of ChatGPT in learning.

User Trust. Shown in Table 2 is the level of user trust among elementary education students on the usage of ChatGPT in learning. As shown in the result, it obtained an overall mean rating of 3.05 with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that the level of user trust among the elementary education students in utilization of ChatGPT in learning is oftentimes practiced. This high overall mean is anchored on the computed category mean of the following indicators namely: trust, intent to use, and actual use.

Table 2. Level of user trust among Elementary Education Students on the usage of ChatGPT in learning

No.	Items	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Trust			
1.	Being competent in providing the information and guidance I need in my study.	3.73	High
2.	Being reliable in providing consistent and dependable information	3.50	High
3.	Being trustworthy in the sense that it is dependable and credible.	3.42	High
4.	Being honest with me and act with integrity.	3.48	High
5.	Being committed to maintaining the confidentiality and security of the information shared, ensuring a safe and secure interaction platform for users.	3.66	High
Category Mean		3.56	High
Intent to Use			
1.	Using ChatGPT as my research assistance to quickly gather information on a wide range of topics, aiding in the early stages of research.	3.62	High
2.	Utilizing ChatGPT to clarify and verify questions I have in mind related to my studies.	3.66	High
3.	Taking decisions based on the recommendations provided by ChatGPT.	3.37	High
4.	Using ChatGPT as an educational tool in making my learning task to enhance my overall productivity and performance.	3.54	High
5.	Using ChatGPT whenever I need more explanation to a certain topic.	3.73	High
Category Mean		3.58	High
Actual Use			
1.	Using ChatGPT in translating text from one language to another.	3.34	High
2.	Using ChatGPT for creative writing or brainstorming.	3.31	High
3.	Using ChatGPT for creative general information or casual conversation.	3.28	High
4.	Using ChatGPT for academic discussions or collaborative projects with classmates or colleagues.	3.42	High
5.	Using ChatGPT for guidance on effective study techniques, time management, and organization skills to enhance the learning process.	3.39	High
Category Mean		3.35	High
Overall Mean		3.05	High

Trust. The level of trust as reflected in the table is high, with an overall category mean of 3.56 which means that the user trust of the students in terms of trust in using ChatGPT is oftentimes practiced. Delving into the specific aspects of trust, item No. 1 - being competent in providing the information and guidance I need in my study obtained the highest mean of 3.73 with a descriptive equivalent

as high. This means that it is oftentimes practiced. Meanwhile, the item with the lowest mean under this indicator is in No. 3 - being trustworthy in the sense that it is dependable and credible with a mean of 3.42 and with a descriptive equivalent as high. This means that it is oftentimes practiced among students in terms of using ChatGPT.

Intent to Use. The level of intent to use as reflected in the table is high, with an overall category mean of 3.58 which means that the user trust of the students in terms of intent to use in using ChatGPT is oftentimes practiced. Further, the result showed that the highest mean of 3.73 was obtained from item No. 5 - willing to use ChatGPT whenever I need more explanation to a certain topic. It has a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes evident among students in using ChatGPT in learning. On the other hand, the item with the lowest mean is item No. 3 - willing to take decisions based on the recommendations provided by ChatGPT with a mean score of 3.37. It has a descriptive equivalent as high which means that it is oftentimes practiced by the students in using ChatGPT in learning.

Actual Use. Finally, the level of actual use as reflected in the table is high, with an overall category mean of 3.35 which means that the user trust of the students in terms of actual use in using ChatGPT is oftentimes practiced. with the platform across a range of activities. Furthermore, found in the result the highest mean of 3.42 was obtained from item No. 4 – using ChatGPT for academic discussions or collaborative projects with classmates or colleagues. It has a descriptive rating as high which means that it is oftentimes practiced by the students in using ChatGPT in learning. On the other hand, the lowest mean rating was obtained from item No. 3 – using ChatGPT for creative general information or casual conversation (3.28). It has a mean score of 3.28 described as high. This can be interpreted as it is oftentimes practiced by the students in using ChatGPT for learning.

Lived Experiences of Elementary Education Students with Regards to their Utilization of ChatGPT in Learning

Presented on Table 2.1 is the thematic analysis based on the responses of the participants in the in-depth interview and focus group discussion which are transcribed in verbatim manner. Furthermore, the responses were extracted from the result of one probed issue to unveil the lived experiences of elementary education students with regards to their utilization of ChatGPT in their learning experiences by which the issues obtained twenty-three codes grouped and clustered as one into different essential themes. By which, these themes are supported by six theoretical perspectives namely: Constructivist Theory of John Dewey, Human Centric AI (HCAIUT) Framework, Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen, Cognitive Development Theory, Language Learning Theory by Noam Chomsky, Input Hypothesis by Stephen Krashen, TPACK Knowledge.

Table 2.1. Lived Experiences of Elementary Education Students with Regards to their Utilization of ChatGPT in Learning

Issues Probed	Core Ideas	Code / Categories	Essential Theme	Theoretical Support
Personal Reasons and Considerations in using ChatGPT	Making the learning tasks and activities easy and simple.	Making Learning Tasks Convenient and Simple	Essential Resources in Learning	Constructivist Theory of John Dewey
	Making everything easy especially those loaded students with subject courses.			
	Having research easy and convenient.			
	Finishing the tasks ahead of time.	Reliable Source of Information	Effective in Giving and Aiding Answers	Human-Centric AI (HCAIUT) Framework
	Answering tests and quizzes immediately to earn higher scores.			
	Information given is well-constructed.			
	Seeking answers for vague and ambiguous questions in the discussion.	Accessible and user Friendly	Being User Friendly, Accessible, and Convenient to Use	Human-Centric AI (HCAIUT) Framework
	Gaining additional information to fully grasp the topic in class.			
	Checking and ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the response from the prompt given.			
	Helping in giving and sharing answers on the different learning tasks.	Convenient and Economically Friendly		
	Immediate answers on the different questions given which is timesaving.			
	Being effective and efficient in giving answers on the different quizzes.			
	Having easily accessible and less hassle for users.			
Having no fees and easy to navigate.				
Being able to easily understand information since it was explained thoroughly.				
Being able to understand and grasp different languages.				
Being convenient since it is free of use and cost nothing from users.				
Giving well-constructed sentences using good choice of words.				

	<p>Being able to translate highfalutin words into simpler terms and lexicon.</p> <p>Becoming responsible on validating the information given if it is accurate and reliable.</p> <p>Reading all the information given to check if it is right or wrong.</p> <p>Checking if the information given is searchable in other e-resources.</p> <p>Using google to verify the validity of the given answers.</p> <p>Evaluating and checking the responses by looking it to other search engines and websites.</p> <p>Learning new writing styles and conventions.</p> <p>Doing rephrasing and paraphrasing to contextualize ideas.</p> <p>Using Grammarly to check grammar and technicalities.</p> <p>Being able to get more ideas and elucidate more the topic.</p> <p>Understanding the concept and explain in one's own words.</p>	<p>Becoming Responsible in Using AI</p> <p>Verify Given Information from Reliable Website</p> <p>Enhance Writing Skills</p> <p>To Elaborate and Acquire More Ideas and Understanding More Informations</p>	<p>Becoming a Responsible User of AI</p> <p>Develop One's Writing Skill</p>	<p>Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen</p>
Impact of ChatGPT on the Students	<p>Helping in grasping the content and idea of the topic.</p> <p>Giving answers to all the questions given.</p> <p>Easily understanding the information given.</p> <p>Getting easily processing all the information related to the content.</p> <p>Making the learning tasks easy to make and finish.</p> <p>Making the answering of learning tasks easy and less hassle.</p> <p>Answering the learning tasks with ease and convenience.</p> <p>Being the writing assistant in making research.</p> <p>Making essays with ease and conviction since data is readily available.</p> <p>Helps in enhancing knowledge of grammar and sentence construction.</p> <p>Having confidence with grammar and in writing.</p> <p>Being over reliant with technology.</p> <p>Relying with AI on the answers and not using one's own knowledge and thinking.</p> <p>Not searching other resources as AI is giving already answers.</p> <p>Relying to AI all aspect of learning.</p> <p>Being narrow-minded and not listening with the ideas of others.</p> <p>Copying all the answers with understanding and conceptualizing it.</p> <p>Consistently using AI and not using one owns knowledge and intellect.</p> <p>Lack of effort and personal involvement in learning.</p> <p>Lack of originality due to relying on ready-made answers.</p> <p>Decreased faith in personal judgment and ideas.</p> <p>Become less inclined to seek out and synthesize information from diverse sources.</p>	<p>Assist in Understanding the Concepts</p> <p>Making the Learning Process Easy</p> <p>Scaffold Writing Skill Development</p> <p>Over Reliance with AI</p> <p>Degrading Critical Thinking and Comprehension</p> <p>Lost Confidence with One's Own Thought</p>	<p>Development of students' Personal Skills</p> <p>Degrading Higher Order Thinking Skills</p>	<p>Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen</p> <p>Cognitive Development Theory</p>
Strategies and Techniques in Using ChatGPT	<p>Doing paraphrasing with the given answers of AI.</p> <p>Rephrasing the given words and contextualize it.</p> <p>Rephrase and paraphrase paragraph to avoid plagiarism.</p> <p>Providing specific and efficient prompt to get the correct answer to your question.</p> <p>Having specific prompt to fit it with the question and context.</p> <p>Having detailed and specific prompt.</p> <p>Having precise prompt that is directly related to the</p>	<p>Doing Paraphrasing Rephrasing</p> <p>Provide and Read Specific Prompt</p>	<p>Enhancing Comprehension and Cultivating the Habit of Reading</p>	<p>Cognitive Load Theory</p>

Difficulties in Using ChatGPT	question.			
	Searching the answer to the other search engine to validate it.	Have Further Readings		
	Evaluating the answers to google.			
	Using grammar checker to check the accuracy of answer.			
	Contextualizing the answer in your own words.	Thorough Reading and Contextualization		
	Explaining the prompt in context to get right and exact answers.			
	Defining first the queries before asking question.			
	Checking the given information if it is reliable and accurate by validating it online.	Discerning the Reliability and accuracy of Information	Validating the Given Information	Input Hypothesis by Stephen Krashen
	Some answers are at far with the question.			
	Filtering all the information by checking accurate and reliable one.			
Checking the meaning of the word in the dictionary.				
Having outdated content since given contents are not searchable in other sources.	Having Outdated Information			
Having some information that is outdate and not relevant.				
having doubt to sign in for data privacy purposes.	Securing the Privacy of Information	Technology-based Concerns	TPACK Knowledge	
Concerning about the privacy and security of data.				
Having low internet connection since user is using mobile data.	Low Internet Connection			
Having no answers because of low internet connection.				

Essential Resources in learning. The incorporation of ChatGPT into the learning experiences of elementary education students reveals its importance as a vital resource in education. As students progress through their academic journey, ChatGPT acts as a trustworthy source of information, making learning tasks easier and offering helpful answers to their questions. By drawing from their own experiences, students discover the convenience of using ChatGPT, which helps them overcome various challenges they face in the learning process. Therefore, ChatGPT emerges as an essential tool that demonstrates the significant role of resources in improving learning outcomes and fostering academic success.

Making Learning Tasks Convenient and Simple. This is the first code of the first probed issue. Student expressed common responses on they perceived the benefits of incorporating ChatGPT into their learning task. Most of them stated that by making learning tasks easier and more straightforward, ChatGPT becomes a valuable resource for students, aiding them in overcoming challenges and enhancing their academic journey leading to improved learning outcomes and student success. Below are their responses.

Similarly, participant 3 acknowledges the utility of ChatGPT, emphasizing its easy access and the significant support it offers, particularly when tackling educational tasks or activities that require completion. This highlights that ChatGPT is not only simplifies their workflow but also accelerates the process of answering and completing tasks, making their learning experience more efficient.

This appreciation stems from ChatGPT's ability to assist with a wide range of learning objectives, thereby enhancing their productivity and enabling them to achieve better results in their educational endeavors more swiftly. He stated that:

“Naga gamit ko ug Chatgpt kay aside sa dali ra sya ma access maka tabang pud sya sa ako specially kong nakoy mga learning task or mga activities na dapat answeran para mapadali.” (IDI-03)

(I used ChatGPT aside for its ease of access; it also proves to be helpful to me, especially when I have learning tasks or activities that require answers, making the process more convenient).

In relation to that, Participant 4 echoed similar sentiments, emphasizing the speed and accessibility of ChatGPT in providing information for all their inquiries. They found ChatGPT's responses to be straightforward, further highlighting its utility in swiftly gathering relevant information. As Participant 4 stated:

“My personal reason of why I am using ChatGPT is because of the speed access that I can easily get information na tanan questions that I am asking is ma provide siya sa ChatGPT”. (IDI-04)

(I utilized ChaGPT to swiftly gather information for all of my queries. All of my inquiries were answered in a straightforward manner).

Moreover, the integration of ChatGPT into studying routines proves to be an asset, especially amidst the demanding workload spanning various subjects. Leveraging ChatGPT's capabilities streamlines learning tasks, rendering them more manageable and efficient. This AI-driven solution facilitates prompt access to answers with minimal effort, optimizing the study process. Embracing practical tools like ChatGPT exemplifies a student-centric approach to tackling academic responsibilities, underscoring the importance of utilizing

technology to simplify tasks and enhance learning outcomes, as aptly highlighted by this experience. As what participant 3 said that:

“My personal reason why I am using ChatGPT in my learning task is para mapadali akong mga buhatonon, samot na karon loaded kaayo ko, so the best thing or option nako is using ChatGPT, because sa kani nga kind of A.I, one click lang nimo mohatag na dayon syag answer, so be practical no as a student para mapadali nalang atong buhatonon”. (IDI-06)

(My personal reason for using ChatGPT in my learning tasks is to make my activities easier, especially now that I have a heavy workload in different subjects. I think ChatGPT is the best option for me because, with this type of AI, you can receive answers with just a single click. So, let us just be practical as students to make our tasks easier).

Similarly, in the focus group discussion, Participant 3 expressed a similar sentiment, stating that they used ChatGPT to facilitate faster response to their queries, projects, tasks, and activities assigned by their instructors. He highlighted the prevalence of technology in today's era and the recognition of ChatGPT as a well-known tool. The Participant emphasized ChatGPT's dependability in providing specific responses to a wide range of questions, making it a valuable resource for their educational endeavors. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“Nag gamit ko ug ChatGPT para mas madali ug answers ang akoang mga queries, projects, task ug activity nga ginahatag sa amoang instructor, tapos ang ChatGPT pud well known siya in to this era kay more on technology namn ta karon gina utilize nato ang ChatGPT kay sa ChatGPT man gud kay naa pud siyay specific answer unya halos tanan nimong questions kay matubag niya.” (FGD-03)

(I used ChatGPT to make it easier to get answers for my queries, projects, tasks, and activities assigned by our instructor. And ChatGPT is well-known in this era because we are more focused on technology now, and we utilize ChatGPT because it provides specific answers, and almost all of my questions can be answered by it).

In addition, students tended to opt for a more relaxed approach to task completion, preferring to relax while completing their tasks. Hence, they utilized ChatGPT to make their research and question answering easier. This choice facilitated the generation of ideas quickly, making the process more efficient and enabling them to finish their work effortlessly. This highlighted the utility of ChatGPT in supporting productivity while catering to individual learning styles and preferences among students. As what participant 6 said that:

“So, my own and personal reason because usually I tend to be very lazy, I tend to like just chill in answering my task so I just use chatGPT to make it more easier to make my easier research about the question and then coping up with idea and then I can finish it”. (FGD-01)

(I tend to be quite lazy, and I prefer to relax while completing my tasks. So, I use ChatGPT to make my research and question answering easier. It helps me generate ideas quickly, making the process more efficient and allowing me to finish my work effortlessly)

In relation to that, one of the reasons students personally turned to ChatGPT was their tendency to procrastinate. Relying on ChatGPT for swift answers to activities, quizzes, and tests allowed them to aim for high scores and effectively complete all assignments and assessments. This highlights how elementary education students strategically utilized ChatGPT to overcome procrastination tendencies and ensure academic success by accessing timely assistance and achieving their academic goals efficiently. As what Participant 4 stated:

“So, one of my personal reasons why I used ChatGPT, because is I always procrastinate and I used ChatGPT to answer immediately all activities, quizzes and in order for my test scores to be high score and to pass may all activities and quizzes.” (FGD-04)

(One of the reasons I personally used ChatGPT is because I have a tendency to procrastinate. I depend on ChatGPT to provide quick answers for activities, quizzes, and tests so that I can aim for high scores and successfully complete all my assignments and assessments).

Furthermore, the utilization of ChatGPT serves a personal need for creating extra time, particularly in handling tasks and activities assigned by their instructors. Participant in the focus grouped stated the instances where multiple tasks were issued simultaneously, presenting a time management challenge. By leveraging ChatGPT, they could expedite the completion of one task, thereby freeing up valuable time to dedicate to other assignments from their teachers. Participant 2 stated that:

Personal reason utilizing ChatGTP is to create additional time for myself, especially when dealing with tasks and activities assigned by my teachers. There are instances when multiple tasks are given simultaneously. Using ChatGPT allows me to complete one task more quickly, leaving me with additional time to focus on other assignments provided by my teachers (FGD-02).

Reliable Source of Information. This is the second code of the first probed issue. Participants in both IDI and FGD emphasized the importance of utilizing ChatGPT for its ability to provide well-constructed information. They highlighted its usefulness in addressing vague and ambiguous questions, enabling them to gain a deeper understanding of topics discussed in class. Moreover, they noted its role in verifying the reliability and accuracy of responses, thereby enhancing their confidence in the information obtained. By leveraging ChatGPT, individuals can augment their comprehension and ensure the dependability of the knowledge they acquire, contributing to more informed decision-making and enriched learning experiences.

Similarly, some information obtained from ChatGPT is deemed reliable, while others are well-constructed. This recognition

underscores the trust placed in AI technologies like ChatGPT to deliver accurate and coherent information, enhancing the overall quality of research and learning experiences. By leveraging ChatGPT, students can access a wealth of reliable and well-constructed information, enriching their understanding and facilitating academic success. As what participant 5 stated that:

“My personal reason why I used A.I particularly the ChatGPT, because some information coming for it are reliable and some information also coming from it are very well constructed”. (IDI-05)

(My personal reason why I used A.I, particularly ChatGPT, is because some information coming from it is reliable and some information also comes from it is very well constructed).

Moreover, upon facing difficulties of organizing ideas and thoughts, particularly when confronted with complex instructions or discussions, poses a common challenge for students. By utilizing ChatGPT's capabilities, it can effectively address the complex aspects of the questions, leading to better comprehension and more coherent responses. This reliance on ChatGPT highlights its value as a tool for enhancing understanding and helping elementary education students to express their thoughts and ideas, ultimately assisting them in overcoming academic obstacles and achieving success. As what Participant 3 said that:

“I have a difficulty in constructing the ideas and thoughts especially kanang pinkalit instruction or discussion so ug mag struggle ko ug sabot sa kana nga particular question I used ChatGPT to para ma answeran tanan ug matubag nako tong mga questions nga mga lisod para sa akoo.” (FGD-03)

(I often face difficulties in organizing my ideas and thoughts, especially when dealing with complex instructions or discussions. When I find it challenging to comprehend a particular question, I turn to ChatGPT to help me answer and address all the difficult aspects of the questions effectively).

Additionally, users recognized the necessity of verifying the accuracy and trustworthiness of information provided by AI, like ChatGPT, is crucial, especially in academic contexts. The rapid response capability of AI can be immensely beneficial for learning and research, but it also underscores the importance of user responsibility in cross-checking facts and aligning the acquired knowledge with established academic standards. Understanding the need for responsible AI use ensures that academic materials are handled with integrity, fostering a learning environment where technology enhances educational outcomes without compromising on quality or reliability. As Participant 1 said that:

“Ang ma consider gyud nako is the reliablity of result gyud sa answer itself because it is important to know gyud gihapon na mahibal ang mga idea if accurate and reliable ba ang mga information na gi provide sa kani nga AI, kay nay instances na mag ask ko ug lenty questrions pataka rapud syag tubag sahay”. (IDI-01)

(What I really consider is the reliability of the results of the answers themselves because it is important to know if the ideas provided by this AI are accurate and reliable. There are instances when I ask numerous questions, and it sometimes gives answers hastily).

Lastly, recognizing the critical role of verifying the accuracy and trustworthiness of information provided by AI, particularly in ChatGPT, is paramount, especially for students relying on it for academic tasks. Rapid responses, while beneficial, necessitate a responsible approach to cross-checking facts and ensuring alignment with academic standards. Understanding the importance of being diligent and conscientious in the use of AI for educational purposes underscores the need for a balanced approach to leveraging technology while maintaining high standards of academic integrity and rigor. As Participant 7 said that:

“My consideration and measures I always keep in mind when using ChatGPT for my learning tasks and activities. First is ang accuracy and reliability jud sa response niya so I ensure that the information provided by ChatGPT is accurate and reliable by cross-referencing it with other credible sources or academic materials. This helps me maintain the quality of my work and avoid spreading misinformation. Ug second is understanding the concept jud, so before accepting ChatGPT's response, I make sure to understand the concepts thoroughly. If the answer seems unclear or ambiguous, so I take the time to research and clarify the topic further to ensure I grasp it fully.” (FGD-07)

(My consideration and measures I always keep in mind when using ChatGPT for my learning tasks and activities. First, I prioritize the accuracy and reliability of its responses. I ensure that the information provided by ChatGPT is accurate and reliable by cross-referencing it with other credible sources or academic materials. This helps me maintain the quality of my work and avoid spreading misinformation. Second, I prioritize understanding the concept thoroughly. Before accepting ChatGPT's response, I make sure to understand the concepts thoroughly. If the answer seems unclear or ambiguous, I take the time to research and clarify the topic further to ensure I grasp it fully).

Effective in Giving and Aiding Answers. This is the third code of the first probed issue. From the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, participants highlighted the significance of ChatGPT in providing immediate and accurate answers to various learning tasks and questions. It emphasized how ChatGPT's efficiency saves time, allowing them to swiftly obtain answers and complete quizzes effectively. This capability proves invaluable in addressing the demands of academic tasks, enhancing productivity, and facilitating smoother learning experiences. By leveraging ChatGPT, students in elementary education can efficiently navigate through their assignments and assessments, contributing to improved academic performance and learning outcomes.

Similarly, participant expresses a strong preference for ChatGPT among the multitude of AI tools available, citing its accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and substantial aid in education. They highlight ChatGPT's ease of access and lack of financial burden as significant advantages, making it a convenient and practical choice. Moreover, the individual emphasizes how ChatGPT significantly improves their academic performance by providing timely assistance and enhancing productivity. By leveraging ChatGPT's capabilities, they not only complete tasks more efficiently but also discover new ways to approach learning tasks creatively. As what Participant 2 said that:

“For me sa kadaghag A.I karon na nang gawas ang sa ChatGPT jud ko hiyang kay dali rajd pud sya ma access, walay gasto unya dako jd pud syag tabang sakong pag skwela, unya tungod ani mas daghan kog na dsdiscover niya kasabay na ana ang pag improve sakong performance na mahimo nako akong mga learning task and activities na simple but creative ug sa uban pang butang na dili makalas imong oras unya mas himo kang productive sa tanan.” (IDI-02)

(For me, among the many AI technologies available today, I find ChatGPT to be the most suitable for me. It is easy to access, does not cost anything, and it greatly helps me in my studies. Because of this, I have discovered more things, and along with that, my performance has improved. I can now handle my learning tasks and activities in a simpler yet more creative way, as well as other tasks that do not eat up too much of my time, making me more productive overall).

Additionally, participants highlighted that they utilized ChatGPT as their primary tool for creating learning tasks and activities. They pointed out that ChatGPT was among the first to popularize AI tools for such purposes, and its advanced development sets it apart from other similar tools. They find ChatGPT easier to use, especially when provided with clear prompts, enabling it to deliver specific responses tailored to their needs. Despite certain features requiring a premium account, participants appreciate ChatGPT's notable feature of being able to connect with other websites, expanding its functionality and usefulness. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“So,I used ChatGPT to be the tool in making my learning task and activities kay maybe beacause kanang siya ang medyo nag una-una sap ag popularize aning mga ai tools so much more developed na siya compared to other ai tools na pareparehas sa iya, ChatGPT kay mas hawod na siya, and then basta tarungon lang pud nimo ug prompt mahatag pud niyang specific na imong gusto , and then daghan napud siyag features na pwede nimo e connect but then kailangan lagi nimo ug premium na account but still a notable feature of ChatGPT to be able to link other website na pwede nimo ma use.” (FGD-01)

(I chose ChatGPT as the tool for my learning tasks and activities because it was one of the first AI tools to become popular, so it is much more developed compared to other similar AI tools. ChatGPT is easier to use, and as long as you provide a clear prompt, it can give you specific answers. Moreover, it has many features that you can connect to, although some require a premium account. Still, a notable feature of ChatGPT is its ability to link to other websites that you can use).

Moreover, participant's choice to use ChatGPT for their learning tasks and activities stems from a desire to streamline and simplify their workload. By relying on ChatGPT, they can efficiently complete their activities and quizzes, ensuring high-quality output without excessive time and effort. This reliance on ChatGPT underscores its role not only as a quick source of answers but also as a partner in their educational journey, enabling them to stay productive and creative. In essence, ChatGPT becomes an integral component of their workflow, facilitating productivity and innovation in their educational endeavors. As what Participant 4 said that:

So, I always used ChatGPT because ChatGPT is effective and efficient in answering the activity and the quizzes and it is very accessible to my part and I have used it everyday to make my activities easier. (FGD-04)

Furthermore, participant's choice to use ChatGPT for their learning tasks and activities stems from a desire to streamline and simplify their workload, particularly when balancing academic responsibilities with other commitments, such as internship duties. By relying on ChatGPT, they can efficiently generate ideas and gather tips to enhance the quality of their activities, thereby alleviating the burden of coming up with creative concepts on their own. This illustrates how ChatGPT serves not only as a resource for accessing immediate answers but also as a creative partner, enabling users to overcome mental fatigue and resource constraints by providing valuable insights and suggestions. In essence, ChatGPT becomes an integral component of their workflow, facilitating productivity and innovation in their educational endeavors. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Para pud sa akoa, gi pili nakong ChatGPT na gamiton para sa akong mga learning tasks and activities para mas mabawas-bawasan ang akong mga gagmay nga buhatonon ug mapadali nalang sa akoa tanan, kay naay usahay kapoyon nako kay gikan pako sa duty for intern so some of my activities na gina buhat unya ug need nakog mga nindot nga mga ideas para sakong activity na e-conduct mo dool ko sa ChatGPT to ask more ideas or tips para akong gamiton.” (FGD-07)

(For me, I chose to use ChatGPT for my learning tasks and activities to reduce the workload and make everything easier for me. Sometimes I feel exhausted coming from my duty as an intern, so when I have activities to do and need good ideas, I turn to ChatGPT for assistance. It helps me brainstorm ideas and get tips quickly, making it convenient for me to conduct my activities efficiently).

Being User Friendly, Accessible, and Convenient to Use. The use of ChatGPT has revealed important qualities that enhance the learning experiences of students. Through personal experiences and coping strategies, it becomes clear that ChatGPT is user-friendly, accessible, and convenient. Students find it easy to access and use, as it does not require any fees and has an intuitive navigation system. Additionally, its ability to explain information thoroughly and simplify complex language ensures that students understand and grasp concepts easily. With well-constructed sentences and support for multiple languages, ChatGPT emerges as a valuable tool for

elementary education students, facilitating a smooth learning process that accommodates diverse needs and preferences.

Accessible and user Friendly. This is the fourth code from the first probed issue. Participant in both IDI and FGD highlighted ChatGPT's accessibility and user-friendly design as crucial. They commended its hassle-free navigation and lack of fees, catering to users of varying technological skills. ChatGPT's comprehensive explanations were praised for simplifying complex information, while its multilingual support was lauded for accommodating diverse language needs. These features enhance ChatGPT's widespread usability, facilitating informed decision-making and enriched learning experiences for users across diverse contexts. Below are their responses:

Similarly, participants mentioned that using ChatGPT was simple and produced accurate results. Based on their experiences, they found it to be more user-friendly and responsive than other existing AI systems. This remark emphasizes ChatGPT's efficiency and ease of use, making it a popular choice among users seeking quick and simple access to information. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“Kuan sir sa ChatGPT nako nakita nga ug mag access nimo sya is dili siya hassle ug dali ra sya maka generate ug answer compared form different existing na mga AI karon.” (IDI-01)

(I find that accessing ChatGPT is not a hassle, and it can generate answers efficiently. In my experience, it seems to be more user-friendly and quicker in generating responses compared to other existing AI platform).

Moreover, among the many AI platforms available, students, particularly elementary education students, considered ChatGPT to be one of the most convenient accessible AI platforms. It was easily accessible, affordable, and greatly aided their educational pursuits. They had discovered new approaches to improving their performance in a variety of learning tasks and activities. It had allowed them to be both basic and creative, making the most use of their time and contributing to overall productivity. As what Participant 2 said that:

“For me sa kadaghag A.I karon na nang gawas ang sa ChatGPT jud ko hiyang kay dali rajd pud sya ma access, walay gasto nya dako jd pud syag tabang sakong pag skwela unya tungod ani mas daghan kog na dsicover nya kasabay na ana ang pag improve sakong performance na mahimo nako akon mha learning task and activities na simple but creative ug sa uban pang butang na dle makalas imong oras nya ma himo kang productive sa tanan.” (IDI-02)

(Among the many AI platforms today, I consider ChatGPT to be one of the most convenient platforms accessible today. It is easily accessible, affordable, and has greatly aided my educational pursuits. I have discovered new approaches to improving my performance in a variety of learning tasks and activities. It allows me to be both basic and creative, making the most use of my time and contributing to overall productivity)

In addition, choosing ChatGPT as a preferred choice is a decision rooted in its ability to present information clearly and understandably. Its knack for explaining concepts effectively, often supplemented with examples, greatly aids in the comprehension of ideas. This clarity and thoroughness in explanation significantly contribute to easing the process of grasping complex concepts and topics. By providing accessible and well-structured information, ChatGPT enhances the learning experience, making it a favored tool for individuals seeking comprehensive understanding and clarity in their educational pursuits. Participant 4 stated that:

“Because ChatGPT is giving an information that I can easily understand, kay iya man gud jud gina explain ug mayo tas nagahatag pud siyag mga example so that’s why ginagamit nako ang ChatGPT.” (IDI-04)

(ChatGPT is my preferred choice because it provides information in a clear and understandable manner. It explains concepts well and often includes examples, making it easier for me to grasp ideas. That is why I chose to use ChatGPT).

Furthermore, the simplicity and accessibility of ChatGPT were highlighted as the primary reasons for choosing it over other AI tools. The emphasis on its ease of access suggested that users appreciated ChatGPT's user-friendly interface and straightforward usability. This sentiment underscored the importance of intuitive design and widespread accessibility in AI tools, as they enabled a broader range of users to benefit from the technology without encountering barriers related to complexity or technical proficiency. As what Participant 2 said that:

“The reason why I used ChatGPT instead of other AI tools because easy lang siya e access ug kanang accessible sya for everyone.” (FGD-02)

(The reason why I chose to used ChatGPT instead of other AI tools is because it is easy to access and readily available for everyone).

Convenient and Economically Friendly. This is fifth code of the first probed issue. From the in-depth interviews and focus group discussions it revolved around ChatGPT's convenience and cost-effectiveness. Users appreciated its accessibility without any associated fees, making it economically friendly. Moreover, ChatGPT excelled in crafting well-constructed sentences with precise word choices, enhancing clarity and comprehension. Additionally, it adeptly translated highfalutin words into simpler terms and lexicons, ensuring accessibility for users with varying levels of language proficiency. This blend of convenience, economic viability, and linguistic adeptness underscored ChatGPT's effectiveness in providing accessible and user-friendly language assistance, catering to a diverse user base. Below are their responses:

Similarly, the participant highlights the convenience of using ChatGPT, noting its ability to provide immediate answers to queries

without any financial cost. This contrast with other AI generators underscores ChatGPT's accessibility, as users can access its features without the need for monetary investment. This accessibility aspect ensures that individuals, regardless of financial means, can benefit from ChatGPT's capabilities, promoting equity in educational resource utilization. Consequently, the participant's observation underscores how ChatGPT's affordability enhances its appeal and usability, contributing to its widespread adoption as a valuable learning tool. Participant 3 stated that:

“Aside sa hatagan dayon ka niyag tubag sa imong mga pangutana it is very convenient to use pud kaayu kay wala kay bayaran bisan piso kong mag log in ka, unlike sa ubang mga A.I generator to use and access information”. (IDI-03)

(Besides the convenience of receiving immediate answers to my questions, another advantage of using ChatGPT is its cost-effectiveness. It does not require any payment, even if you log in, unlike other A.I. generators that may have associated fees for accessing information).

Moreover, the participant's choice to utilize ChatGPT for learning tasks and activities stemmed from its ability to generate well-constructed results and sentences. This stated that it can use to articulate language and the presentation of information in paragraph form, distinguishing ChatGPT from other AI systems that often presented results in bullet points. This preference indicated a desire for creativity and productivity in their learning process. By leveraging ChatGPT's capacity for producing coherent and detailed responses, the participant enhanced their learning experience, fostering deeper understanding and engagement with the material. Thus, their decision underscored the value of ChatGPT in facilitating innovative and effective learning approaches. As what Participant said that:

“I used ChatGPT as a tool in making my learning tasks and activities, because as I have observed sa ChatGPT man gud ang mga mahatag niya na result or sentences are well constructed like nindot jd kaayu ang mga words na iyang gipang gamit nya paragraph form nasad siya, unlike sa mga laing A.I na ang result kasagaran is naka bullet lang sya so choose ChatGPT to make my learning task and activities more creative and productive.” (IDI-05)

(I used ChatGPT as a tool for my learning tasks and activities because I have observed that it provides well-constructed results and sentences. The words used are articulate, and it presents information in paragraph form, unlike other A.I. systems that often present results in bullet points. I chose ChatGPT to make my learning tasks and activities more creative and productive).

In addition, ChatGPT's exceptional multilingual prowess, notably in Bisaya, enhances learning experiences. Its flexibility comprehensively explains diverse topics, crucial for BEED students grappling with complex mother tongue subjects. ChatGPT adeptly simplifies intricate terminologies, aiding comprehension. In tasks like lesson planning, where convoluted terms pose challenges, ChatGPT streamlines processes, making them more manageable. This adaptability underscores its efficacy in supporting diverse learning needs, offering invaluable assistance in navigating linguistic complexities and facilitating better understanding, crucial for academic success among elementary education students. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“ChatGPT can understand and respond naturally in any language bisan pag bisaya imong gina feed sa iyaha na question makasabot gihapon siya, mo respond pud siyag bisaya,ang ChatGPT kay convenient and flexible lang jud siya na kaya niya e explain halos tanan or naa siyay ma explain sa gusto nimo ipasabot unya mahatag pud niya. Specially for us a BEED student we haved a mother tongue subject there are some terminology that lisod kaayu siya sabton, by using ChatGPT kaya niya mapahubad in simple terms into common terms para mas masabtan nimo pag ayo. Adtionally, pud katong nag buhat mi ug lesson plan para sa among mother tongue na subjectec. ... there are some terminologist na lisod jud kay siya sabton so with the used of ChatGPT makasabot dayon mi ug mas mapadali ang buhatanon.” (IDI-06)

(Based on my experiences, ChatGPT demonstrates a remarkable ability to understand and respond naturally in various languages, including Bisaya. It stands out for its flexibility, allowing it to explain a wide range of topics comprehensively. This flexibility is especially beneficial for us as BEED students, dealing with mother tongue subjects that may involve challenging terminologies. ChatGPT simplifies complex terms into more understandable language, aiding in better comprehension. Moreover, in tasks like lesson planning for mother tongue subjects, where intricate terminologies may pose difficulties, ChatGPT's assistance helps streamline the process and make it more manageable for us).

In relation to that, ChatGPT reflected a proactive approach to learning. Relying on recommendations and recognizing the importance of diversity in learning resources, they embraced a multifaceted approach to education. ChatGPT's recent updates in Bisaya and Tagalog further enhanced its suitability for diverse learners. They viewed ChatGPT as a valuable partner in their learning journey, emphasizing its role as a tool rather than a sole reliance. This approach highlighted the participant's adaptability and openness to leveraging technology as a complement to traditional learning methods, enriching their educational experience. As Participant 7 stated:

“Among those AI dili lang man pud ChatGPT akong gina use so daghan ko ug gina use via sa recommendation, as youth, and as a learner dili lang pud jud ko mag rely on sa A.I but as a student as learner ma dali-dali jud nako si ChatGPT specifically now nga grabing update niya via bisaya, tagalog, kanang ma do jud niya halos tanan same pud sa uban. I used ChatGPT to be the tool in using my learning task is that because is one of my partner but dili lang jd si ChatGPT pud na gina gamit as a learner.” (IDI-07)

(Among those AI, I do not solely rely on ChatGPT. I use several AI tools based on recommendations. As a youth and a learner, I do not just depend on AI, but as a student, I find ChatGPT particularly helpful. With its frequent updates and support for languages like

Bisaya and Tagalog, it can handle almost everything. ChatGPT is one of my go-to tools for learning tasks, but it's not the only one I use as a learner.

Furthermore, the response highlighted ChatGPT's convenience in its ability to paraphrase and simplify language, enhancing ease of use. Users found it practical, as these tasks could be performed directly within the platform, setting it apart from other AI tools. ChatGPT's ability to swiftly transform complex information into more understandable forms was valued, streamlining various processes. This convenience facilitated smoother interactions and increased productivity, making ChatGPT a preferred choice for its efficiency in handling linguistic tasks. As Participant 6 stated that:

“So, ang reason nganung mas gipili nako ang Chatgpt, kay unlike sa uban kay naman gud uban nga mga AI gihapon for example consensus mag search ka didtoa pero dili na nimo ma kuan for example mag paraphrase ka ana dili na nimo pwede buhaton didto, sa ChatGPT mn gud kay ug maka search kag information pwede ra nimo ipa paraphrase sa iyaha or kong tan aw nimo nga murag kuan ra kaayu kanang lag-lom ra kaayo ang words na iyang gi gamit pwede ra nimo ipa simplify sa iyang ang gamiton. So, when it come using ChatGPT kuan jud kay siya dali rajud kaayo siya gamiton diria pud akong mostly jud mao jud ni akong gina gamit.” (FGD-06)

(The reason why I preferred to use ChatGPT is because unlike other AI tools, some of them, for example, Concensus, when you search there, you cannot really do much. For example, if you want to paraphrase something, you cannot do it there. But with ChatGPT, if you search for information, you can easily ask it to paraphrase the content. If you feel that the language used is too complex, you can also ask to simplify it. So, when it comes using ChatGPT, it is really convenient to use. That is why it is mostly what I used.

Lastly, ChatGPT stood out as a user-friendly AI tool. Its accessibility and cost-free nature made it easily accessible to users, eliminating barriers to entry. Moreover, ChatGPT was highly reliable and accurate in providing responses, whether generating ideas or answering queries and tasks. Its versatility shone through, adapting to various contexts and effectively addressing diverse needs. This combination of user-friendliness, reliability, accuracy, and versatility underscored ChatGPT's value as a dependable resource for learners, offering a seamless and effective experience in navigating educational tasks and queries. As what participant 7 stated that:

“ChatGPT kasi is a kind of AI na user friendly lang siya as what she mentiond, free lang jud sIya and it has high level of reliability and accuracy man pud in terms in providing responses like ang pag generate sa mga ideas and to my queries and tasks nga matawag jud nato’g versatile jud kaayo siya.” (FGD-07)

(ChatGPT is a type of AI that is user-friendly, as mentioned. It is also free, and it has a high level of reliability and accuracy in providing responses, such as generating ideas and answering queries and tasks. It is indeed very versatile).

Becoming a Responsible Use of AI. Based on the information gleaned from in-depth interviews and focus grouped discussion, it is claimed that Elementary education students engage in a transformative journey when utilizing ChatGPT in their learning endeavors. As they navigate this AI tool, they inherently adopt the essence of responsibility in their actions. Validating the accuracy and reliability of information becomes paramount, prompting them to meticulously read and evaluate responses. By cross-referencing with other e-resources and utilizing search engines like Google, students ensure the validity of provided answers. This process not only fosters critical thinking but also instills a sense of accountability in utilizing AI effectively.

Being Responsible in Using AI. This is the sixth code from the first probed issues. Participants suggested that individuals should not passively accept information provided by AI systems, but rather actively engage in verifying its accuracy. This involves cross-referencing information across multiple platforms and using reliable search engines to ensure the information's credibility. The practice of becoming responsible in using AI teaches users to discern quality information from misinformation, enhancing their information literacy skills. This is especially pertinent in academic settings, where the integrity of information is paramount.

Similarly, as a responsible student utilizing AI, it's imperative to verify the information obtained and ensure that all claims align with academic standards. This conscientious approach not only enhances understanding but also fosters a sense of responsibility in using AI tools for academic purposes. By discerning between accurate and erroneous information, users not only uphold academic integrity but also gain valuable insights into effectively incorporating AI into their academic endeavors. This process underscores the importance of critical thinking and discernment in leveraging AI for academic tasks, thereby contributing to a more informed and responsible approach to integrating technology into one's educational journey. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“As a student being responsible of used AI it is need to verify first jd the information obtained by AI and of course to ensure that it all claims are aligns with academic standards so as a user masabtan rasada nako kay sa kana nga mga mali naka learn man sad ko on how being responsible using AI, interms of parting my academics stuff.” (IDI-01)

(As a student, it is essential to verify the information obtained from AI and ensure that all claims align with academic standards. By doing so, you can better understand the material and develop critical thinking skills. Learning to be responsible when using AI in academic pursuits is crucial for academic integrity and personal growth).

Additionally, the participant emphasizes the importance of authenticity in the information provided by ChatGPT, particularly in learning tasks where accuracy is paramount. They adopt a cautious approach by cross-referencing the information with other reputable websites to verify its legitimacy. This practice reflects a responsible use of AI tools, where users actively engage in fact-checking

processes to ensure the reliability of the information they utilize. By prioritizing authenticity, users not only uphold academic standards but also cultivate a critical mindset essential for discerning reliable sources amidst the vast amount of information available online. As Participant 3 said that:

“So for me I always consider the authenticity of the information, which is very needed kaayu in some learning task and gina confirm pud nako sya sa uban website if legit b a ng mga information na gihatag ni ChatGPT.” (IDI-03)

(For me, I always consider the authenticity of the information, which is very needed in some of my learning tasks. I also verified the information provided by ChatGPT by confirming it on other websites to ensure its legitimacy).

Furthermore, the participant acknowledges that while ChatGPT can provide a wealth of information, there's a risk of it overwhelming them with excessive responses, leaving them without a clear direction. To manage this, they adopt a meticulous approach by carefully reading and considering each response provided by ChatGPT for every question posed. This strategy reflects a deliberate effort to sift through the abundance of information provided by the AI, ensuring that they extract only the relevant and useful insights. By actively engaging with the responses and discerning their value, the participant demonstrates a thoughtful and discerning approach to utilizing ChatGPT as a tool for accessing information effectively. This approach helps them navigate the potential information overload, enabling them to derive maximum benefit from the AI's capabilities while maintaining control over the quantity and quality of the information they receive. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“I always consider na ang ChatGPT is sometimes the information provided is too much kumbaga na masubraan syag hatag na wala na namao,so every question na iyang gi provide gina basa jd nako siya.” (IDI-04)

(I always considered that ChatGPT sometimes provides excessive information, to the point that where it becomes overwhelming. Therefore, I make sure to read through every answer it provides to filter out the excess).

Moreover, amidst the growing reliance on AI for learning tasks, users prioritized not only accuracy but also the effectiveness of responses in addressing their goals. This reflected a nuanced approach to information evaluation, where users sought comprehensive and actionable insights from AI-generated content. It underscored the evolving role of AI as a partner in learning, where users actively engaged in a dialogue with the technology to enhance their understanding and achieve desired outcomes. Participant 6 stated that:

“Every time na nagagamit ko ug ChatGPT for my learning task and activities, ang una jd nako gina consider is the relevance and accuracy being provided. Additionally, gina evaluate nako ang comprehensiveness sa response to ensure na effective sya and at the same time na address imohang tumong.” (IDI-06)

(Every time I use ChatGPT for my learning tasks and activities, my first consideration is the relevance and accuracy of the information it provides. Additionally, I evaluate the comprehensiveness of the response to ensure its effectiveness and that it addresses my goals).

Additionally, when it comes to using ChatGPT, the primary concern for users often revolves around the accuracy and reliability of the information it provides. Consequently, users make it a point to meticulously verify and understand the details shared by ChatGPT every time they consult it. This approach ensures that the information aligns accurately with their queries and needs. By leveraging ChatGPT, it is essential to critically evaluate and cross-reference the data obtained from AI, recognizing that while it can offer valuable insights, it is also susceptible to limitations and errors inherent to its programming and the data it has been trained on. As what participant 2 stated that:

“Haved only one consideration when it comes into using ChatGPT and that is the credibility of the information being provided by them so, if nakoy information na ma gather o makuha sa ChatGPT syempre akoo panang gina basa o ginasabot ug tama bana siya sa akoang mga gina pangutana or gina ask every time ug mag gamit ko ug ChatGPTt.” (FGD-02)

(I have only one consideration when it comes to using ChatGPT, and that is the credibility of the information provided by it. So, whenever I gather or obtain information from ChatGPT, I always make sure to read or understand if it is correct according to what I am asking or inquiring about every time I use ChatGPT).

Lastly, user emphasizes a cautious and discerning approach to utilizing ChatGPT's capabilities. They prioritize two key factors: credibility and relevance. By insisting on credibility, the user aims to ensure that the information provided by ChatGPT is reliable and accurate. This involves verifying the accuracy of the responses against other sources or their own knowledge. Additionally, the user stresses the importance of relevance, meaning that the information provided should directly address the topic or question at hand. By checking for relevance, the user ensures that the information aligns with their specific needs or inquiries, maximizing its usefulness. As what Participant 5 said that:

“So, when it comes sa considerations and measures, akoo always na gina consider when using ChatGPT kay kanang if naa koy e-search is basahon pa nako daan ang iyahang mogawas gud na mga ideas na ginahatag sa ChatGPT if credible ba siya and connected ba siya sa topic na akong gi send para makabalo ko na kani ba na information is makatabang pud ba sa akoo.” (FGD-05)

(When it comes to considerations and measures, I always take into account the credibility and relevance of the information provided by ChatGPT. Before accepting the information, I check if it is credible and if it is connected to the topic I have sent. This helps me

determine if the information is helpful to me).

Verify Given Information from Reliable Website. This is the seventh code from the first probed issue. In utilizing ChatGPT, participants assumed the responsibility of employing AI to advance their understanding by emphasizing the importance of sourcing information from reliable websites. They mentioned that the process was not merely about verifying the information but also about assessing the authority and trustworthiness of the source. This approach was crucial in both academic research and daily information consumption, where the accuracy of information could greatly influence decisions and beliefs. By leveraging ChatGPT, it was suggested that users were encouraged to look beyond the surface and evaluate the reliability of the source itself, which fostered a more discerning and critical online community.

In that since, users are actively verifying the information provided by ChatGPT against reliable websites and other sources. This practice is crucial, considering the AI's limitations in discerning the absolute accuracy and recency of its training data. By cross-referencing information, users can mitigate potential inaccuracies inherent in AI-generated responses. As what participant 2 said that:

“Para sa akong gusto like tama ang mga terms and grammar na iyang gi gamit, so maoto gina balik-balik sad pud jd nako’g basa ang iyang ginahatag na answer para sigurado.” (IDI-02)

(As a ChatGPT user, I always double-check the validity of the respond or information provided. I check to see if the information is consistent with other sources, sometimes using Google to cross-reference. Beforehand, I usually have an idea of whether something exists or not. I also consider the reasoning and logic in its responses, ensuring that they are consistent with what I am looking for, including the proper use of terminology and grammar. As a result, I often go back and read its responses several times to ensure accuracy.)

Similarly, the user focused on the relevance of ChatGPT's information, conducting diligent cross-references with reliable websites. This step-by-step verification ensures the information's pertinence to their needs. This targeted validation process showcases a methodical approach to ascertain the utility and applicability of AI-generated content, emphasizing the importance of relevance in information consumption and the value of external validation in confirming accuracy. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“My consideration and measures I always consider everytime I used ChatGPT is that considering the relevant of the information being given by the ChatGPT, and the way that I’ve measured is that step by step through search also from the other reliable websites like Google if that information coming from ChatGPT is relevant.” (IDI-05)

(My considerations and measures whenever I use ChatGPT include evaluating the relevance of the information it provides. I measure this by cross-referencing step by step and conducting searches on other reliable websites like Google to verify if the information from ChatGPT is indeed relevant).

Furthermore, in a landscape where AI-driven solutions proliferated, users exercised caution by supplementing AI-generated content with personal research and interpretation. This signified a broader trend of active participation in the learning process, where users took ownership of their knowledge acquisition. It reflected a shift towards a more empowered and critical approach to utilizing AI, where users harnessed technology as a tool to augment, rather than replace, their cognitive abilities and expertise. As what participant 1 stated:

“Every time na mag use konug ChatGPT, kabalo najud ko na dili solely mag rely kung unsa ang gi generate sa ChatGPT, so ang every answers is dapat e search pud nako individual kay para mas mo solid pa ang iyahang answer and then ang kada word pud, dili nako i copy word by word but also to like paraphrase it in my own words so thatthose are the considerations and measures that I do in using ChatGPT.” (FGD-01)

(Every time I used ChatGPT, I am aware that I should not solely rely on what it generates. Therefore, every answer should be individually researched to ensure its accuracy and reliability. Additionally, I do not copy the responses word for word; instead, I paraphrase them in my own words. These are the considerations and measures I take when using ChatGPT).

Moreover, users employed a multifaceted approach to validate information in a context where linguistic precision held great importance. By combining AI-driven tools with conventional methods, users aimed to achieve meticulous accuracy. This strategy showcased a broader trend towards hybrid learning, blending AI advancements with traditional techniques to enrich communication effectiveness. It emphasized the significance of considering both content substance and linguistic structure, reflecting a comprehensive endeavor to elevate the clarity and integrity of exchanged information.

“After using ChatGPT kanang e check sa nako siya through sa kanang mga website or apps na pang check sa grammars ug satanan nako nga na construct na sentence gikan sa ChatGPT para mas ma ano ba siya kong accurate ba gyud siya sakong questions or sa akong gipa answer.” (FGD-03)

(After using ChatGPT, I check it through websites or apps that check the grammar and structure of sentences constructed by ChatGPT to ensure accuracy in my questions or the answers I receive).

Additionally, users navigated the digital landscape by employing a combination of AI and traditional research methods. This reflected a pragmatic approach to information validation, where users sought to corroborate AI-generated content through external sources. It underscored a broader trend of digital fluency, where users leveraged technology as a means to access, evaluate, and apply information effectively in their endeavors. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Ang consideration nga akoang gina buhat when it comes on getting information from ChatGPT so akoo jud gina make sure nga, kuan na sya kanang reliable na siya nga idea, so akong gina buhat naga search pud ko sa Google, ug ang gina hatag ni ChatGPT ug tama ba, kuan pud kanang dapat dili lang pud ko mag salig nga mag gamit ug chatgpt, dapat mo gamit pud ko ug other resources para daghan kog information na ma gather.” (FGD-06)

(My consideration when it comes to getting information from ChatGPT is ensuring its reliability. So, what I do is I search on Google to verify if the information provided by ChatGPT is correct. I also make sure to not solely rely on ChatGPT; I use other resources to gather more information).

Lastly, as reliance on AI for information retrieval increased, users adopted comprehensive approaches to ensure knowledge integrity and depth. This reflected a proactive engagement with AI-driven solutions, where users verified information and deepened their understanding. It underscored a shift towards critical digital engagement, prioritizing accuracy, reliability, and comprehension in interactions with AI technologies.

“Para pud sa akoo my consideration and measures I always keep in mind when using ChatGPT for my learning tasks and activities. First is ang accuracy anf reliability jud sa response niya so I ensure that the information provided by ChatGPT is accurate and reliable by cross-referencing it with other credible sources or academic materials. This helps me maintain the quality of my work and avoid spreading misinformation. Ug second is understanding the concept jud, so before accepting ChatGPT's response, I make sure to understand the concepts thoroughly. If the answer seems unclear or ambiguous, so I take the time to research and clarify the topic further to ensure I grasp it fully.” (FGD-07)

(When using ChatGPT for learning tasks, I consider two important factors. Firstly, the accuracy and reliability of its responses. To ensure this, I cross-reference the information provided by ChatGPT with other credible sources or academic materials. This helps me maintain the quality of my work and avoid spreading misinformation. Secondly, understanding the concept is crucial. I thoroughly understand the concepts before accepting ChatGPT's response. If the answer seems unclear or ambiguous, I take the time to research and clarify the topic further to ensure a full grasp of it).

Develop One’s Writing Skills. Based on insights gathered from in-depth interviews and focused group discussions, it emerged that elementary education students underwent a transformative journey while refining their writing abilities. Key facets of this journey included mastering diverse writing styles, employing rephrasing and paraphrasing techniques, and utilizing tools such as Grammarly for grammatical accuracy. By immersing themselves in these processes, students broadened their understanding of written expression, fostering critical thinking and a deeper comprehension of topics. This holistic approach not only honed their writing skills but also empowered them to articulate ideas confidently and effectively.

Enhance Writing Skills. This is the eighth code from the first probed issue. Participants expressed using ChatGPT to elevate their writing proficiency and explore new styles, indicating its utility in various creative endeavors such as storytelling, poetry, and song composition. Moreover, they highlighted its role in bolstering confidence in grammar usage and refining essay construction. By leveraging ChatGPT, individuals not only enhance their writing skills but also gain access to valuable feedback and guidance, ultimately improving the quality of their written work.

Similarly, participant’s decision to utilize ChatGPT was driven by a personal goal of enhancing their writing skills and exploring new learning styles in writing. As someone who enjoyed writing stories, poems, and even composing songs, they viewed ChatGPT as a valuable tool for generating ideas and expanding their creative repertoire. By engaging with ChatGPT, they were able to explore different writing prompts, receive suggestions, and experiment with various writing techniques, thereby broadening their skill set and fostering their passion for writing. This highlighted how ChatGPT served as a versatile resource not only for academic tasks but also for personal growth and creative expression, offering opportunities for individuals to refine their craft and explore new avenues in their writing journey. As what Participant 1 said that:

“Personal reason nako sir nganung nag gamit ko ug Chatgpt is to enhance my writing skills, and try to learn a new learning style sir in writing po, since ako po is hilig mn ko mag sulat-sulat sir ba like mag buhat ug mga story, magbuhat ug poem, even mag composed ug kanta sad gani and also get ideas for assignments. So isa ang chatgpt sakong option para ana. Mao lang sir.” (IDI-01)

(My personal reason why I used ChatGPT is to enhance my writing skills and to try learning new style of writing. Since I like writing such as writing stories or even composing a song. Also, I used ChatGPT to gather ideas for my assignments. So ChatGPT is one of my options for that.)

Additionally, participants found ChatGPT helpful, particularly in terms of essay writing. There were times when they constructed essays without much confidence in their grammar or the adequacy of the information they included. In such instances, they could simply input their essay into ChatGPT, which would then correct their grammar and suggest additional information to enrich and

enhance the content of their essay, making it more comprehensive and polished. This illustrates how ChatGPT serves as a valuable writing assistant, providing support in refining language skills and improving the overall quality of written work. As what Participant 6 said that:

“Naka tabang jud ni siya, kay interms gani pud sa essay writing kay, kuan nay usahay na naga construct ko pag dili ko ingun confidence sa grammar na akong gi gamit ug dili kaayu kuan ang information nga akong gibutang sa akoang essay, pwede ra nako siya e kuan sa ChatGPT and then si ChatGPT nay bahala mo correct sa akoang grammars as well as mag add more information para mas kuan abundant ug kanang content ang akoang essay”. (FGD-06)

(It really helps me because, especially in terms of essay writing, there are times when I am not confident about the grammar I am using or I am not quite sure about the information I am putting in my essay. I can just input it into ChatGPT, and then ChatGPT can correct my grammar as well as add more information to make my essay more abundant and comprehensive).

To Elaborate and Acquire More Ideas and Understanding More Information. This is the ninth code from the first probed issue. Participants cited personal reasons for utilizing ChatGPT to streamline their academic workload and gain deeper insights into complex topics. They emphasized the efficiency of using ChatGPT for research purposes, particularly when faced with difficulty in elaborating ideas or understanding certain concepts. By leveraging ChatGPT's capabilities, individuals sought to expedite their learning process and enhance their understanding of various subjects, thus optimizing their time management and academic performance.

In connection to that, in the in-depth interview, participants emphasized the belief in working smarter rather than harder as students. They found ChatGPT to be an efficient tool for research, particularly when facing difficulties in elaborating ideas or understanding concepts. They appreciated the assistance provided by ChatGPT in overcoming moments of writer's block and expressed gratitude for its contribution to time management. As what participant 7 stated that:

“Personal reasons of using these one because I believed that as a student, I should act smarter not hard, so I mean why would I work hard, and think hard if there is an easy way, so easy way for me is to use ChatGPT, and by that specially doing my research via use ChatGPT is really help for me specially in elaborating my ideas so kong out of words nako then I could just ask help through ChatGPT and then I am very thankful for that and that is it my personal reason for my studies or my activities or anything na mapadali akong trabaho”. (IDI-07)

(Personal reasons for using ChatGPT stem from my belief that, as a student, working smarter, not harder, is key. Why put in excessive effort when there is an easier way? For me, that easier way is utilizing ChatGPT, especially for research purposes. It greatly aids in elaborating on my ideas. If I ever find myself struggling to articulate my thoughts, I can simply seek assistance through ChatGPT. I am immensely grateful for this convenience. This approach streamlines my studies and activities, making tasks easier to manage).

Similarly, an elementary education student echoed these sentiments, citing ChatGPT as a valuable tool in their academic pursuits. They expressed satisfaction with its usefulness in research activities, particularly in elaborating on ideas and overcoming moments of writer's block. They recognized the importance of time management and the role ChatGPT played in making their work more manageable and efficient. Participant 7 stated that:

I took satisfaction in using ChatGPT since it has proven to be really useful, particularly in my research activities. ChatGPT serves as a valuable tool for me, particularly in elaborating on my ideas and overcoming moments when I run out of words. I am grateful for its assistance in making my work more manageable and efficient. Time management is crucial for me, and if I encounter challenges, I do not hesitate to seek assistance, especially in this technologically advanced era. That is why ChatGPT has become an indispensable part of my studies and activities. (IDI-07).

Additionally, in focus-group discussion participant shared personal reasons for using ChatGPT, citing its usefulness in gaining additional information on complex topics. They utilized ChatGPT to improve their understanding of unfamiliar subjects, finding it helpful in clarifying concepts beyond their comprehension. As what Participant 5 said that:

“So for me my own and personal reasons in using ChatGPT maybe kanang kuan para maka gain ug additional information on a certain topic para mas masabtan nako kong kani nga topic, for example, kaning dili kayko kasabot ani. So akoa siyang gina search sa ChatGPT para mas maka sabot ko kong unsa na siya na topic.” (FGD-05)

(My own personal reasons for using ChatGPT include gaining additional information on a certain topic to better understand it. For example, if there is a topic I do not quite comprehend, I search for it using ChatGPT to gain a better understanding).

Furthermore, another focus group participant shared their experience with using ChatGPT, especially when information found through conventional search engines was insufficient or hard to understand. They appreciated how ChatGPT could break down concepts and topics into more digestible explanations, making it easier to grasp the information they needed. This participant's experience underscores ChatGPT's role in making learning more accessible and less daunting. As what participant 6 stated that:

“My personal reason on using ChatGPT is there are times nga kanang ang makuha nako sa Google nga mga information is para sa akoa is dili enough ug napud uban na lisod siya sabton so akong gina buhat, naga utilize ko sa ChatGPT kay sa ChatGPT man gud murag e-explain jud ug unsa jd na nga concept, unsa na nga topic, ug tungod para sa akoa dali nalang siya sabton ang mga information ba na

akong nakuha.” (FGD-06)

(My personal reason for using ChatGPT is that sometimes the information I find on Google is insufficient, and some topics are difficult to understand. So what I do is I utilize ChatGPT because it really explains the concepts and topics thoroughly. For me, it is easier to comprehend the information I gather through ChatGPT).

Development of students' Personal Skills. Based on the information gleaned from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it was found that elementary education students actively engaged in honing their personal skills through various means. The use of ChatGPT, characterized by its ability to aid in understanding complex topics, provide comprehensive answers, and facilitate easy comprehension of information, played a pivotal role in this development. Moreover, ChatGPT simplified learning tasks, making them more manageable and less burdensome for students. Its assistance in essay writing and research further enhanced students' grammar and sentence construction skills, instilling confidence in their writing abilities. Thus, ChatGPT served as a valuable tool in scaffolding the development of students' personal skills, contributing significantly to their academic journey.

Assist in Understanding the Concepts. This is the tenth code from the second probed issue. Participants highlighted the positive impact of using ChatGPT in aiding their academic pursuits. They emphasized its role as a valuable tool for brainstorming ideas, providing writing support, and assisting in research tasks. ChatGPT was credited with simplifying complex topics, improving time management, and enhancing comprehension, especially in tasks such as assignment completion and constructing grammatically correct sentences. Users appreciated its ability to promptly address challenging queries and deliver precise information, facilitating a deeper understanding of subjects. Overall, participants regarded ChatGPT as an indispensable resource for streamlining tasks and expanding their knowledge base, ultimately contributing to their academic success.

Similarly, Given the observations made, it's evident that ChatGPT played a crucial role in facilitating the academic journey. Acting as a versatile tool, it supported brainstorming sessions, provided writing assistance, and aided in research endeavors. Reflecting on this experience revealed a noticeable reduction in hurdles associated with understanding intricate subjects and organizing activities. Previously daunting tasks like assignment completion and crafting grammatically sound sentences became more approachable with ChatGPT's assistance. Consequently, its contribution substantially bolstered proficiency in these domains. As what Participant 1 said that:

“Positive for me sir na nahatag sa akong student when it comes using ChatGPT in making my stuffs is that ChatGPT serves as a helpful tool for me, for brainstorming ideas po, writing support, and my research assistant po, ug I compare tong sa una ug karon is easy nalng po sako sa karon na ma overcome tong mga butang or topic gani sir na naglisod ko sa pagsabot, and also sakong mga activities, labi na sa pag buhat ug assignment or pag construct ug grammar and sa proper way of constructing a sentence sir ba, mag struggle mn ko usahay ana, so chatgpt helps me a lot jd to improve a lot pajd”. (IDI-01)

(ChatGPT has been very helpful as a student in various aspects. It serves as a valuable tool for brainstorming ideas, providing writing support, and acting as my research assistant. When I compare my experience before and now, things have become easier for me to overcome, especially in understanding complex topics and managing my activities. This is particularly evident in tasks like assignment completion and constructing grammatically correct sentences, where I used to struggle. ChatGPT has played a significant role in helping me improve in these areas).

Moreover, upon reflecting on the experience with ChatGPT, it becomes apparent that it presented both significant advantages and some limitations. Notably, one of its most significant strengths lay in the comprehensive assistance it offered, especially when encountering challenging queries or uncertainties. ChatGPT demonstrated remarkable capability in addressing nearly every question posed to it, thus significantly aiding in overcoming obstacles during academic pursuits. As what Participant 3 stated:

“So based sakong paggamit ug ChatGPT maka ingun jd ko nga naa siyay pros and cons. Ang pros is that dako jud kaayu siyag tabang, specially kong naa koy I search na mga questions or lisod sabton ang ChatGPT man gud bisan unsa mga questions imong I pangutana tubagon jd na niya”. (IDI-03)

(Based on my experience with ChatGPT, I can conclude that it has both advantages and disadvantages. The benefits include much assistance, particularly when I have challenging queries or concerns. ChatGPT can answer nearly every question I pose).

Additionally, elementary education students benefit from the positive aspect highlighted, which is the perceived utility of the information acquired for academic studies, coupled with the ease with which it can be comprehended. This underscores the valuable role that ChatGPT plays in facilitating understanding and accessibility of relevant information, thereby contributing to the academic endeavors of the users. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“I guessed the positive one is the information na akong makuha and I can easily understand sa mga mahatag niya nga mga information”. (IDI-04)

(I believed the positive aspect is the usefulness of the informations I obtain for my studies, and I can easily understand the provided information.)

Furthermore, ChatGPT has played a significant role in facilitating academic endeavors. Particularly, it has simplified the process of

digesting complex material, making it easier for users to grasp difficult concepts. For instance, when faced with learning activities or challenging topics, ChatGPT provided instant access to precise ideas with just a single click. This convenience has undoubtedly contributed to a more efficient and effective learning experience for students. Participant 5 stated that:

“Ang nahatag na positive sa amoa as a user or as a student, is dali nalang para sa amoa ang ma process ang some information tungod sa aning ChatGPT. For example, naay learning task na ipubuhay, unya usahay maglisod kog sabot sa mga topic, so salamat sa ChatGPT kay one click lang mo hatag nadayon syan precise na mga ideas.” (IDI-05)

(ChatGPT has had a beneficial influence on us as users or students since it has made digesting specific material simpler. For example, when presented with a learning activity and trying to grasp particular concepts, ChatGPT allows us to instantly acquire exact thoughts with a single click.)

In connection to this, the impact of ChatGPT was evident in its remarkable ability to simplify tasks and clarify ideas, especially when users encountered difficulties in expressing themselves. ChatGPT consistently astonished with its capabilities, effectively articulating thoughts that were challenging to convey. This proficiency in understanding and responding to complex queries undoubtedly enhanced the overall user experience, making ChatGPT an invaluable tool for academic pursuits. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“So for me, as a student the positive impact of it, is it really helps me a lot para mapadali ang mga gawain ko, mga task ko, and for illustrating my ideas when I am out of words, and the ChatGPT is really amazing when mo pop yong answer niya is that mapa-ingun nalang jud ka na wow that's the word that I think I cannot brust it out, so yun.” (IDI-07)

(It greatly facilitates my tasks and assignments, making them more manageable. When I find myself struggling to articulate my ideas, ChatGPT comes to the rescue by providing insightful responses. The way ChatGPT generates answers sometimes leaves me in awe, as it often delivers exactly the word or phrase I could not seem to express myself. It is truly remarkable).

Lastly, the impact of employing ChatGPT extended beyond mere convenience, significantly benefiting students in their academic pursuits. By serving as a reliable resource, ChatGPT facilitated the expansion of knowledge by furnishing relevant and valuable information. This access to a wealth of insights not only streamlined tasks but also enriched the learning experience, empowering students to delve deeper into their studies and explore diverse topics with confidence. Thus, ChatGPT emerged as an indispensable tool for academic growth, equipping students with the resources they need to thrive in their educational journey. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“So for me the positive impact of using ChatGPT is that it makes more think convenient most especially sa mga students parehas sa akoo, then and aside from that kay kanang when using ChatGPT man gud pwede ma broaden imonghang knowledge sa mga imong gina ask sa iya, kay naga provide man siyag information nga relevant and kanang magamit pud juf nimo”. (FGD-02)

(The positive impact of using ChatGPT is that it makes things more convenient, especially for me us as a student. Additionally, using ChatGPT can broaden your knowledge on topics you inquire about, as it provides relevant information that you can utilize).

Making the Learning Process Easy. This is the eleventh code from the second probed issue. Participants highlighted ChatGPT's positive impact in simplifying tasks, such as assignments and research, making them more manageable and efficient. They appreciated how ChatGPT provided instant ideas and accurate responses, especially when they were struggling to articulate their thoughts. Additionally, participants praised ChatGPT for its creativity and helpfulness in writing essays and addressing challenging questions, describing it as a smart and invaluable resource for students.

Similarly, when faced with the frustration of articulating thoughts, ChatGPT emerged as a trusted ally, effortlessly providing instant ideas and precise responses. Each encounter left them in awe of ChatGPT's uncanny ability to verbalize what seemed impossible to express. Such seamless assistance not only lightened their academic load but also boosted their confidence in navigating complex challenges efficiently, marking a significant shift in their learning experience. As what participant 7 stated that:

“As a student the positive impact of it, is it really helps me a lot para mapadali ang mga gawain ko, mga task ko, and for illustrating my ideas when I am out of words, and the ChatGPT is really amazing when mo pop yong answer niya is that mapa-ingun nalang jud ka na wow that is the word that I think I cannot brust it out, so yun.” (IDI-07)

(As a student, the positive impact of using ChatGPT is tremendous. It significantly aids in simplifying my tasks and assignments, making them more manageable. Moreover, when I find myself struggling to articulate my ideas, ChatGPT serves as a valuable tool for expression. It is ability to generate responses often leaves me astonished, providing me with the precise words or phrases that I could not seem to conjure up myself. It is truly remarkable).

Moreover, another participant underscored the pivotal role of ChatGPT in expediting the research process. They contextualized how the AI tool facilitated a significant acceleration in research pace, enabling students to access information swiftly and enhance their scholarly pursuits. This streamlined approach not only saved crucial time but also empowered students to delve deeper into their academic inquiries, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. Through ChatGPT's assistance, students could navigate the intricacies of scholarly exploration with agility and precision, thereby elevating the quality of their academic endeavors. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“In terms of positive impact, it makes the students’ task must easier the research more faster”. (FGD-01)

(In terms of positive impact, ChatGPT makes students' tasks much easier and research faster).

Additionally, amid a focused group discussion on educational aids, a participant shed light on ChatGPT's profound impact on the learning journey. They contextualized how the AI tool significantly eased the process of addressing questions and tasks assigned by instructors. By providing prompt and accurate responses, ChatGPT emerged as an indispensable companion in navigating academic challenges. Its role in simplifying complex concepts and elucidating intricate queries not only streamlined the learning process but also empowered students to engage more effectively with their coursework. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“So positive impact sa ChatGPT and when utilizing ChatGPT mas mapadali nako ug tubag ang akoang mga questions ug mga task na ginahatag sa amoang instructors. (FGD-03)

(The positive impact of using ChatGPT lies in its ability to simplify and speed up answering my questions and completing tasks assigned by my instructors).

Furthermore, building on the group's discourse, another participant articulated their perspective on ChatGPT's positive influence on student learning within the broader context of academic support systems. They commended the AI tool for its invaluable assistance, particularly in generating instant ideas and delivering accurate responses. ChatGPT's prowess in essay writing and adeptness in tackling challenging questions emerged as noteworthy attributes. By serving as a reliable resource for academic endeavors, ChatGPT played a pivotal role in enhancing students' learning experiences within the dynamic landscape of modern education. Its ability to provide timely guidance and support not only facilitated academic success but also instilled a sense of confidence in students' abilities to overcome academic hurdles with ease, thus enriching their educational journey. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“For me ang positive na akong nakita is ChatGPT is very helpful jud sya sa among mga studyante labi na sa akoo, kay ang ChatGPT man gud mo hatag jud syag mga instant na ideas gani and most sa iyang response accurate pud, ug good jud kaayung ChatGPT kay natabangan jud ko niya like for writing essays ug sa mga assignment kay super creative jud iyang response, ug mas mahatagan jud niyang tubag imong mga pangutana ug mag lisod ka. (FGD-07)

(Positive thing I have noticed is that ChatGPT is very helpful to our students, especially to me. ChatGPT provides instant ideas and most of its responses are accurate. ChatGPT is really good because it has helped me a lot with writing essays and assignments; its responses are super creative. It also helps a lot when you are struggling to come up with answers to your questions).

Scaffold Writing Skill Development. This is the twelfth code from the second probed issue. Participants highlighted the positive impact of ChatGPT in scaffolding their writing skills by providing assistance with homework, personal learning, and essay construction. They emphasized how ChatGPT streamlines tasks, enhances productivity, and improves critical thinking skills by facilitating quick access to information and aiding in grammar correction. Overall, ChatGPT serves as a valuable tool in making writing tasks more manageable and helping students achieve higher scores in assignments.

Similarly, in today's educational landscape, students often face an overwhelming amount of academic tasks. With the integration of technology like ChatGPT, students can access instant support for writing assignments. This assistance is especially valuable in the digital age, where information is abundant but sometimes challenging to navigate. By utilizing ChatGPT, students can efficiently address their writing needs, leading to enhanced learning outcomes and academic success. As what Participant 2 said that:

“Para sa akoo kong sa postive ta mag una , una jd ana is maka tabang jd sya sa akong mga homeworks and also my personal learning, labo na sa pagbuhat ug assignment or mag create ug essay dali rajd kaayu nya ha-om pud sya ug unsay gusto nimo na tubang nga makuha sa imong gi pangutana. ikaduha ana is sapaggamit nakog chatgpt na enhance sad akong critical thingking sapagsabot sa mga pangutana nga lisod gud sya sabton sa uban like mag hatag pajd kag dagahn oras para lang sa isa ka questions para matubag, tungod aning chatgpt napadali nalg sa akoo tanan.” (IDI-02)

(The positive aspect of ChatGPT comes first in helping me significantly with my homework and personal learning, especially in doing assignments or creating essays. It is extremely user-friendly and helps to quickly find answers to the questions I have. Moreover, ChatGPT has improved my critical thinking skills by allowing me to understand complex questions that others find difficult to answer. It also saves a substantial amount of time compared to spending hours on a single question. Therefore, ChatGPT has undoubtedly made everything much easier for me.)

Moreover, in an era marked by rapid technological advancements, students are increasingly turning to AI-powered tools like ChatGPT to augment their learning experience. By leveraging these tools, students can overcome common writing challenges such as grammar errors and information synthesis. This not only enhances the quality of their work but also fosters critical thinking skills as they engage with complex topics more effectively. As such, ChatGPT serves as a valuable ally in students' academic journey, empowering them to achieve their full potential. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“This serve as my partner to help to enhance my productivity like constructing a grammar, and sentences. Aside pajud ana using ChatGPT dali lang ta maka kuhag answer or information isa lang kapangutana nimo mo hatag dayon syag best answer. Napansin sad nako nga na improve jud akong mga learning task labi na sapag construct ug grammar, unya well construct najd kaysa nya mas ni

increase pagd akong confident kay naka gain mn kog dako na score sakong mga task”. (IDI-06)

(It serves as a helpful partner in enhancing my productivity, particularly in constructing grammar and sentences. Using ChatGPT also allows me to quickly obtain answers or information with just a single question, providing me with the best response. I have observed improvements in my learning tasks, especially in constructing grammar, resulting in well-constructed outputs. This has boosted my confidence and contributed to higher scores in my tasks.)

Additionally, the student expressed gratitude for ChatGPT's assistance, particularly in the context of World Literature studies. By facilitating essay construction, ChatGPT enabled the student to navigate complex literary concepts more effectively. This personalized support not only streamlined the writing process but also enriched the student's understanding of the subject matter, highlighting the transformative impact of AI technology on education. As what Participant said that:

“As a student kay dako siya nga tabang sa akua especially karon nga naa mi kanang subject sa world literature, so ang ChatGPT is nakatabang siya sa akua, like to construct kanang mga essay kanang mga ana gud.” (FGD-05)

(As a student, ChatGPT has been a big help to me, especially now that we have a subject on world literature. ChatGPT has assisted me in constructing essays and forming coherent ideas).

In connection to that, the participant acknowledged ChatGPT's instrumental role in essay writing, particularly in addressing grammar issues and enriching content. By leveraging ChatGPT's capabilities, the student could refine their essays and ensure clarity and coherence in their writing. This personalized feedback not only improved the quality of the student's work but also instilled a sense of confidence, illustrating the transformative potential of AI technology in supporting student learning.

“So, in terms of positive impact kay naka tabang jud ni siya, kay interms gani pud sa essay writing kay, kuan nay usahay na naga construct ko pag dili ko ingun confidence sa grammar na akong gi gamit ug dili kaayu kaun ang information nga akong gibutang sa akoang essay, pwede ra nako siya e-kuan sa ChatGPT then si ChatGPT nay bahala mo correct sa akoang grammars as well as mag add more information para mas kuan abundant ug kanang content ang akoang essay”. (FGD-06)

(So, in terms of its positive impact, ChatGPT has been really helpful. Especially in essay writing, there are times when I lack confidence in my grammar usage and may not be entirely sure about the information I include in my essay. In such cases, I can simply input my content into ChatGPT, and it takes my grammar address mistakes as well as adding more information to enrich the content of my essay).

Degrading Higher Order Thinking Skills. Based on insights gathered from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it was evident that elementary education students faced challenges related to over-reliance on AI, leading to a degradation of critical thinking and comprehension skills. The findings suggested that students tended to depend excessively on AI for answers, neglecting to utilize their own knowledge and thinking abilities. This reliance on AI not only limited their exposure to diverse perspectives but also hampered their effort and personal involvement in learning. Consequently, students might have exhibited a lack of originality, diminished faith in their own judgment, and a reluctance to seek information from varied sources. This trend highlighted a concerning decline in higher-order thinking skills among elementary education students.

Over-Reliance on AI Assistance. This was the thirteenth code from the second probed issues. Participants expressed concerns about becoming overly reliant on ChatGPT, noting that they tended to use it for every question, even for simple ones, which could lead to a decrease in critical thinking skills. This over-reliance on ChatGPT may have hindered the development of essential research skills and limited students' ability to seek information from diverse sources.

Similarly, during discussions, a participant shared insights into the adverse effects of relying too heavily on technology. They expressed concerns about their own over-dependence, noting a tendency to excessively rely on ChatGPT. This individual admitted to frequently resorting to the AI tool for answers to various questions, regardless of the level of difficulty, all in an effort to speed up the completion of tasks. As what Participant 2 said that:

“Sa negative side pud ani niya na nakita nako sakong pag gamit is kuan lang naging overly reliant nako sa tech like tnan pangutana bisan simple ra tubagon mag ChatGPT dayon ko para mapadali lang ang tanan.” (IDI-02)

(However, I have noticed that using of ChatGPT has made me overly reliant on technology. I tend to use ChatGPT for every question, even the simplest ones, to make everything faster and easier. While it simplifies things and makes my work easier).

Additionally, participant reflected on the negative impact of their dependence on ChatGPT's answers, highlighting a lack of reliance on their own critical thinking skills. They expressed concern over their tendency to solely rely on ChatGPT for answers, indicating a diminished engagement of their own analytical abilities. As what Participant 4 said that:

And the negative is kanang mag rely ko sa answer na iyang gi hatag, kumbaga dili nako mag gamit ug critical thinking kumbaga sa ChatGPT nako mag rely jud.” (IDI-04)

(On the negative side, relying on the answers it gives means I may not use critical thinking; in other words, I depend on ChatGPT rather than engaging in critical thinking).

Furthermore, the participant highlighted another negative aspect of over-reliance on AI assistance, pointing out that they sometimes refrained from conducting thorough research themselves because they relied solely on ChatGPT to construct answers. This dependency on ChatGPT resulted in a reduction of their own efforts, as they no longer felt the need to extend themselves in seeking information independently. This observation underscores how over-reliance on AI tools like ChatGPT can lead to a passive approach to learning and diminish the motivation to engage in critical thinking and independent research. As what participant 5 stated that:

“Sa negative pud nay usahay na magsalig nalang ko dili nako mag research pag maayo kay tungod sa ChatGPT siya nalang mag construct ug answer, so ang impact sa atoa nay usahay na maka tapol jd sya na dle nata ma extend ug effort ba.” (IDI-05)

(On the downside, there are instances when I depend completely on ChatGPT without doing much investigation. This can have an influence on us by reducing our capacity to put in additional effort to comprehend the issue in depth).

Lastly, participant in focus-group discussion raised concerns regarding the negative impact of excessive reliance on ChatGPT. They noted a tendency among students to heavily depend on ChatGPT for various aspects of their studies, bypassing traditional methods such as reading books, seeking advice from others, or conducting research on Google. This direct dependence on ChatGPT could potentially limit students' exposure to diverse sources of information and critical thinking opportunities, leading to a narrow approach to learning.

“The negative impact is that student tends to be more more reliant on the ChatGPT and then everything related to their studies kuan kanang diretsoon na nila sa ChatGPT dili katong mga daan na ways na mag read pa through books, mag ask pa through other people, or mag research sa google na normal, karon deritsoon na kaayu ChatGPT.” (FGD-01)

(The negative impact is that students tend to become overly reliant on ChatGPT for everything related to their studies. They may skip the traditional methods of reading through books, asking others for help, or conducting research on Google. Instead, they go directly to ChatGPT for solutions).

Similarly, apprehensions about relying solely on ChatGPT highlighted a perceived lack of effort and initiative, as students tend to rely solely on the answers provided by ChatGPT without exerting additional effort to expand their understanding or explore alternative sources of information. This reliance on ChatGPT as the sole source of answers may hinder students' willingness to engage in independent learning and critical thinking, potentially limiting their overall academic growth and development. As participant 3 stated that:

“Ang negative kay mag rely lang mi sa ChatGPT murag mag salig lang mi so murag dili name mag exceed ug effort, didto lang mi mag rely rami sa gihatag na answer sa ChatGPT na among gi pa answeran.” (FGD-03)

(The negative aspect is that we just rely on ChatGPT, it is like we are only depending on it, so it seems like we do not put in extra effort. We just rely on the answers given by ChatGPT to our questions).

Additionally, a participant in focus-group discussion the negative consequences of the ease with which information can be obtained through ChatGPT. They expressed concerns about becoming overly dependent on the tool, which may lead to a decline in their ability to gather information from various sources independently. This overreliance on ChatGPT could hinder the development of their research skills and limit their ability to critically evaluate information, ultimately impeding their overall learning experience. As what Participant 6 said that:

“Then for the negative side pud nay usahay, tungod kay dali nalang kaayu ma kuan makuha ang information using ChatGPT, murag kanang kuan bitaw dependent napud ko ani ba, so dili nakay nako magamit akong skill to gather my information on different kind of sources, kay wla man, kanang naa namay ChatGPT then deretso nalang e ask nalang nimong question tubagon ra niya.” (FGD-06)

(Then for the downside, sometimes it is because information can easily be obtained using ChatGPT, it is like I have become dependent on it, so I no longer use my skills to gather information from different kinds of sources. Because, you see, there is already ChatGPT, and you can just directly ask your question and it will just answer it).

Degrading Critical Thinking and Comprehension. This was the fourteenth code from the second probed issue. This was observed as a negative aspect by participants, as they mentioned the instances of over-reliance on ChatGPT for decision-making and idea generation. Some participants acknowledged that they occasionally neglected fairness and responsibility towards others due to their reliance on technology, leading to doubts about others' opinions and a preference for individual work in group activities to ensure accuracy. Additionally, participants highlighted how overuse of ChatGPT could lead to a decline in their ability to articulate their own ideas and spell out concepts, as they became accustomed to relying on ChatGPT's responses without engaging in conceptualization. This trend was seen as potentially detrimental to developing critical thinking skills, as participants expressed concerns about being less open to using their own judgment and relying too heavily on ChatGPT's input.

Similarly, during discussions, a participant shared insights into the adverse effects of relying too heavily on technology. They expressed concerns about their own over-dependence, noting a tendency to excessively rely on ChatGPT. This individual admitted to frequently resorting to the AI tool for answers to various questions, regardless of the level of difficulty, all in an effort to speed up the completion of tasks.

As what Participant 2 said that:

“Negative side sad sir kuan lang ga rely ko sa chatgpt sakong mga decision making in life po like wla na nako napanatili ang pagiging fair sa uban or responsible gud sapagamit ug tech akoo is na over used najud , some instances is dle ko mo tuo sa uban ug maghatag ig idea, mag duha2 gani kog tuo sir or sahay dili nako maminaw sa opinion sa uban samot na sa group activity ,mas gustohon nako sir na mag individual lang kay mas masigurado nako nga akong answer or mga ideas is tama para sa akoo.” (IDI-01)

(On the negative side, I sometimes find myself relying too much on ChatGPT for decision-making in life. There are instances where I may neglect the importance of being fair to others or responsibly using technology, as I tend to overuse it. I also admit that I might doubt others' opinions and prefer to work individually in group activities to ensure that my answers or ideas are accurate according to my understanding).

Additionally, the response delves into the participant's recognition of a significant downside of relying heavily on ChatGPT. It articulates how this reliance can lead to a detachment from one's own thought process, as individuals may become accustomed to simply typing out the responses generated by the AI without actively engaging in the conceptualization of their ideas. By emphasizing this tendency, the response highlights the importance of maintaining a balance between utilizing AI assistance and fostering personal agency and creativity in communication. It suggests that over-reliance on AI can potentially hinder individuals' ability to express themselves authentically and independently, emphasizing the need for users to remain actively involved in the generation and articulation of their own ideas. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“And the negative impact of using ChatGPT is that am, may time kasi na I realized, way back in last year na nag rely nako sa chatgpt, usahay wla nakoy words to spell it out kong unsa akong idea, kay ga rely nalng ko sa chatgpt kay ni type nalng ko kong unsa iyang gi hatag without conceptualizing it”. (IDI-07)

(The negative impact of using ChatGPT is that there are times when I realized, especially looking back at last year, that I have become reliant on ChatGPT. Sometimes, I no longer have the words to spell out what my idea is, because I just rely on ChatGPT and type whatever it provides without really conceptualizing it myself).

Furthermore, the individual elaborates on the negative impact of their reliance on ChatGPT. They express that while they initially believed it could assist in constructing essays, they've realized they've started relying too heavily on it. Consequently, they feel they're no longer using their own ideas and are unable to construct their own thoughts. This highlights a loss of personal agency and creativity, as they feel disconnected from their own intellectual process due to over-reliance on AI assistance.

“And when it comes naman sa negative impact ani kay syempre akong ingun ganina na makatabang siya no na mo construct essay so murag nag rely nako sa iyaha so wla na murag wla na nako gi gamit akong ideas wla nako nako naka construct ug akong own ideas.” (FGD-05)

(And when it comes to the negative impact of this, of course, as what I have mentioned earlier, it can help in constructing essays, so it is like I have become more reliant on it. So, it is as if I am no longer using my own ideas, I am not able to construct my own ideas anymore).

Lastly, the individual reflects on the negative aspect of their reliance on ChatGPT, resonating with the concerns expressed by others. They acknowledge that they, too, have become dependent on ChatGPT and have consequently become less inclined to utilize their own critical thinking skills. This admission reveals a deeper issue of diminished confidence in their own intellectual capabilities, as they often default to accepting whatever responses ChatGPT provides without engaging in their own analytical processes. This reluctance to exercise independent critical thinking signifies a potential erosion of their ability to reason and problem-solve autonomously, further emphasizing the need to reassess the balance between AI assistance and personal cognitive engagement. As participant 7 said that:

“Sa negative pud na side sama sa ilang gi ingun, ako pud ga rely nako ug ChatGPT, and then mas dili nako open to use my own critical thinking kay mag salig mn ko sahay pud kong unsa lang iyang gina feed.” (FGD-07)

(On the negative side, like what they mentioned, I also find myself relying on ChatGPT, and I become less open to using my own critical thinking because I sometimes just trust whatever it feeds me).

Lost Confidence in One's Own Thoughts. This was the fifteenth code from the second probed issue. Participants expressed concerns about relying too heavily on ChatGPT, which led to a loss of trust in their own ideas and originality. They noted a tendency to automatically accept ChatGPT's answers instead of formulating their own opinions. Furthermore, participants highlighted the risk of becoming lazy and resorting to cheating by copying and pasting ChatGPT's responses without genuine engagement. This over-reliance on ChatGPT was seen as detrimental to personal growth and the development of critical thinking skills.

Similarly, the individual highlights a significant downside of their reliance on ChatGPT, which is the loss of confidence in their own thoughts and ideas. They express that instead of trusting and valuing their personal opinions, they have become dependent on the answers provided by ChatGPT. This shift has led to a diminished self-reliance where they increasingly lean on externally generated responses rather than developing and expressing their unique perspectives. This over-dependence not only impacts their self-esteem but also inhibits their ability to engage critically and independently with various topics and decisions. As Participant 3 said that:

“While ang cons para nako kay nawad-an ko’g salig sakong kaugalinong ug kauglingong idea, kay mag agad nalng mn ko sa answer sa ChatGPT dili na sa akong personal openion.” (IDI-03)

(On the other side, the disadvantages for me are losing faith in my own senses and personal views. I usually rely on ChatGPT for replies rather than establishing my own ideas).

Additionally, the participant highlights a significant downside to using ChatGPT, noting that it leads to a loss of originality due to over-reliance on the AI’s responses. This dependency on pre-generated answers diminishes personal input and creativity, fostering a tendency to bypass the critical thinking process. Furthermore, the participant identifies an ethical issue, equating the act of copying and pasting AI-generated answers to cheating. This not only skirts the educational value of tasks but also raises concerns about the integrity and authenticity of their work, reflecting a problematic aspect of AI dependence. As Participant 6 said that:

“Negative side pud using ChatGPT para sa akoa is maga rely on nalang ko sa iya, wala natay originality kay gasalig nalang manta sa ChatGPT. Second one is mahulog sad ni siyag cheating, kay naga copy and paste nalng mn ta ug unsa iyang gina hatag na answer.” (IDI-06)

(However, there are negative aspects to using ChatGPT. One concern is the tendency to overly rely on it, potentially diminishing originality since trust is placed solely in ChatGPT. Another issue is the risk of falling into the trap of cheating, as there is a temptation to simply copy and paste the provided answers).

Furthermore, the participant delves into a significant downside of their reliance on ChatGPT, emphasizing how it has fostered a sense of laziness in their approach to activities and quizzes. This admission reflects a broader concern about the impact of technological dependence on personal motivation and engagement. By consistently turning to ChatGPT for answers, the participant has inadvertently cultivated a habit of passivity, wherein they no longer feel compelled to actively participate in the learning process. This reliance on immediate, AI-generated responses can lead to a reduction in effort and initiative, as the participant may prioritize convenience over genuine intellectual engagement. As Participant 4 said that:

“The negative is I became lazy because nag salig rako sa ChatGPT na mo answer sakong activities and quizzes”. (FGD-04)

(The negative aspect is that I have become lazy because I rely on ChatGPT to answer my activities and quizzes).

Enhancing Comprehension and Cultivating the Habit of Reading. Insights from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions revealed that elementary education students actively cultivated a reading habit. They demonstrated proficiency in paraphrasing and rephrasing AI-generated responses, indicating a strong inclination towards deep understanding of content. Emphasizing the importance of specific prompts, they aimed for accuracy with precise inquiries. Answers were cross-verified with external sources, and grammar checkers were employed for accuracy. Prioritizing articulation in their own words underscored the significance of clearly defined queries. The use of ChatGPT in these practices underscored students' dedication to enhancing their reading and comprehension abilities.

Doing Paraphrasing and Rephrasing. Participants highlighted the importance of paraphrasing and rephrasing when using ChatGPT to ensure effectiveness and efficiency. They emphasized the need to avoid directly copying ChatGPT's answers and instead opt for rephrasing or replacing certain words to add depth and maintain originality. By rephrasing, participants aimed to simplify complex terms and enhance understanding, ensuring that the responses are accurate and clear.

Similarly, since ChatGPT provides continuous responses, the participant in the in-depth interview underscored the importance of employing specific strategies and techniques to ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of utilizing ChatGPT. Emphasizing the significance of avoiding direct replication of the AI’s responses, the participant advocated for rephrasing or substituting certain words to uphold originality and depth. By being mindful of the need to gather answers and ensure accuracy, the participant highlighted the importance of revising ChatGPT’s responses thoroughly in reading. Emphasizing the necessity of checking for correctness and accuracy to guarantee that the provided answers align with the intended context and requirements. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“Ang strategy and techniques jd akong gina gamit sir sapag gamit aning chatgpt para mahimong effective and efficient is, dle nimo i copy dayong iyang answer na gihatag sir dapat e-rephrase or pulihan jd nimong uban words ana na lalom rakaayu kay mawla nasad atong pagka originality ana, so minful ta satong pag gather sa answer kay dle tanan result na iyang gi hatag jd accurate, importante jd gihapon na najd revesion sa mga answer nga gi hatag sa chatgpt, e- check jd ug tama ba ug accurate ba iyang mga answers.”(IDI-01)

(My strategy and techniques for using ChatGPT effectively and efficiently include not copying its answers directly. Instead, I rephrase or replace certain words to add depth and avoid losing originality. It is crucial to be mindful when gathering answers since not all results from ChatGPT are accurate. It is essential to carefully revise the answers it provides, checking for correctness and accuracy).

Moreover, it further emphasized the importance of rephrasing the words provided by ChatGPT, particularly those that contain complex terms that are difficult to understand and articulate. Participant stated about challenging part in grappling with intricate terms and indicated that they often seek clarification on which words could be replaced or substituted to facilitate better comprehension and accuracy in their responses. By refining the answers generated by ChatGPT through reading in order to ensure they are clear, understandable, and aligned with the intended context. By actively engaging in this process of refinement, the participant demonstrates a commitment to enhancing the quality and accuracy of their interactions with ChatGPT. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Gina rephrase sad nako tong mga words na gihatag niya na lalom na gani kaayu nya mga terms na lisod napud gani sabton ,then mag ask nasad ko ug unsa tong mga words na pwede mapuli,or i replace para dali ra masabtan and ma na acurate akong mga answers.” (IDI-02)

(I also rephrase the words provided by ChatGPT, espicially when it uses complex terms that may be difficult to understand. Additionally, asking alternative words that can replace for a clearer and more accurate responses).

In addition, participant engages in the practice of rephrasing paragraphs to further enhance the simplicity and comprehensibility of the text. To facilitate this process of rephrasing, they incorporate the use of paraphrasing tools, such as QuillBot, indicating a resourceful approach to achieving a more digestible and precise expression of ideas. This method showcases the participant's proactive efforts in refining the information received from ChatGPT, tailoring it to better meet their specific needs and preferences for clear and effective communication. As what Participant 5 said that:

“The strategy and techniques when I am using ChatGPT is that I am usually avoid very complex words known as flowering words and isa pa pud sa gina buhat nako gina rephrase nako ang paragraph. And isa pud sa way na ma rephrase ang isa ka paragraph is gagamit pud ko ug mga paraphrasing tool, such as Quillbot.” (IDI-05)

(My strategy and techniques when using ChatGPT include avoiding ovely complex or estabellished language, also know as ‘flowering words.’ Additionally, I rephrase the paragraphs to simplyfy them, I also I take to rephrase a paragraph by using paraphrasing tools, such as Quillbot).

Moreover, the participant outlines their strategy and approach when utilizing ChatGPT, emphasizing a focus on utilizing the generated ideas effectively to enhance their understanding of specific concepts or lessons. Rather than passively accepting the responses provided by ChatGPT, they actively engage with the ideas, ensuring comprehension and clarity. This approach indicates a proactive effort to integrate AI assistance into their learning process as a supplementary tool rather than a replacement for their own cognitive efforts. By using the generated ideas to formulate responses, they aim to achieve high scores or perfect grades, indicating a goaloriented approach to leveraging ChatGPT as a means to academic success. This strategy reflects a thoughtful and strategic use of technology to support and enhance their learning outcomes, demonstrating a balance between utilizing AI assistance and maintaining personal engagement and comprehension in their academic endeavors. As what Participant 4 stated that:

"My strategy and technique while using ChatGPT is I emphasizes and utilizing the ideas correctively in order to have a better comprehension on a particular idea or a lesson ,and I will use that learning to answers in order to have a scores high and or have a perfect grade." (FGD-04)

(My strategy and technique when using ChatGPT involve emphasizing and utilizing ideas effectively to gain a better comprehension of a particular idea or lesson. I then apply that learning to provide answers).

Provide and Read Specific Prompt. This was the seventeenth code from the third probed issue. Participants emphasized the importance of specificity when engaging with ChatGPT to ensure accurate and efficient information retrieval. They described various strategies for achieving effective outcomes, such as asking detailed and specific questions, providing complete instructions, and ensuring concise communication. Participants mentioned that by being specific in their queries, they could receive more relevant and useful responses from ChatGPT, avoiding irrelevant information and streamlining the interaction process. This approach facilitated more efficient utilization of ChatGPT's capabilities, enhancing the overall effectiveness of their interactions with the AI system.

In connection to this, one effective strategy students employ when using ChatGPT is crafting specific questions to ensure accurate and efficient information retrieval. By providing clear and concise inquiries, students guide ChatGPT to focus on the exact topic or information they require, minimizing irrelevant responses. This approach streamlines the communication process and enhances the likelihood of obtaining precise and relevant insights. Additionally, specific questions help mitigate ambiguity, reducing the potential for misunderstandings and ensuring that ChatGPT delivers actionable information aligned with the students' intended purpose. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Isa jd sa mga strategie na akong gina gamit sa pagamit ug ChatGPT kanang the way ko mag ask ug question is in specific jd sya para acurate and efficient na mga informations akong makuha sa iya and in order to have an effective pud na result gikan sa iya”. (IDI-02)

(One of the strategies I used when using ChatGPT is to ask questions in a specific manner to enssure accurate and effiencent information. To acheive effective outcomes).

Similar to that , when students ask ChatGPT questions, they find it necessary to be specific so that the responses match the information they're looking for. By providing clear and detailed inquiries, students guide ChatGPT to focus on the exact topic or information they need, minimizing irrelevant or off-topic responses. This specificity helps streamline the interaction and ensures that the information retrieved is accurate and aligned with their intended purpose. Additionally, being specific reduces ambiguity, making it easier for students to understand and utilize the information provided by ChatGPT effectively.

“For me so dapat specific ka sapag ask ug question sa ChatGPT para sapag gather nimog answers is mag fit siya sa imong gipangita na answer”. (IDI-03)

(When asking ChatGPT questions, I find it necessary to be specific so that the responses match the information I am looking for.)

Additionally, students can effectively and efficiently utilize ChatGPT by employing the technique of asking detailed and specific questions. By providing complete details in their queries, students can access more accurate and relevant information tailored to their needs. This approach ensures that the responses from ChatGPT are closely aligned with the intended purpose, minimizing the likelihood of receiving irrelevant or off-topic information. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“My technique using ChatGPT effectively and effecienly is that I am asking the question nga detailed or specific sya kumpleto sya so that I can access acurate information.” (IDI-04)

(My technique for using ChatGPT effectively and efficiently is to ask detailed and specific questions. By providing complete details in my queries, I can access more accurate and relevant information).

Moreover, strategies and techniques employed by elementary education students for achieving successful outcomes using ChatGPT involve several key aspects. First and foremost, efficient communication is essential. Ensuring that questions are concise and specific helps students receive assistance from ChatGPT and achieve their intended goals with accurate answers. Additionally by employing specificity in their queries, students optimize interaction with ChatGPT, leading to more effective outcomes in knowledge acquisition and problem-solving. Overall, these approaches enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of elementary education students' utilization of ChatGPT as a valuable tool for information retrieval and learning enhancement. As what Participant 6 said that:

“My strategies and techniques I have use to have an effectively and efficiently using ChatGPT.First, ang effective Communication, so gina enssure nako na akong mga questions are concise ug specific para matabangan ko sa ChatGPT ug ang akoang tumong ug makahatag siyag sakto na answer.” (IDI-06)

(My strategies and techniques for achieving successful and effective outcomes using ChatGPT involve several key aspects. First and foremost, efficient communication is essential. I ensure that my questions are concise and specific in order to receive assistance from ChatGPT and achieve my intended goals with accurate answers.)

To add, the key strategy when utilizing ChatGPT involves providing clear instructions and ensuring that questions are precise and aligned with the intended goals. Sometimes, inputs are kept short and simple to avoid lengthy or irrelevant responses. This practice ensures that the received responses are relevant and useful for the questions asked, enhancing the effectiveness of the interaction with ChatGPT. By maintaining clarity and conciseness in communication, users can optimize the accuracy and efficiency of information retrieval from ChatGPT, leading to successful outcomes. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Akong strategy na gina gamit ug mag gamit ko ug ChatGPT, same thing mag hatag ko ug instructions sa iyaha ug kanang dapat pud akong question na gina ask sa iyaha is kanang kuan siya ba precise or kanang center siya sa akong gusto na makuha, unya usahay pud akoa siyang ginabutangan ug make it short and simple, kay naman gud instances na tag-as kaayu iyahang gina hatag unya ang uban dili na siya useful nay uban layo na siya sa imong question na gina ask sa iyaha.” (FGD-02)

(My strategy when using ChatGPT involves providing clear instructions and ensuring that my questions are precise and aligned with what I want to achieve. Sometimes, I also keep my inputs short and simple to avoid getting lengthy or irrelevant responses. This ensures that the responses I receive are relevant and useful for the questions I ask).

Furthermore, the strategy when using ChatGPT involves providing clear instructions and ensuring that questions are precise and aligned with the desired outcomes. Keeping inputs short and simple at times helps avoid lengthy or irrelevant responses, ensuring the received responses are relevant and useful. This approach streamlines the interaction, allowing for more efficient retrieval of relevant and useful information aligned with the intended purpose. By maintaining specificity in queries, users can enhance the effectiveness of their engagement with ChatGPT, leading to more successful outcomes in knowledge acquisition and problem-solving. As what Participant 5 said that:

“So for me when it comes into strategies and techniques no sa paggamit ug ChatGPT, ano najud ko be specific kong unsa imong gusto mahibal an, so kanang ug unsa ra akong gusto nga makuha nga answer mao rapud to akoang specific nga questions akong ihatag sa ChatGPT para dili kay siya daghang mahatag nga information sa akoa.”(FGD-05)

(So for me, when it comes to strategies and techniques in using ChatGPT, I usually focus on being specific about what I want to know. I ensure that my questions are targeted towards getting the exact answer I need, so I do not get overwhelmed with unnecessary information from ChatGPT).

Lastly, to use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently, the strategy involves giving specific commands and questions on how it should answer. By providing clear instructions and precise queries, users can guide ChatGPT to produce responses that meet their requirements accurately. This tactic helps minimize ambiguity and ensures that the information retrieved is relevant and useful for the intended purpose. By strategically structuring commands and questions, users can optimize their interaction with ChatGPT and enhance the overall effectiveness of utilizing the tool for various tasks and inquiries.

“So, to use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently ang strategy rajud akoa gina gamit when comes giving command ako rajud gina specific

ang akoang questions ug unsaon niya pag answer ug pag hatag.” (FGD-06)

(To use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently, my strategy is to give specific commands and questions on how it should answer).

Have Further Readings. This was the eighteenth code from the third probed issue. Participants emphasized the importance of engaging critically with ChatGPT responses, rather than simply copying and pasting them. They advocated for a deeper exploration such as reading of the concepts to ensure a more accurate understanding and the ability to articulate the response in one's own words. Critical evaluation of ChatGPT's responses was highlighted to ensure alignment with the intended purpose and factual accuracy. Techniques included reconstructing the gathered information to prevent plagiarism while still drawing from ChatGPT's insights. By providing users with links to additional resources from other search engines, users can cross-reference information and verify its accuracy. This enhances the reliability of search results and promotes critical thinking by encouraging users to consider multiple perspectives.

Similar to that, when conducting research, it's important not to simply copy and paste the answers that come up. Instead, it's crucial to critically evaluate the information provided and delve deeper into the topic to ensure accuracy and understanding. By synthesizing the information in your own words, you can better comprehend and articulate your findings, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. As what Participant 3 said to that:

“Dapat pag mag search ka diba mo gawas manang answers, ayaw e-copy and paste dayon ug unsay result, dapat mag depende lang ato tapos ikaw na mismo mo dig deeper sa idea para mas accurate imong result makuha para mas masabtan nimo nya ma estate na nimong answer in your own works.” (IDI-03)

(It is important not to just copy and paste the replies received. Instead, it is preferable to rely on oneself to go further into the concept, guaranteeing a more accurate grasp and allowing for the articulation of the response in your own words.)

In addition, the critical evaluation of the responses provided by ChatGPT to ensure alignment with one's intended purpose and factual accuracy. Additionally, it highlights the technique of reconstructing the gathered information to avoid plagiarism, thereby making it one's own by presenting it in a unique way. While the basis of the answer may come from ChatGPT, the reconstruction process transforms it into one's own work, enhancing originality and integrity. This approach not only fosters a deeper understanding of the material but also promotes ethical research practices. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Critically evaluating ,so dre gina evaluate sa nimo ang repond na gihatag sa ChatGPT to ensured na align siya sa imong intended purpose and are factually accurate pud sya. Sa techniques pud when I gathered the result akoo syang gina reconstruct sa so gina serve sa nako sya as basis na data tas e reconstruct nako sya para maiwasan nako ang pag plagiarised, so mahimo na syang sariling ako kay ako namn syang gi reconstruct, but ang basis sa answer sa ChatGPT gihapon ga gikan.” (IDI-06)

(Critical evaluation is crucial. I carefully assess the responses provided by ChatGPT to ensure alignment with my purpose and factual accuracy. In terms of techniques, when gathering results, I reconstruct the information obtained, treating it as a foundational dataset. This allows me to create my own rendition, avoiding plagiarism, while still drawing from the insights provided by ChatGPT).

Furthermore, users avoid solely relying on he provided answers and does not simply copy everything without verification. Instead, they carefully scrutinize the responses to ensure accuracy and relevance, checking for any words or phrases that may be unrelated or irrelevant to the topic or sentence structure. Additionally, the user employs techniques such as utilizing grammar and sentence checkers, either through apps or websites, to enhance the quality and coherence of the responses generated by ChatGPT. These strategies demonstrate a proactive approach to ensuring the reliability and usefulness of the information obtained from ChatGPT. As what Participant 3 stated that:

"My strategies in using ChatGPT are kanang kuntahay naa ang answer sa akoang question dili ko mag rely, dili nako e copy tanan akoo sa siyang i check ug tama bato siya kay basin naay mga words na dili d i siya related ato kanang irrelevant siya ato na topic or sa sentences. And my techniques in using ChatGPT is gagamit ko or mag install ko ug kaning app or mag open ko ug isa ka website nga kanang checker sa grammar ug sa sentence nga gikan sa ChatGPT." (FGD-03)

(My strategies in using ChatGPT are to first verify if the answer to my question is correct and not rely solely on it. I do not copy everything from ChatGPT and instead, I check if it is accurate because there may be words or sentences that are not related or irrelevant to the topic. My techniques in using ChatGPT include using or installing an app or opening a website that checks grammar and sentences from ChatGPT).

Thorough Reading and Contextualization. This was the nineteenth code form the third probed issue. This was a notable strategy among participants when using ChatGPT. They emphasized the importance of through reading and contextualization to avoid indiscriminate reliance on ChatGPT's responses.

Similarly, Participant emphasized the importance of understanding the information provided by ChatGPT and rephrasing it in a way that aligns with one's own understanding. By doing so, users can ensure that they grasp the content accurately and can express it in their own language, thereby reinforcing their comprehension. As what Participant 7 said that:

“Work smarter, but then for me the strategy for me is that ano lang jud contextualization lang jud, dle tanan mag salig perme sa

ChatGPT though it gives everything but then every idea gina contextualize rajud nako na dli jud gina copy tanan kasi very wrong and unfair man pud to those students or anyone na wlay technology. So, mao to maingun nako sya na strategies and techniques na nako to siya na dli tanan e copy paste diretso nga gihatag ni ChatGPT, and also sa question pud na gihatag ni teacher dli pud jud sya mao akong e-copy or e type kay ChatGPT so gina contextualize sad nakong question bago mag ask.” (IDI-07)

(The strategy I employ is contextualization. I do not rely entirely on ChatGPT’s responses because not all ideas are suitable for direct copying. It would be unfair to those without access to technology. Therefore, I ensure that I contextualize the information provided by ChatGPT and do not simply copy and paste it. Similarly, when responding to the teachers’ questions, I contextualize my answers instead of directly copying from ChatGPT).

In addition, the significance of framing questions or prompts clearly within the context of the desired information. By providing context, users guide ChatGPT to generate responses that are relevant and specific to the intended query, increasing the likelihood of obtaining accurate and useful answers. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“I found out one strategy before to use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently is to give it a role for example first nimo e-type like act as a Teacher or act as Doctor then ang question na nimo then ang ihatag nga answer sa ChatGPT is after ana more on focus na sa imohang gihatag nga role much more align pud kay siya answer sa gusto nimo na ma answer niya and then other techniques kay maybe pag kanang lisod kaayu ang questions e-add nako sa ChatGPT na prompt e add nako na e-explain it like into a 5 years old para ang mogawas na answer is very simple ug dali ra kaayu masabtan.” (FGD-01)

(Another strategy I have found to use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently is to give it a role, such as "act as a teacher" or "act as a doctor," before asking a question. This helps ChatGPT provide answers that are more focused and aligned with the role I have given it. Additionally, if the question is particularly difficult, I add a prompt to ChatGPT to explain the answer as if to a five-year-old. This helps me receive a simple and easy-to-understand response).

Furthermore, the necessity of clearly defining what information is sought before interacting with ChatGPT. By structuring queries effectively and ensuring clarity, users can streamline the communication process and facilitate more efficient exchanges with the AI model, leading to more satisfactory outcomes. As what Participant 7 said that:

“So, para pud sa akoa I have developed ahm several strategies and techniques to use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently in my learning tasks and activities, first is kanang dapat clear or specific imong I ask sa ChatGPT so, bali kuan before engaging with ChatGPT, I clearly define first my queries or prompts to ensure that the AI understands what information I need. This helps ChatGPT provide more accurate and relevant responses.” (FGD-07)

(To use ChatGPT effectively and efficiently in my learning tasks and activities, I have developed several strategies and techniques. Firstly, I make sure to ask clear and specific questions to ChatGPT. Before engaging with ChatGPT, I clearly define my queries or prompts to ensure that the AI understands what information I need. This helps ChatGPT provide more accurate and relevant responses).

Validating the Given Information. Based on insights gathered from in-depth interviews and focused group discussions, it is evident that in utilization of ChatGPT contributing their academics endeavourse, elementary education students play an active role in validating the accuracy and reliability of provided information. Utilizing online resources, they meticulously verify the credibility of data and filter out outdated or irrelevant content. Moreover, students employ techniques such as cross-referencing and consulting dictionaries to ensure comprehension and precision in their understanding. This proactive approach not only enhances their critical thinking skills but also cultivates a discerning attitude towards information consumption, contributing to their overall academic growth and development.

Discerning the Reliability and accuracy of Information. This was the twentieth code from the fourth probed issue. Users of ChatGPT encountered challenges in discerning the reliability and accuracy of provided information, despite its efficiency in generating responses. Concerns arose regarding the depth and context of answers, leading to potential misinformation and hampering genuine learning and critical thinking. To address these challenges, users emphasized the importance of verifying ChatGPT-generated information through additional research and external sources to ensure academic integrity and facilitate deeper comprehension.

Similarly, the participant highlighted the challenge of discerning the reliability and accuracy of the information provided by ChatGPT for learning purposes. While ChatGPT can swiftly generate responses, users may struggle to determine if the information lacks depth or context, potentially leading to misunderstanding or misinformation. Moreover, there's a risk of overreliance on ChatGPT without critically evaluating the information, which could hinder the development of genuine learning and critical thinking skills. As what Participant 1 said that:

“One of the notable difficulties that I have face in utilizing ChatGPT for learning is discerning the reliability and accuracy of the information it provides. Kabalo ta that ChatGPT can provide the answer in a second lang, mo generates ug mga idea hawod sad kaau, pero sahay, the information might lack depth or context, so lisod para sa atoa o sa akoa to grasp some info so nay tendency na ma mislead ang mga information atong nagamit. As a result, I had learned to verify the information provided by ChatGPT through additional research and external sources to ensure academic integrity and a deeper understanding of the topics at hand.” (IDI-01)

(One of the notable difficulties I have faced in utilizing ChatGPT for learning is discerning the reliability and accuracy of the information it provides. We know that ChatGPT can generate answers in seconds and is adept at coming up with ideas. However, sometimes the information might lack depth or context, making it challenging to grasp certain concepts. This can lead to the risk of being misled by the information we use. As a result, I have learned to verify the information provided by ChatGPT through additional research and external sources to ensure academic integrity and a deeper understanding of the topics at hand).

To add, the participant shared their initial struggle with prompting ChatGPT effectively to obtain the desired answer. They found it challenging to determine the most effective way to frame their prompts to elicit the desired response. Consequently, they engaged in numerous trial and error attempts and closely observed how to prompt ChatGPT correctly. Therefore, by simply refining their approach and persistently experimenting with different prompts, they eventually developed a better understanding of how to effectively communicate with ChatGPT, leading to improved outcomes in obtaining accurate responses. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“So at the beginning nag used ko ug ChatGPT nag lisod pako ug unsaon gani siya pag prompt kay para mahatag jud ang gusto nako na answer, so mao nang daghan pa kayo ug trial and error daghan pa kaayug gi tan-aw ug unsaon siya pag tarong pag prompt.” (FGD-01)

(At the beginning, when I started using ChatGPT, I struggled with how to prompt it effectively to ensure that it would provide the answer I wanted. That is why there were many trial and error attempts, and I spent a lot of time observing how to prompt it correctly).

Consequently, students may encounter difficulty in effectively utilizing ChatGPT due to challenges in sorting through and filtering the information it provides. As mentioned earlier, ChatGPT sometimes offers information unrelated to the questions asked by the user, leading to confusion and frustration. In such instances, students may need to repeatedly rephrase their queries or ask multiple questions to ensure they receive the desired or correct response. This process can be time-consuming and may impede the efficiency of using ChatGPT for learning purposes. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Para sa akong ang difficulty lang naku sa paggamit o ChatGPT is kanang magsala ug information ug mag-filter since sa akong gi mentioned ganina kay naa siyay gina-provide na information na unrelated sa questions na ako ang gina ask sa iyaha sa usahay maglisod pa ako daghan pa ko queries gina balik-balik nako ug question sa iyaha para lang makuha na po akong gusto na question or tama nga question or tama nga answer para sa akong question.” (FGD-02)

(The only difficulty I have with using ChatGPT is that it sometimes gives inaccurate information or does not filter out irrelevant details from the answer. This can make it hard to find the answer I am looking for. Sometimes I must ask ChatGPT many questions to get the specific answer I need, or even to confirm if the answer it gave is actually correct).

Furthermore, Participant 5 highlighted a difficulty they encountered with ChatGPT, specifically regarding the comprehension of the information provided. They expressed that some of the words used by ChatGPT were challenging to understand, necessitating the use of a dictionary for clarification. This indicates that the language used by ChatGPT can be complex and not always easy to grasp, leading to difficulties in comprehension for users. This obstacle underscores the need for improvements in ChatGPT's language processing capabilities to ensure that the information it generates is easily understandable for users. He stated that:

“So, for me when it comes difficulty maybe sa information lang jud na ginahatag sa ChatGPT which is dili ko kaayo kasabot so uban meaning kailangan panako siya e-search sa dictionary para masabtan so, ka na lang ang mga words na ginahatag or ginagamit sa ChatGPT is kaang difficult siya dili siya eazy to understand sa mga words.” (FGD-05)

(For me, the difficulty lies in the information provided by ChatGPT, which I sometimes struggle to understand. In such cases, I often need to look up the words in a dictionary to comprehend their meaning. The language used by ChatGPT can be quite complex and not always easy to understand, making it challenging to grasp the intended message).

Lastly, the participant expressed a desire for ChatGPT to accurately generate responses in native languages such as Bisaya and Tagalog, highlighting the challenges faced by students who primarily communicate in languages other than English. While ChatGPT does offer these languages, the accuracy may not always be optimal. Additionally, the participant raised concerns about privacy and security when using ChatGPT, particularly regarding the storage and handling of personal data. These concerns add another layer of complexity to the challenges associated with using ChatGPT, especially for students who rely on languages other than English and prioritize data privacy and security. As what Participant 7 said that:

“Sa ako pud is kuan lang kana ganing gusto unta nako na mo generate nag sakto ang ChatGPT ug mga native language gud mga in ana like bisaya jud ug tagalong, though naa mn siya pero dili jud haom kaayu so para sakoa, ahm so this can be challenging for students who primarily communicate in languages other than English, in addition sa katong security concerns pud about privacy and security when using ChatGPT, particularly regarding the storage and handling of personal data”. (FGD-07)

(For me, it would be ideal if ChatGPT could accurately generate responses in native languages such as Bisaya and Tagalog. While it does offer these languages, the accuracy may not always be optimal. This can pose a challenge for me as a student who primarily communicate in languages other than English. Additionally, there are concerns about privacy and security when using ChatGPT, particularly regarding the storage and handling of personal data. These concerns further compound the challenges associated with using the tool, especially in educational settings where privacy and data security are paramount.

Having Outdated Information. This was twenty-first the code from the fourth probed issue. Elementary education students utilizing ChatGPT encountered challenges in discerning the reliability and accuracy of provided information, despite its efficiency in generating responses. Concerns arose regarding the depth and context of answers, leading to potential misinformation and hampering genuine learning and critical thinking. To address these challenges, users emphasized the importance of verifying ChatGPT-generated information through additional research and external sources to ensure academic integrity and facilitate deeper comprehension.

Similarly, the participant encountered several difficulties while utilizing ChatGPT. One challenge was that at times, the information provided by ChatGPT was significantly different from the main question, leading to confusion. Additionally, there were instances where the participant would type a question, but unfortunately, the resulting answer lacked sources or references. Moreover, the information provided by ChatGPT was sometimes outdated, as verified by checking with other credible sources where the results differed or additional information was provided. These challenges highlight the importance of critically evaluating and verifying the information obtained from ChatGPT to ensure accuracy and relevance. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“So, some difficulties that I have faced while utilizing ChatGPT is that some information na gikan sa Chatgpt naay times layo ra kaayo iyang tubag sa main question... ChatGPT is outdated sya kay upon checking pud like sa Google or other Ai pud like Bard ang mo gawas sa result is dle parehas or nay kulang na nahatag sa ChatGPT.” (IDI-05)

(Some difficulties that I have faced while utilizing ChatGPT include instances where the information provided is not directly relevant to the main question. Additionally, ChatGPT can be outdated, as I have noticed discrepancies when cross-referencing its answers with sources like Google or other AI like Bard. The results from these other sources often differ or contain additional information that ChatGPT does not provide.)

In addition to the challenges mentioned, using ChatGPT presents notable difficulties. Firstly, users often question the accuracy and relevance of the information provided. Secondly, while ChatGPT is powerful, it lacks deep understanding, especially about past events. Its reliance on human-fed data can lead to gaps or inaccuracies. Verifying information from ChatGPT is important due to potential inaccuracies or outdated content. Moreover, it may struggle to adapt to current events. Thus, critical assessment and seeking additional sources are essential. Engaging with knowledgeable peers is an effective tactic, promoting collaborative learning and deeper understanding. As what Participant 6 said that:

“For me the notable difficulties when I utilizing in ChatGPT is that first jud is galibog ug naga duha-duha ko kay sa mga gipang provide niya na mga data information if accurate or relevant paba sya now a days ,so that it is lead to confusion para sa amoa nga mga studyante or as users.Second one,wala kay siyay deep understanding sa mga past events gani compared jud sa human,so kay tao man ang naga buhat sa ChatGPT so ug unsay gi feed pud sa iya mao lang pud to ang mga information na mogawas .Aside pa ana kailangan pud nato siya e-check sa na gather niya na mga information, kay some of information na ma provide sa imoha kay dili sya usahay accurate and outdated pud.” (IDI-06)

(For me, the notable difficulties when utilizing ChatGPT are primarily related to the accuracy and relevance of the information it provides. Firstly, I often feel confused and hesitant about the data it generates, questioning whether it is accurate or relevant to current times. This can lead to confusion for us as students or users. Secondly, ChatGPT lacks a deep understanding of past events compared to humans. Since it is created and fed information by people, it can only provide what it has been given. Additionally, it is necessary to verify the information gathered by ChatGPT, as some of the information it provides can be inaccurate or outdated.)

In connection to that, notable difficulties in using ChatGPT include instances where it fails to base responses on updated versions of questions, resulting in incomplete or irrelevant outputs. Additionally, there are occurrences where ChatGPT provides results without accompanying references, which may hinder users' ability to verify or understand the information provided. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“The notable difficulties in utilizing ChatGPT is kanang wala siya usahay basihan ro dli siya updated ang mga version sa akoang questions dili tanan mo gawas, ug sa kanang walay mga reference na mugawas sa mga result gikan sa ChatGPT.” (FGD-03)

(The notable difficulties in utilizing ChatGPT are that it sometimes lacks the ability to understand certain topics, it is not always updated with the latest information, and it tends to produce results without providing references from external sources).

Technology-based Concerns. Based on the experiences gleaned from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it is evident that elementary education students encounter technology-based concerns, particularly regarding privacy and internet connectivity. Users' express hesitancy to sign in due to data privacy apprehensions, highlighting their concerns about the security of personal information. Moreover, students face challenges with low internet connection, often resulting in difficulties accessing resources and obtaining answers promptly. These issues underscore the importance of addressing privacy and connectivity issues to ensure a seamless and secure learning experience for elementary education students.

Securing the Privacy of Information. This was the twenty-second code from the fourth probed issue. Elementary education students utilizing ChatGPT expressed concerns about the security of their personal information, particularly during the sign-in process where email addresses are required. Some participants felt uneasy about providing personal details, fearing potential security risks. Additionally, language barriers posed challenges, especially for students who primarily communicate in languages other than English,

as ChatGPT's proficiency in languages like Bisaya and Tagalog was perceived as inadequate. Moreover, privacy and security concerns persisted regarding the storage and handling of personal data, despite some efforts to address them. These issues remained significant considerations for users, highlighting the importance of ensuring the privacy and security of information when using ChatGPT.

Similarly, the participant elaborates on their concerns about the security of their personal information when signing in to ChatGPT. They express a feeling of unease and doubt regarding the platform's level of security, particularly when prompted to provide their email address for authentication purposes. This hesitation stems from apprehensions about sharing personal information, as they fear potential risks associated with data breaches or unauthorized access. Despite eventually using the platform, their initial reluctance underscores the importance of robust security measures and transparent data handling practices to reassure users and alleviate concerns related to privacy and confidentiality. As participant 6 said that:

"Katong mag sign in pako ana is naka feel ko na kanang dili bitaw kaayu sicured so kuan mag duha-duha ko ug log in sa ChatGPT syempre mag require mn siya ug email, kuan murag makuan sa akua ba nga mag hatag bitaw ug personal information though nagamit napud noon nako siya karon at first mahadlok lang jud ko." (FGD-06)

(When I signed up for it, I felt that it was not very secure. Whenever I logged in to ChatGPT, it required an email, which made me feel like it might be asking for personal information. Even though I'm using it now, I was initially quite afraid).

Additionally, the participant highlights further concerns regarding privacy and security when utilizing ChatGPT, particularly pertaining to the storage and management of personal data. Although efforts have been made to address these concerns to some degree, they emphasize that these issues remain a significant consideration for users. This acknowledgment underscores the ongoing importance of robust data protection measures and transparent practices in handling user data, as maintaining user trust and confidence is crucial in fostering a safe and secure online environment. Despite strides made in addressing privacy and security concerns, there is continued recognition of the need for vigilance and diligence in safeguarding user privacy rights and data integrity. As Participant 7 said that:

"In addition, sa katong security concerns pud about privacy and security when using ChatGPT, particularly regarding the storage and handling of personal data. While these concerns have been addressed to some extent, same for me that it is still a consideration for the users. (FGD-07)

(In addition, there are also security concerns regarding privacy and data protection when using ChatGPT, especially regarding the storage and handling of personal data. While some steps have been taken to address these concerns, they still remain a consideration for users like me).

Low Internet Connection. This is the twenty-third code from the fourth probed issue. One significant challenge encountered by users when utilizing ChatGPT is the issue of low internet connection, particularly when relying on mobile data. Users reported instances of prolonged loading times due to poor connectivity, hindering the smooth operation of the platform.

Similarly, elementary education students encounter issues with ChatGPT, particularly regarding connectivity problems, especially when relying on mobile data. There are instances when the platform experiences prolonged loading periods due to poor network connections. As what Participant 3 stated that:

"Ang problema lang man sa akua ug maggamit ko ug ChatGPT, kay ang connection especially kay ga data lang ko, naay mga times na loading jd kaayu sya". (IDI-03)

(My connection is the issue I have with ChatGPT, especially when I am using mobile data. There are instances where processing takes a long time).

Moreover, elementary education students commonly face notable challenges when using ChatGPT. One such difficulty involves the need for frequent logins whenever they access the platform. This repetitive process can be cumbersome and time-consuming, impacting their overall user experience. Additionally, students sometimes encounter issues with connectivity, particularly when dealing with weak signals. As a result, they may find themselves unable to access the ChatGPT platform promptly due to blank pages or slow loading times. These connectivity issues can disrupt their workflow and hinder their ability to utilize ChatGPT effectively for their educational needs. As what Participant 4 stated that:

"My notable difficulty is I always na kanang pag mo agto ko sa ilang platform, mag sige ko ug log in, and usahay pud sa kahina guro sa signal blanko sya dle ko dayon maka sulod sa iyang page." (IDI-04)

(My notable difficulty is consistently having to log in whenever I access their platform. Additionally, there are times when poor signal strength causes the page to go blank, preventing me from accessing it immediately).

Similarly, elementary education students encountered difficulties when utilizing ChatGPT, especially in situations where internet connectivity was unavailable. For students who preferred to stay at home and did not have access to the internet, reliance on ChatGPT became ingrained due to its convenience and purpose. However, the absence of internet access posed challenges, particularly when urgent research or assignments needed to be completed promptly. Students found themselves waiting for an internet connection or facing difficulties in conveying their exact points to ChatGPT for accurate responses. This reliance on technology sometimes led to

frustration and hindered the effectiveness of using ChatGPT for academic purposes. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“The difficulties siguro facing in utilizing ChatGPT specifically when there is no internet in our home, then ako nga tao is dili ko hilig mag gawas-gawas ug wlay net sa balay, wla jud so mao to maanad nako na mag rely sa ChatGPT specifically kay mao man jud ni purpose nag gamit ko ani, so kong naay pasahonon ugma na dapat ipasa ugma akong na research agad-agad tomorrow, so mag tanga ko to wait the Internet, ug usahay jud dili jud kay nako mas mapasabot kay ChatGPT ang akoang point nga dapat maoy mo gawas man gud kay but then, maybe when I construct or asking a question maybe dili kay nako ma pen point ang akong mismong gusto so maybe that is some my difficulty I have faced in utilizing for ChatGPT.” (IDI-07)

(The difficulties I face in utilizing ChatGPT arise, particularly when there is no internet connection at home. Personally, I am not fond of going out without internet access, so I have become accustomed to relying on ChatGPT specifically for this reason. For instance, if I have an assignment due tomorrow that requires immediate research, I may find myself waiting for an internet connection. Sometimes, it is challenging for me to articulate my exact point when constructing or asking a question, which can hinder my communication with ChatGPT).

The insights of Elementary Education Students with Regards to their Utilization of ChatGPT in Learning.

Presented on Table 3 is the thematic analysis based on the responses of the participants in the In-Depth Interview and Focus Group Discussion which are transcribed verbatim. Responses are extracted from the result of one probed issue to unveil the insights of elementary education students with regards to their utilization of ChatGPT in their learning experiences. The issue obtained fifteen codes. Finally, the essential themes can be supported by six theoretical perspectives namely:

ChatGPT as Essential Resource for Learning. The insights of elementary education students in accordance with user trust in utilizing of ChatGPT in learning are being elaborated based from the similar responses provided by the participants. Based on the information given by the participants actively contribute to the establishment of ChatGPT as a trustworthy learning tool. By prompting meaningful questions, offering assistance in teaching demonstrations and presentation creation, and furnishing a diverse array of resources on various subjects, ChatGPT actively facilitates students' learning endeavors.

ChatGPT as a Teaching Tool. This is the first code for the first probed issue. The participant discussed the use of ChatGPT as a teaching tool, specifically highlighting its introduction to students and fellow educators through demonstrations and practical examples. The participant envisions incorporating ChatGPT into classroom activities, such as lesson planning and discussions, to streamline processes and enhance learning outcomes. By integrating ChatGPT into teaching practices, the participant aims to facilitate critical thinking development among students and fellow educators, ultimately improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the learning experience.

Table 3. *Insights among Elementary Students with Regards to their Utilization of ChatGPT in Learning*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code / Categories</i>	<i>Essential Theme</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Different Impact and Trust of ChatGPT in Learning	Prompting worthwhile questions to aid one’s learning tasks and activities.	ChatGPT as a Teaching Tool	ChatGPT as Essential Resource for Learning	Connectivism Theory of George Siemens
	Seeking assistance from ChatGPT relative to teaching demonstrations and in making PowerPoint presentations.			
	Providing varied, distinct, and wide range of resources and information on various topics.			
	Assisting in organizing different tasks and activities which develops one’s critical thinking.	Enhance and Increase Student Learning		
	Helping in producing and crafting creative outputs, tasks, and activities.			
	Providing concrete and vivid answers on the most difficult and ambiguous questions.			
	Being an essential tool in crafting research and in providing deeper understanding on the topic.	Promoting Effectiveness in Students’ Learning Progress		
	Sharing with other users or students on the effectiveness of ChatGPT in helping their learning experiences.			
	Sharing other students the useful and essential information that ChatGPT is giving which help their learning.			
	Being convenient to use and navigate which in turn provides essential learning inputs.	High Level of Trust in Using ChatGPT	Building Trust in the Utilization of ChatGPT	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)
	Acknowledging the value of ChatGPT in aiding one’s learning progress.			
	Recognizing the need for verification, critical thinking, and personal effort in using ChatGPT.			
	Emphasizing the reliability and effectiveness of ChatGPT despite its occasional inaccuracies and limitations.			

	Having trust and confidence in the ability of ChatGPT in helping students' academic pursuit with varying degree of reliance and verification.			
	Being a language-based assistant tool that explains complex questions and provide clear information for learning tasks.	Building Trust with ChatGPT as an Assistant Learning Tool		
	Being completely aware of the various limitations and deficiencies of ChatGPT as assistant learning tool.			
	Being able to recognize the fact that there must be a lance use of its potential benefits and its accuracy and reliability.	Ensuring a balance Use of ChatGPT	The Need of Becoming a Responsible User of ChatGPT	
	Being not overusing ChatGPT in all aspect of learning.			
	Recognizing its limitations and the need of critical thinking and independent research.			
	Building confidence knowing that other students are also using the same AI tool.	Peer Discussion on the Proper Navigation of ChatGPT		
	Collaborating with other students in discussing the potential benefits of ChatGPT in learning.			
Personal Techniques in Navigating Uncertainties in Using ChatGPT	Using of Google to check and verify if the information is correct.	Look for Other Similar Apps and Websites	Techniques in Using ChatGPT as Learning Resource	Constructivist Theory of John Dewey
	Using grammar checker to evaluate the construct of the answer.			
	Contextualizing the lengthy answers of ChatGPT by using fast-checking tools.	Contextualize and Evaluate the Information		
	Having self-reflection of the answers provided.			
	Owning the answer by having paraphrasing and rephrasing.			
	Adjusting the choice of words so it can help to clarify the information and reduce uncertainties.			
	Asking peers about their understanding of the topic or content given by ChatGPT.	Consulting Peers and Others		
	Consulting peers and classmates who were also using ChatGPT about proper navigation of the AI.			
Further Improvements Needed to Enhance the Educational Usage of ChatGPT	Developing modifications and adjustments to secure the reliability and accuracy of the information.	Improve Its Accuracy and Reliability in Educational Context	Essential Development of ChatGPT for its Efficiency and Efficacy	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)
	Developing fast-checking tools that will improve the understanding of educational context.			
	Providing more relevant and updated answers to a question.	Development of Its User Interface and Database		
	Developing and improving user interface to make it more intuitive and user-friendly.	Generate Pictures Alongside with Text	Development of its Features and Algorithms	Dual Coding Theory
	Involving a lot more languages aside from English to enhance educational context and setting.			
	Being able to produce texts with pictures for ease in comprehension and understanding of the concept.			
	Providing images or illustrations to visualize the idea easily.			
	Including images, graphics, and 3D objects to have a creative and informative data.			
	Including link, citation, and references to easily navigate important sources of information.	Provide Hyperlink and Its References		
	Providing reference lists to easily evaluate and check information if its valid and reliable.			
	Providing privacy and security to use the AI safely.	Ensure the Data Privacy and Security		
	Providing security measures in each user.			

ChatGPT as a Teaching Tool. This is the first code for the first probed issue. The participant discussed the use of ChatGPT as a teaching tool, specifically highlighting its introduction to students and fellow educators through demonstrations and practical examples. The participant envisions incorporating ChatGPT into classroom activities, such as lesson planning and discussions, to streamline processes and enhance learning outcomes. By integrating ChatGPT into teaching practices, the participant aims to facilitate critical thinking development among students and fellow educators, ultimately improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the learning experience.

Similarly, Participant envisioned introducing ChatGPT to fellow students and teachers by creating PowerPoint presentations for demonstrations in the classroom. This create to facilitate the teaching process, making it more efficient and streamlined. By incorporating ChatGPT into lesson planning and classroom discussions, the participant believed it would enhance the flow of

instruction and improve the overall quality of teaching practices on a daily basis. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“I introduce nako sa ilaha ang ChatGPT through demonstration ug unsaon pag gamit, like sa search bar dre mag ask ug question something in ana sir para mapadali ilang buhatanon.” (IDI-02)

(I introduced ChatGPT to them through a demonstration of how to use it, like in the search bar where you ask questions to simplify their tasks).

Moreover, participants utilized ChatGPT to assist in achieving their learning outcomes, as well as during demo teaching and classroom discussions to foster critical thinking skills. They perceived ChatGPT as a valuable tool in generating answers and stimulating intellectual inquiry, contributing to a more dynamic and engaging learning environment. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“As a future elementary teacher I can introduce ChatGPT to my fellow students and fellow teachers for example by creating a PPT's kanang mag demonstration ka, mag demo sa klase and in making a lesson plan, makatabang pud siya para mas mapadali ug mas mapahapsay ang flow sa imong discussion ug mas mapa okay ang imohang gina himo sa daily basis sa imohang pag tudlo.” (FGD-03)

(As a future elementary teacher, I can introduce ChatGPT to my fellow students and colleagues by, for example, creating PowerPoint presentations where I can demonstrate its use in class and integrate it into lesson planning. It can help streamline the flow of discussions and improve the effectiveness of my daily teaching activities).

In addition, Participants in elementary education student aimed to raise awareness about ChatGPT and teach others how to use it properly, ensuring its effective and efficient utilization. By imparting knowledge on the appropriate ways to leverage ChatGPT, Participant sought to educate others in a manner that enhances learning outcomes and promotes efficient use of the tool. As what Participant 3 said that:

“Utilizing ChatGPT, my peers perceive it in order to achieve their learning outcomes, and in terms on their demo teaching and their discussion in the class to develop their critical think to those answers come from the ChatGPT.” (FGD-03)

(When utilizing ChatGPT, my peers perceive it as a tool to achieve their learning outcomes. In terms of their demonstration teaching and class discussions, they use it to develop their critical thinking skills by analyzing and evaluating the answers generated by ChatGPT).

Furthermore, the participants, envisioning their role as a future educator, expressed their intent to enhance awareness about ChatGPT and provide instruction on its proper usage. By teaching individuals how to effectively utilize ChatGPT, they aim to facilitate learning in a manner that is both efficient and effective, thereby maximizing its educational benefits.

“As a future educator I can provide awareness and I can teach them how to use ChatGPT and utilize it na kanang proper way so I can teach them in an effective and efficient manner.” (FGD-04)

(As a future educator, I can provide awareness and teach them how to use ChatGPT and utilize it in the proper way, so I can teach them in an effective and efficient manner).

Enhance and Increase Student Learning. This is the second code for the first proved issue. Participants in elementary education emphasized the platform's versatility in providing a wide array of resources, aiding in task organization, enhancing critical thinking skills, and facilitating effective communication. By sharing their positive experiences and demonstrating ChatGPT's capabilities, participants aimed to showcase its effectiveness in supporting student learning across various subjects and tasks positive experiences and demonstrating ChatGPT's capabilities, participants aimed to showcase its effectiveness in supporting student learning across various subjects and tasks. Through these efforts, they sought to promote deeper understanding, productivity, and collaboration among students, ultimately enriching the overall learning experience.

Similarly, participant intent to share their positive experiences with ChatGPT through demonstrations, aiming to relate their personal learning journey to others. They highlight ChatGPT's diverse impact on their learning, including providing a wide array of resources, assisting in task organization, enhancing critical thinking skills, and fostering effective communication and collaboration. This response underscores the multifaceted role of ChatGPT in supporting learners' educational endeavors, showcasing its potential to positively influence various aspects of the learning process. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“For me ma share nako ni sa ila through demonstration, so e-relate nako sa ila about in my experience using chatgpt, that ChatGPT has positively impacted my understanding and engagement in learning in several ways. Firstly, it has provided me with a wide range of resources and information on various topics, which has helped me gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Secondly, it has assisted me in organizing my tasks and activities by suggesting effective strategies and techniques. Thirdly, it has enhanced my critical thinking skills by providing me with diverse perspectives and arguments. Lastly, it has facilitated effective communication and collaboration among my peers and me.” (IDI-01)

(I will relate to them how ChatGPT has positively impacted my understanding and engagement in learning in several ways. Firstly, it has provided me with a wide range of resources and information on various topics, which has helped me gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Secondly, it has assisted me in organizing my tasks and activities by suggesting effective strategies and techniques.

Thirdly, it has enhanced my critical thinking skills by providing me with diverse perspectives and arguments. Lastly, it has facilitated effective communication and collaboration among my peers and me).

Furthermore, the participant expresses their intention to share their positive experiences with ChatGPT among fellow students by highlighting its effectiveness in answering various types of questions, whether random or related to discussions. It aims to convey the positive impact of ChatGPT based on their personal experiences, emphasizing its utility in addressing queries and clearing up confusion. This underscores the participant's desire to promote ChatGPT's benefits among peers, indicating its potential to enhance collaborative learning environments and support knowledge sharing among students. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“I can share it to my fellow students through giving them an idea how amazing ChatGPT is when it comes answering different questions, its either random lang sya na pangutana or related sya na discussion ,ug e-share pud nako sa ila akong experience ug unsa ang positive na impact ni ChatGPT sa akua like ug naa koy gi kalibogan” (IDI-03)

(I can share with my fellow students by giving them an idea of how amazing ChatGPT is when it comes to answering various questions, whether they are random inquiries or related discussions. I can also share my own experience and the positive impact ChatGPT has had on me, such as clearing up confusion when I have questions).

Additionally, participant expresses their inclination to share positive aspects of ChatGPT with their fellow students, highlighting its role beyond providing well-structured information. They emphasize ChatGPT's capability to enhance creativity and productivity in learning tasks and activities. Moreover, they note the value of encountering novel words or ideas through ChatGPT, suggesting its potential to introduce fresh perspectives and insights not readily available elsewhere. This perspective underlines the participant's recognition of ChatGPT as a versatile tool that extends beyond conventional information retrieval, contributing to a richer learning experience. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“Sa akua lang maingun nako sakong mga fellow student about something positive sa ChatGPT aside sa information na very well constructed ug kong gusto man jud ka nga imong mga output, learning task and activities is very creative and productive, ChatGPT is the answer, aside ana ang naka nindot lang pud sa ChatGPT naa jud kay masugat-an na mga words or ideas na bag o pa para sa imoha na didto lang jud nimo makita sa ChatGPT.” (IDI-05)

(In my opinion, I would share something positive about ChatGPT to my fellow students. Aside from the well-constructed information and creative and productive learning tasks and activities, ChatGPT is the answer. Additionally, ChatGPT can provide words or ideas that may be new or unfamiliar to you, which you can only find in ChatGPT).

Similarly, the participant described their ability to share instances where ChatGPT positively impacted their comprehension or engagement in learning. They highlighted how ChatGPT aided in explaining and clarifying complex topics that would have otherwise been difficult to understand. By leveraging ChatGPT, they found it easier to grasp challenging concepts, emphasizing its role in facilitating their learning process. This sentiment underscored the participant's recognition of ChatGPT as a valuable tool for enhancing understanding and overcoming learning obstacles. As what Participant 6 said that:

“I can share instances where ChatGPT has positively impacted my understanding or engagement in learning by providing through explanation o clarification on complex topic diba there are some topic that lisod kaayu sabton with that with the use of ChatGPT it helps me to grasp difficult concept more easily masabtan dayon nato sya” (IDI-06)

(I can share instances where ChatGPT has positively impacted my understanding or engagement in learning by providing through explanation or clarification on complex topics. There are some topics that are difficult to understand, but with the use of ChatGPT, it helps me to grasp difficult concepts more easily and understand them better).

In connection to that, the participant highlighted their capability to share experiences utilizing ChatGPT as an AI tool, emphasizing its substantial aid, especially in learner tasks and research endeavors. By leveraging ChatGPT, it significantly deepened their comprehension of specific lessons or topics, emphasizing its importance in augmenting the learning process and research activities. As what Participant 7 said that:

“I can share my experiences in using this AI tool that ahm this AI tool ChatGPT is very helpful for us in specially learner task, specially reconducting a research kay is really big help for us, and para mapa deeper atong understanding in that certain lesson or that certain topic” (IDI-07)

(I can share my experiences in using this AI tool. This AI tool, ChatGPT, is very helpful for us, especially in learning tasks and conducting research. It is a big help for us to deepen our understanding of certain lessons or topics)

Promoting Effectiveness in Students' Learning Progress. This is the third code for the first probed issue. Participants involves sharing firsthand experiences and highlighting the utility of ChatGPT in providing useful information and aiding academic tasks. By discussing its effectiveness in delivering accurate and accessible information, participants aim to showcase the platform's value in supporting students' educational endeavors. Through such efforts, they seek to encourage fellow students to leverage ChatGPT as a tool to enhance their learning experiences and academic responsibilities due to its ease of use and practical benefits.

Similarly, participant highlighted the act of sharing information, such as discussing ChatGPT's effectiveness during interviews or conversations, as a means to showcase its value to other students. By engaging in these discussions and providing insights into ChatGPT's efficacy, participants contribute to raising awareness about its potential benefits in aiding academic tasks and enhancing learning experiences. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“Like what we’re doing right now it is an example of sharing information, so just like this interviewing or giving an idea about ChatGPT ug unsa siya ka effective, so I guess it is one of the example to share to others student the effectiveness of this A.I.” (IDI-04)

(Like what we are doing right now, it is an example of sharing information. So, just like this interview or giving an idea about ChatGPT and how effective it is, I guess it is one of the examples to share with other students the effectiveness of this AI).

In connection, the participant expressed their intention to share with their fellow students the positive impact of ChatGPT on their study by highlighting its effectiveness in providing information. By promoting ChatGPT's ability to furnish useful information, the participant aims to underscore its value to other students, emphasizing its potential to support their academic endeavors. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Seguro ma share nako sa akoang mga fellow students sa ang positive impact ni ChatGPT sa akong pag skwela through promoting the effectiveness of ChatGPT in providing information since if magamit tag ChatGPT maka provide mn jud siya ug useful na information sa atoang mga students.” (FGD-02)

(Perhaps I can share with my fellow students the positive impact of ChatGPT on my schooling by promoting its effectiveness in providing information. Since when we use ChatGPT, it really does provide useful information to us students).

In relation to that, the participant discussed their approach to promoting ChatGPT among their peers, focusing on its effectiveness based on their firsthand experience. They highlighted the convenience and utility of ChatGPT in academic tasks and responsibilities, noting how it simplifies the completion of these tasks. This reflects their appreciation for ChatGPT's ease of use and its impact on their academic performance, serving as a testament to the tool's practical benefits in an educational context. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Ang way nga makuan ma promote nako sa ila ang ChatGPT is iingun lang nako ang effectiveness bitaw sa pag use sa ChatGPT since na kuan man nako sya na experience nako siya firsthand jud unya nindot siya gamiton unya makatabang pud ni siya sa atong mga academics task or mga responsibilities nato kay dali ramn kay siya gamiton.” (FGD-06)

(The way I can promote ChatGPT to them is by simply telling them about its effectiveness in actual use. Since I have experienced it firsthand and found it easy and helpful in our academic tasks or responsibilities, I can easily convey its benefits).

Building Trust in the Utilization of ChatGPT. Based on insights gathered from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it is evident that elementary education students actively participate in building trust in the utilization of ChatGPT as an assistant learning tool. The discussions underscore the high level of trust students place in ChatGPT, recognizing its reliability and effectiveness in aiding their learning tasks. Participants highlight the importance of establishing trust with ChatGPT to maximize its potential as a learning assistant. By fostering trust in its capabilities, students can confidently leverage ChatGPT to enhance their educational experiences, deepen their understanding of various subjects, and achieve academic success.

High Level of Trust in Using ChatGPT. This is the fourth code from the first probed issue. Participants expressed varying levels of trust in utilizing ChatGPT for learning tasks, with ratings ranging from moderate to high. While they acknowledge the platform's value in providing information and support, they also recognized its limitations and the importance of verifying its response. Factors influencing their trust include the platform's effectiveness in delivering well-constructed and accurate information, as well as their own experiences and the need for critical evaluation. Overall, they view ChatGPT as a valuable tool but emphasize the necessity of maintaining a balanced reliance on it alongside other sources and critical thinking skills.

Similarly, the participant demonstrated a moderate level of confidence in employing ChatGPT for educational objectives. While recognizing its capacity to provide valuable insights and support learning endeavors, they also acknowledged potential drawbacks in terms of accuracy and reliability. As a result, they adopted a cautious strategy by verifying the information obtained from ChatGPT with alternative sources and employing critical thinking skills to assess its validity. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“My level of trust in utilizing ChatGPT sir in learning is moderate. While I believe that it can provide valuable insights and support my learning process, I also recognize that it may not always be accurate or reliable. Therefore, I tend to verify the information provided by ChatGPT using additional sources and my own critical thinking skills.” (IDI-01)

(I have a moderate level of trust in using ChatGPT for learning. While I acknowledge its potential to offer valuable insights and aid in my learning, I also understand that it may not always be entirely accurate or dependable. Hence, I make it a practice to verify the information provided by ChatGPT through other sources and my own critical thinking abilities).

In connection to that, the participant provided a rating of 8 out of 10 for ChatGPT, highlighting its substantial assistance in their academic tasks such as searching for words and completing assignments. However, they noted a few drawbacks, such as over-reliance

on technology and the need for personal effort. This nuanced evaluation suggests an awareness of both the benefits and limitations of ChatGPT, emphasizing the importance of maintaining a balanced approach to utilizing AI tools in education. As what Participant 2 said that:

“Kuan kong e rate nako siya out of 10 seguro is 8 siya, since dako naman ug natabang sa akua ang ChatGPT sir kay kung nakoy e search nga mga word or nakoy e search sa akong mga assignment ug mga learning task so dako-dako najd syag natabang sa akua sir. Nag hatag kog 8 sir beacause dle jd sya ma perfect jud sir like kanang naa jud mga 2 percent sir na disadvantage kay ma over used na sa technology, sa A.I, so mao to akong gi mentioned ka ganina sir nga dili pud sya good if mag rely lang ta sa perme sa A.I dapat napud ta mismo sa atong self na ikaw gyud ang mag effort ana.” (IDI-02)

(If I were to rate ChatGPT out of 10, I would give it an 8. It has been very helpful to me because when I search for words or when I have assignments and learning tasks, ChatGPT provides significant assistance. However, it is not perfect as there are some disadvantages, such as over-reliance on technology and AI. Therefore, it is not advisable to rely solely on AI and instead, we should make an effort ourselves).

To add, participant expressed a high level of trust in utilizing ChatGPT for learning tasks, rating it at 90 out of 100. They emphasized the platform's ability to provide comprehensive, well-constructed, and accurate information. Conversely, they also acknowledged occasional instances where the information provided by ChatGPT may lack precision or concreteness. In such cases, they mentioned contextualizing the ideas themselves to ensure clarity and accuracy. This nuanced perspective reflects a balanced assessment of ChatGPT's strengths and limitations, indicating a thoughtful approach to its use in educational contexts. As what Participant 2 said that:

“So my level of trust in utilizing of ChatGPT in learning especially in making my task and activities, to rate from it it is 90 over 100, since based on my experience ChatGPT provides more information, the data, well construct and and accurate na mga idea no , but there are some instances that maka hatag sya ug information but dle jud siya ingun nga exact or kaning dili usahay concrete ang mga information na ginahatag sa imoha, so as what I have said earlier there is a time na ako nang siyang gina contextualize para sa han ay nako ang mga idea na gikan sa iyaha.” (IDI-06)

(My level of trust in utilizing ChatGPT for learning, especially in completing my tasks and activities, would be rated at 90 out of 100. This is because, based on my experience, ChatGPT provides a wealth of well-constructed and accurate information. However, there are instances where it may provide information that is not exactly precise or concrete. In those cases, I take it upon myself to contextualize the ideas from ChatGPT to suit my needs).

Lastly, participant's level of trust in using ChatGPT is quite high, rated at around 8 out of 10. This indicates a strong belief in the effectiveness of ChatGPT in providing information. The participant likely has firsthand experience that has demonstrated the reliability and usefulness of ChatGPT in delivering accurate and relevant content. This level of trust suggests that the participant has found ChatGPT to be a valuable tool in their learning or work processes. However, it's important to note that while ChatGPT may be effective in many instances, there may still be occasional inaccuracies or limitations to consider. Therefore, maintaining a degree of critical thinking and verification when using ChatGPT remains essential, despite its proven effectiveness.

“Seguro ma describe nako akong level of trust in using ChatGPT kay mga around 8 over 10 since na proved man pud nako ang effectiveness niya sa pag hatag ug information”. (FGD-02)

(I can describe my level of trust in using ChatGPT as around 8 out of 10, as I have found it to be effective in providing information).

In connection, the participant described their level of trust in utilizing ChatGPT, rating it at 8 out of 10. They emphasized the helpfulness of this AI tool in their student life, particularly in research endeavors. This rating reflects their confidence and reliance on ChatGPT to assist them in academic tasks, underlining its significance in supporting their learning journey.

“I can describe my level of trust in utilizing ChatGPT so if akua siyang e-rate maybe naa sa 8 over 10 since kani siya nga ai tool helpful jud siya sa akua as a student especially sa amoang research so mao to akoang ma rate sa iyaha.” (FGD-05)

(I would describe my level of trust in using ChatGPT as an 8 out of 10. As an AI tool, it has been incredibly helpful to me as a student, particularly in my research endeavors. So, that is the rating I would give it)

Moreover, the participant elaborated on their level of trust in ChatGPT, estimating it to be around 80%. They acknowledged that while ChatGPT is still being developed and may not have all the information, it excels in assisting with tasks and activities. Their trust in ChatGPT is bolstered by their prior research into its purpose and functionality, recognizing it as a language tool that retrieves information from the internet. Despite its reliance on online sources, primarily Google, the participant finds ChatGPT's results to be trustworthy, considering its ability to streamline searches and provide relevant information. This perspective reflects a balanced assessment of ChatGPT's capabilities and reliability, acknowledging its strengths while remaining mindful of its limitations. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“Ang level of trust nako sa ChatGPT if e-scale nato is like around 80% mga in ana kay of course kanang gina develop paman gihapon siya, kanang dili papud siya tanan information kaya niya, but then good gihapon siya in making task and activities... ano man gud ni siya language tool, but ang language niya is comes from internet so tanan kanang murag gipadali kang niya ug search everything in the

internet but still ahm iyang mga sources is gikan gihapon ang uban sa Goole or unsa ang mo come up gud sa Google so in a same way to be trusted man pud iyang mga results sa ChatGPT." (FGD-01)

(My level of trust in ChatGPT, if I were to scale it, would be around 80%. Of course, it is still being developed and it doesn't have all the information, but it is still good in making tasks and activities easier. My trust is quite high because when I searched for the meaning of ChatGPT before, I found out that it is a language tool that comes from the internet. Its language is derived from the internet, so it can easily search for everything on the internet. However, its sources still come from Google or other search engines, so in the same way, the results from ChatGPT can also be trusted).

Subsequently, elementary education student expressed a high level of confidence in utilizing ChatGPT for various learning tasks and activities. Despite recognizing the imperfections inherent in AI tools, they attest to ChatGPT's reliability and effectiveness in aiding their academic endeavors consistently. Hence, they confidently rated their trust in ChatGPT at approximately 8 to 10, reflecting their reliance on the platform for educational support and guidance. As what Participant 7 stated that:

As a fourth-year Bachelor of Elementary Education student, I have a high level of confidence in using ChatGPT for learning tasks and activities. While I understand that no AI tool is perfect, ChatGPT has consistently proven to be reliable and effective in assisting me with a range of academic pursuits. So, I would rate my level of trust in ChatGPT at around 8 to 10. (FGD-07)

Building Trust with ChatGPT as an Assistant Learning Tool. This is the fifth code for the first probed issue. Participants' varying levels of trust in ChatGPT as an assistant learning tool reflect a nuanced perspective on its utility and reliability. While some view ChatGPT as a valuable aid that enhances understanding and performance, they also stress out the importance of verifying its responses and not solely relying on them. Conversely, others adopt a more cautious stance, highlighting instances where ChatGPT's answers may diverge from those of other sources, necessitating validation. Overall, participants underscore the importance of critical evaluation and the incorporation of supplementary sources alongside ChatGPT to achieve comprehensive learning outcomes.

Similarly, the participant portrays ChatGPT not as a complete solution but as an indispensable assistant tool in the learning process. They emphasize its pivotal role in providing explanations and elucidating complex concepts, offering clarity where understanding may falter. This underscores ChatGPT's significance in navigating intricate subjects and overcoming challenging learning tasks. By positioning it as a valuable resource, they highlight its capacity to facilitate learning and elevate individual performance. Furthermore, their readiness to advocate for ChatGPT's efficacy among peers underscores its potential as a supportive aid in educational pursuits, emphasizing its role in empowering learners to achieve academic success. As what Participant 5 stated that:

"For me sir, ma describe nako ang ChatGPT as an assistant tool lang jud sya and since language-based lang man jud sya naa lang ang ChatGPT sa ato to help to explain sa mga pangutan na mag struggle ta and also give ideas and provide clear information sa mga complex labi na sa atong mga learning task and activities, kuan pud sir isa pud sya sa gateway para motobag satong mga pangutana na feeling nato lisod pangitaag paagi at the end mahatagan niya, unyag basian sad nato akong performance sir nag improve jd sya, so ma recommend jd nako ni sa uban how good that ChatGPT na mahimong assistant tools satong mga learning activities." (IDI-05)

(ChatGPT as a tool that assists in explaining challenging concepts and providing clear information for complex learning tasks and activities. It can also generate ideas and provide answers to difficult questions. You have observed an improvement in your performance after using ChatGPT, and you would recommend it as a valuable assistant tool for learning activities).

Moreover, Participant emphasized the substantial support ChatGPT offers as an assistant learning tool. However, they emphasized the necessity of not simply copying its responses. Instead, they advocate for reflecting on and customizing the answers to harmonize with individual viewpoints and concepts. This entails challenging oneself to elaborate on and conceptualize the ideas provided by ChatGPT, utilizing it as a guiding resource rather than solely depending on its recommendations. As what Participant 7 said that:

"Dako jd kay siyag tabang satong mga students but then, sama sakong gi ingun dli lang nga copy and paste ba, but then we should ano kanang reflect gud satong kaugalingulon ana nga answer though that is our idea that is what we think, nga dle mongawas satong baba and we should also challenge our selve na mo add pa ana mo conceptualize pa ana nga idea nga gihatag ni ChatGPT, kibali guide lang nato sya para sa atong mga idea." (IDI-07)

(ChatGPT can be a great help to students, but it is important to not just copy and paste its answers. Instead, we should reflect on the answers and think critically about them, adding our own ideas and concepts to further develop the ideas provided by ChatGPT. It should serve as a guide for our own ideas).

Furthermore, the participant describes their level of trust in ChatGPT, likening it to a personal academic assistant. They express confidence in ChatGPT's ability to streamline their academic tasks, particularly in gathering extensive information efficiently. By relying on ChatGPT, they find that they can quickly acquire the information they need, with the majority of its responses being accurate. This positive experience with ChatGPT contributes to their growing trust in its capabilities as an effective learning tool. As what Participant 6 stated that:

"If I am going to describe the level of trust na akong ma kuan sa ChatGP, is for me I can consider that ChatGPT as my personal assistant bitaw in terms of my academics because through chatgpt mn gud murag mas ma lessen na akoang mga kuan buhatonon samot na sa

kanang if mag required ba siya na mag search ug daghang informations so with the use of chatgpt akoa na siyang dali ma acquired ug mostly mn pud tama man iyang ginahatag, so maka gain pud kog trust sa iyaha." (FGD-06)

(In my perspective, I consider ChatGPT as my personal academic assistant, as it aids me in reducing my workload by searching for information. Additionally, I find that it provides mostly accurate information, which has helped me build trust in it).

Conversely, the participant expressed a mixed perspective, describing their trust in ChatGPT. They highlighted instances where the answers provided by ChatGPT differed from those obtained from other websites, leading to doubt regarding its reliability. This comparison with alternative sources suggested a level of skepticism about the accuracy and consistency of ChatGPT's responses, indicating a cautious approach to trusting its output. As what Participant 3 stated that:

"So para nako kay 50-50 sya kay there are times na mag ask kag question tapos lahi na ang mo gawas na answer kong e-compare nimo sya other website na mag provide sad ug information." (IDI-03)

(In my opinion, ChatGPT's reliability is around 50-50, as there are instances when its answers may differ from the information provided by other websites. Therefore, I compare its answers with other sources to ensure accuracy).

In relation to that, Participant articulated a balanced viewpoint regarding their reliance on ChatGPT. They recognized that although ChatGPT doesn't always provide accurate answers to every query, it effectively addresses their specific concerns and offers satisfactory responses to their inquiries. Consequently, they assessed their level of trust in ChatGPT as being evenly split. As what Participant 4 stated that:

"So my level of trusting in utilizing in ChtGPT is 50-50, because naay uban nga dili tanan ma answer sa ChatGPT. However, iyang ma address ang akoang mga concern like mga questions na akong mga gipangutana sa iyaha so my level of trust is 50-50 jud or 50%." (FGD-03)

(My level of trust in using ChatGPT is 50-50, because not all questions can be answered by ChatGPT. However, it can address some of my concerns and answer some of my questions, so my level of trust is also 50-50 or 50%).

The participant's rating of 6 to 7 out of 10 for ChatGPT's reliability suggested that while they find it generally useful, they had reservations about its consistency in providing accurate and up-to-date information. They likely arrived at this rating based on their experiences where ChatGPT's responses may have been outdated or not entirely reliable. As a result, they emphasized the importance of cross-referencing ChatGPT's answers with information from other sources to verify their accuracy. As what Participant 4 stated that:

"Ahm, ug I rate nako sya siguro nasa 6 to 7 over 10, because usahay iyang mga result is dle up to date or dle sya updated so kailangan gihapon nimo sya I very sa laing sources." (IDI-04)

(I would rate ChatGPT around 6 to 7 out of 10. Sometimes, the results it provides are not up-to-date, so it is still necessary to verify the information from other sources).

The Need of Becoming a Responsible User of ChatGPT. Based on information gleaned from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it is asserted that elementary education students engage in understanding the necessity of becoming responsible users of ChatGPT. The discussions underscore the importance of ensuring a balanced utilization of ChatGPT, emphasizing the need for students to navigate the tool responsibly. Participants advocate for peer discussions aimed at promoting proper navigation and usage of ChatGPT, fostering a culture of responsibility and accountability among elementary education students. These discussions highlight the imperative for students to recognize their role in using ChatGPT ethically and effectively, contributing to a positive learning environment and facilitating meaningful educational experiences.

Ensuring a balance Use of ChatGPT. This is the sixth code for the first probed issue. Participants highlighting the importance that they need to ecognize both its benefits and the need for caution. While they acknowledge the assistance ChatGPT provides, they also emphasized the importance of not overrelying on it. This balanced approach reflects their commitment to preserving the integrity of their own critical thinking skills and ensuring the accuracy of the information they receive from ChatGPT.

Similarly, the participant acknowledges the importance of their own critical thinking skills in conjunction with their use of ChatGPT. This perspective shapes their overall perception of the tool, as they aim to strike a balance between leveraging its potential benefits and verifying the accuracy and reliability of the information it provides. This approach reflects a thoughtful and cautious attitude towards integrating technology into their learning process, demonstrating a commitment to both utilizing available resources effectively and ensuring the integrity of their academic endeavors. As what Participant 1 stated that:

"I use my own critical thinking skills. This perception influences my own perception of ChatGPT, as I strive to maintain a balance between utilizing its potential benefits and ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the information it provide." (ID-01)

(I also use my critical thinking skills when using ChatGPT. This perception influences my own view of the AI, as I aim to balance its potential benefits with the accuracy and reliability of the information it provides).

Moreover, user highlights that they have observed others also utilizing this AI tool, indicating its widespread use and beneficial impact among their peers. It was emphasized that the importance of not over-relying on AI technology, cautioning against its excessive use. This perspective underscores the need for moderation and discernment in the utilization of AI tools like ChatGPT, acknowledging their value while also advocating for responsible and balanced usage. As what Participant 2 said that:

“makita pud nako sa ila na nagagamit pud d i sila ani nga A.I since nakatabang pud d i sa ila ang ChatGPT. But then mao lang to sir dili lang jud kay nato abusohon sa paggamit sa A.I.” (IDI0-02)

(I have observed that my peers also use this AI, including ChatGPT, because it helps them. However, I believe that we should not abuse the use of AI).

Furthermore, the user expressed the efficiency of ChatGPT, noting that even if the accuracy of the information is sometimes uncertain, it is still effective to find answers compared to Google. However, the importance of a balanced use of ChatGPT, indicating that while it can be beneficial for elaborating on topics or lessons, it should not be solely relied upon. This highlights the need for users to judiciously integrate ChatGPT into their learning processes, ensuring that its use complements rather than replaces traditional research methods and critical thinking skills. As What Participant 3 stated that:

“Efficient man jud ang ChatGPT bisan 50-50 ang katinood sa information basta mas dali siya mapangitaan ug tubag kaysa sa Google maong mas better pud siya gamiton if gusto jud ka na mas ma illaborate ang is aka topic or ang is aka lesson.” (IDI-03)

(ChatGPT is efficient, even if the accuracy of the information is only 50%. It can provide answers faster than Google, making it a better option if you want to elaborate on a topic or lesson quickly).

Peer Discussion on the Proper Navigation of ChatGPT. This is the seventh code for the first probed issue. Participants observed that their peers leveraging ChatGPT effectively, which not only influences their perception of ChatGPT's utility but also boosts their confidence in integrating it into their learning processes. The shared experiences and insights about using ChatGPT foster a collaborative learning environment, wherein peers exchange tips and strategies to enhance their use of ChatGPT. This collective sentiment to learning and problem-solving emphasized the importance of peer influence in adopting and navigating new technologies, emphasizing the role of communal learning in maximizing the benefits of tools like ChatGPT.

Similarly, the participant's insights resonate with the broader discourse among peers regarding the proper navigation of ChatGPT. By observing the widespread use and perceived usefulness of ChatGPT among peers, the participant gains confidence in utilizing the tool themselves. This highlights the importance of peer discussions in shaping individual perceptions and behaviors towards AI tools like ChatGPT. Through sharing experiences and insights, peers can collectively navigate and understand how to effectively leverage ChatGPT as a learning aid while also maintaining a balanced approach to its usage. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“So, ang akola lang ma perceive no among my peers is kanang makita man nako sa ilaha nga kuan bitaw useful pud kaayo bitaw ang pagamit ug ChatGPT then nakita pud nako sa ilaha na murag dali nalang nga buhaton nila ilang mga task ba tungod sa ChatGPT, so naka kuan pud na sa akoang perception about ChatGPT kay kuan man kanang , bali nag nag delve pud ko ug confident na mo gamit ug ChtGPT kay naa mn pud mga kauban nako na nagagamit bitaw.” (FGD-06)

(So, what I perceive from my peers is that they find ChatGPT to be very useful and helpful in completing their tasks. I have observed that they are able to accomplish their tasks more easily with the help of ChatGPT. This has also influenced my own perception of ChatGPT, and I have become more confident in using it because I have seen my peers using it effectively).

Moreover, The participant elaborates on the shared perception among peers regarding the value of ChatGPT as a learning tool. They emphasize that peers likely view ChatGPT as a convenient resource for obtaining quick and relevant information to support academic endeavors. This perception is likely shaped by their own experiences or observations of ChatGPT's effectiveness in assisting with various learning tasks. Importantly, the participant notes that their peers' positive perception of ChatGPT also influences their own perspective. During collaborative discussions, where experiences and tips are shared, the participant recognizes a sense of collective learning and understanding emerging. Through these interactions, facilitated by ChatGPT, peers collaborate to maximize the tool's benefits, fostering a collective effort towards enhancing overall learning outcomes. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“The same sa akola na they likely see it as a convenient resource na kuan gani they can provide quick and relevant information to aid in our academic pursuits. So this perception may stem from their own experiences or observations of the effectiveness of ChatGPT in assisting with various learning tasks. And their positive perception pud of the ChatGPT is likely influences my own perception sa kaning nay time na mag tapok-tapok mi, tapos mag share mi sa among experience or amoang mga tips on how this AI its effective to use...nakita nako ang sense of collaboration like throug lang sa ChatGPT.”(FGD-07)

(Similarly, I likely see ChatGPT as a convenient resource because it can provide quick and relevant information that supports our academic pursuits. This perception may stem from my own experiences or observations of ChatGPT's effectiveness in assisting with various learning tasks. Moreover, the positive perception of ChatGPT by others likely influences my own perception. For instance, when we gather and share our experiences or tips on how to effectively use this AI, it fosters a sense of collaboration. Through ChatGPT, we collaboratively learn and understand how to maximize its benefits, enhancing our collective learning experience.).

Techniques in Using ChatGPT as Learning Resource. Based on the information gathered from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it is claimed that elementary education students engage in employing various techniques to maximize their use of ChatGPT as a learning resource. These techniques include actively seeking out other similar apps and websites to supplement their learning, contextualizing and evaluating the information provided by ChatGPT, and consulting with peers and other sources for additional insights. By adopting these strategies, students enhance their understanding and critical thinking skills, effectively leveraging ChatGPT to support their educational endeavors.

Look for Other Similar Apps and Websites. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Participants' proactive measures in ensuring the accuracy and security of the information provided by ChatGPT. They shared instances of doubting ChatGPT's responses, leading them to seek verification through other applications, web searches, and directly on Google. This process was often motivated by concerns over the currency, accuracy, and privacy of the information obtained from ChatGPT.

Similarly, participant shared a similar experience of doubting a response provided by ChatGPT, likely due to unfamiliar terms. To address this, they took proactive steps by searching for alternative apps and conducting browser searches to verify if the information aligns with other sources. This approach was aimed at ensuring the accuracy of the information obtained from ChatGPT. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Yes sir, naka experienced ko na nag doubt ko sa isa ka answer sa gihatag sa ChatGPT seguro dili pud kay nako familiar ang words, and then kuan kaning akong gi buhat ato sir is nangita ko ug lahi na app, gi search nako sya sa Browser, and Google to verify ug parehas ba sila ug point or answer or something naa ba silay kapariha, so in ato akong gi buhat para ma verify nako sya ug tama ba.” (IDI-02)

(Indeed, there have been instances where I doubted a ChatGPT's answer, likely due to unfamiliar words. In response, I sought out another application, conducted a browser search, and used Google to cross-verify if they shared similar points or answers. This was my approach to confirming the accuracy of the information).

Moreover, in this statement, the participant underscores their cautious approach to using ChatGPT by expressing their doubts about the accuracy of the information it provides. They emphasize the importance of verifying ChatGPT's responses by cross-referencing them with information from other reliable sources like Google or other websites. This reflects the participant's proactive attitude towards ensuring the credibility and reliability of the information obtained through ChatGPT. By seeking confirmation from external sources, they demonstrate a responsible approach to using AI tools and mitigating potential inaccuracies or misinformation. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“So for me, it is a yes since I always wonder if tama ba ng mga information na gi hatag ni ChatGPT. So gina address nako sya sa by confirming mismo sa Google or other website weather the informations na gihatag ni ChatGPT is concrete or ga exist ba jud siya.” (IDI0-3)

(So, for me, it is a yes, as I often wonder about the accuracy of the information provided by ChatGPT. I address this concern by cross-verifying the information on Google or other websites to confirm its validity. Additionally, I have reservations about the security of my account and personal information. Before logging into ChatGPT, I asked my classmates and other users if they had encountered issues with personal information being accessed. They assured me that it has not been a problem for them. Hence, I continue to use ChatGPT).

Additionally, the participant's concern about ChatGPT occasionally offering outdated or inaccurate information, and even acknowledging mistakes, highlights the need to verify information from alternative sources to guarantee accuracy and reliability. This acknowledgment underlined awareness of the potential limitations of AI tools like ChatGPT and their proactive approach to mitigating these risks by cross-referencing information. By recognizing the possibility of errors and outdated content, the participant emphasizes the importance of employing critical thinking skills and consulting multiple sources to ensure the accuracy of information obtained through ChatGPT. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“Like what I haved said kanina ChatGPT is murag naga inform sya sa imoha or ang mga information na iyang mahatag dle updated and dili pud accurate iyang mga information sahay and mo ingun man sad sya na naa siyay mistake so kailangan gyud gihapon nato mo consider na mangita ug lain sources.” (IDI-04)

(As I mentioned earlier, ChatGPT provides information that may not be updated or accurate. It may also admit to making mistakes, so it is important to consider looking for other sources as well.)

Subsequently, Participant's proactive approach to validating information from ChatGPT highlights the importance of critical thinking and verification in utilizing AI tools for learning. Their past experiences of doubting ChatGPT's outputs demonstrate the necessity of corroborating information from multiple sources to ensure accuracy and reliability. This insight underscores the role of users in exercising discernment and seeking supplementary resources to enhance the trustworthiness of AI-generated content, thereby promoting informed decision-making and learning efficacy. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“Yes, maingun jd nako nga naa jud instances nga mag duha-duha ko sa information or result na gihatag sa ChatGPT like kani ba tanang result is useful ba syay connection sa matag-usa, despite ana dili lang pud ko always mag rely sa ChatGPT ug gina sure nalng pud gani

nako sa iyang mga result na gihatag,so mag search nalang pud ko sa laing web para sa additional information sir ug kong tama baa ng ginahatag sa ChatGPT.” (IDI-05)

(Yes, there are instances where I doubt the information or outcomes provided by ChatGPT. I wonder if all of the findings are valuable and related to one another. Despite this, I do not always depend only on ChatGPT and make sure to double-check the findings. I look for extra information on other websites to ensure that the information supplied by ChatGPT is correct).

To add, Participant's experience revealed ChatGPT's limitations in research tasks, where its answers seemed forced and lacked alignment with expectations, prompting doubts about reliability. They emphasized the importance of cross-referencing AI-generated content with credible sources. Despite this, they recognized ChatGPT's utility in tasks where detailed references were unnecessary. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“So, one experience dati is gi used nako ang Chatgpt to come up with kaning sa isulod gud nako to sa research unta but then ang ni gawas is kanang ni try hard kaayu ang ChatGPT to come up with kanang answers na akoa gud na gusto, but then sometimes suspicious kaayu kay curative ra kaayu kanang align ra kaayu and then if mo search ka sa Google is actually mag lisod paka na mag search gud ato na information so gi isa-isa nako iyang mga cite na author na gihatag didto ako jud pud gi search ug tama bani na title ug ang sulod ato na research study but dili mn ,nya mao to nag doubt ko never na nako gi use ang ChatGPT na instances na mga in ato.” (FGD-01)

(I used ChatGPT to come up with an introduction for my research, but the answers it provided were not exactly what I was looking for. Sometimes, the information provided by ChatGPT seemed too generic and did not align with what I needed. When I searched for the same information on Google, it was difficult to find. So, I checked the websites and authors that ChatGPT provided, but I could not find the exact title and research study. This made me doubt the reliability of ChatGPT, and I have not used it since then for my research).

Furthermore, the participant shared instances where they experienced doubt regarding the information provided by ChatGPT. This doubt arose when they noticed discrepancies between ChatGPT's responses and the results obtained from their own Google searches. Such experiences prompted the participant to adopt a cautious approach and seek validation by cross-referencing ChatGPT's information with external sources like Google. This highlights the participant's inclination towards critical thinking and the importance they place on verifying the accuracy of AI-generated content before accepting it as reliable. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Sometimes ug magamit ko ug ChatGPT usahay mag duda pud ko saiyang ginahatag na information since kanang naka try man gud ko na nag ask ko sa iyang question no kay layo rai yang gihatag na information unya katong nag search pud ko sa Google dili pud siya mao, layo ra d i siya sa akoang gi pangayo sa iyaha mao nang usahay mag doubt ko, unya gina address nako to mao to mo agto ko ug Google akoang gina check ug tama ba iyang informations na gi provide sa akoa.” (FGD-02)

(Sometimes when I use ChatGPT, I doubt the information it provides because the answers can be far-off from what I was expecting. Even when I search for the same question on Google, the information is different. This makes me doubt the accuracy of the information provided by ChatGPT. To address this, I cross-check the information by using Google to see if the information provided by ChatGPT is correct).

Additionally, participant 3 expressed doubts about relying solely on ChatGPT for information, as there may be instances of unreliable responses. To address this concern and cope with uncertainties, participants mentioned using grammar checkers on various websites or apps to verify answers received from ChatGPT. This approach helps them ensure the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained, mitigating potential risks associated with relying solely on AI-generated responses.,

“Yes, naakoy doubt sa utilizing sa ChatGPT parehas anang sa mag duha-duha ko kong basin naay uban dili reliable na mga information so ang buhaton nako para ma cope up na nga mga struggles or kana nga mga pag duha-duha is ga gamit ko ug mga grammar checker sa uban website or apps para ma check to akoang answer gikan sa ChatGPT.” (FGD-03)

(Yes, I have experienced doubts when using ChatGPT, and I sometimes worry that there might be unreliable information. To cope with these uncertainties, I use grammar checkers on other websites or apps to check my answers from ChatGPT).

Contextualize and Evaluate the Information. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Participants articulated a cautious approach towards information provided by ChatGPT, highlighting their efforts to contextualize and evaluate the accuracy and relevance of such information. Doubts about the reliability of ChatGPT's responses prompted users to not only question the information but also to actively seek verification through fact-checking tools and websites. This process involved a critical assessment of whether the information was current or outdated. The engagement with AI tools, as discussed by the participants, is nuanced. While they recognize the utility of such tools in providing assistance, there's a clear understanding that reliance on these technologies should be balanced with critical thinking and personal input. The information provided by ChatGPT is seen as a starting point, which needs to be critically assessed, contextualized, and augmented by the user's own knowledge and research.

Similarly, Participant's expressed skepticism regarding the reliability of information obtained from ChatGPT, citing instances of inaccuracies. To address this concern, they adopted a methodical approach of contextualizing the information provided, particularly when it was extensive. In response to uncertainties, they employed fact-checking tools and websites to verify the information's validity, assessing its current status and whether it remained relevant or outdated. This meticulous verification process reflects their commitment

to ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained from ChatGPT. As what Participant 6 said that:

“Well yes, and I felt doubt about the information provided by the ChatGPT, just what I have said earlier some information given by the ChatGPT is not an accurate, so pamaagi ana ako jud gina contextualize jud nakong mga information like lengthy na iyang gina provide, so to address this uncertainties, akong gina buhat is I used fact cheking tools or websites to clearly verified the information I gathered from the ChatGPT kong still nga ga exist paba sya karon, outdated or updated ba sya.” (IDI-06)

(Well, yes, and I often feel doubt about the information provided by ChatGPT. As I mentioned earlier, some information given by ChatGPT may not be accurate. To address this uncertainty, I contextualize the information it provides, especially when it is lengthy. To further verify the information, I use fact-checking tools or websites to determine its current existence and whether it is outdated or updated).

Moreover, Participant’s emphasized that while ChatGPT is undeniably beneficial to students, it shouldn't be used merely for copying and pasting information. Instead, they advocated for critical reflection on the provided answers, encouraging individuals to consider their own understanding and perspectives. They stressed the importance of not simply regurgitating ChatGPT's responses but rather challenging oneself to enhance and contextualize the ideas presented by the tool. In this way, they viewed ChatGPT as a guiding resource rather than a definitive source of knowledge, promoting active engagement and critical thinking among users. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Dako kay syag tabang satong mga students but then, sama sakong gi ingun dli lang nga copy and paste ba, but then we should ano kanang reflect gud satong kaugalingulon ana nga answer though that's our idea that is what we think, nga dle mongawas satong baba and we should also challenge our selve na mo add pa ana mo contextualize pa ana nga idea nga gihatag ni ChatGPT, kibali guide lang nato sya para sa atong mga idea.” (IDI-07)

(It is a big help for our students, but then, I always say it is not just about copying and pasting, but we should also reflect deeply on our own thoughts about that answer, even if it is our own idea, what we think. It should not just come from our mouth, and we should also challenge ourselves to add more to it and contextualize the idea provided by ChatGPT. It is just a guide for our own ideas).

Additionally, participants highlighted instances where they felt uncertain about the responses provided by ChatGPT, noting discrepancies between the complexity of the answers and their own perceived level of intelligence. This discrepancy sometimes led to doubt and apprehension, particularly concerning the possibility of their teachers using similar tools. Consequently, they expressed a need to rephrase or modify the provided answers to align more closely with their own understanding, emphasizing the importance of personalization and refinement in utilizing ChatGPT's responses effectively. As what Participant 6 said that:

“Naa man gud times nga inig mag ask kag question bali murag kuan kaayu ug imohaang e-compare imohang level of intelligence sa iyang gina provide na answer murag dili bitaw mag tugma murag kuan kaayu murag deep ra kaayu ang ginahatag ni ChatGPT ba mao nang murag dli mn ko in anig inansweran unya makulbaan ko basig mag doubt pud ang akoang maistra uy basin lahi ni basin naga gamit nanig in ani, so akoang ginabuhat kay kuan lang ug naay answer akoang gina kuan murag gi in my own ba ,usabon pud nako ba , kanang nakoy i usab-usab.” (FGD-06)

(There are times when I ask a question, but it seems like it is not comparing its level of intelligence to the answer it provides, as if it's not really understanding or going deep into the topic. So, I doubt the answer and question my own understanding, wondering if it is just me or if there is something off with the tool. To address this, I try to rephrase the question or use my own words to see if I can get a more accurate answer. I also try to use the same question again to see if I get the same response).

In a similar vein, participants acknowledged experiencing uncertainty or doubt regarding the information provided by ChatGPT. When encountering such uncertainties, they adopted various strategies to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the information. These strategies included rephrasing or reformulating queries to ChatGPT to elicit more precise and relevant responses. Additionally, they emphasized the importance of adjusting the wording of their questions to enhance clarity and minimize uncertainties associated with the responses provided by the tool. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“Yes, there have been instances where I have felt uncertain or doubtful about the information provided by ChatGPT. When faced with such uncertainties, I employ several strategies to verify the accuracy and reliability of the information. First, is e-rephrase or reformulate my queries to ChatGPT to obtain more accurate and relevant responses. Aside pajud ana is kanang adjusting sa mga wordings gani sa every sakong mga pangutana so the it can help to clarify the information and reduce uncertainties.” (FGD-07)

(Yes, there have been instances where I have felt uncertain or doubtful about the information provided by ChatGPT. When faced with such uncertainties, I employ several strategies to verify the accuracy and reliability of the information. First, I rephrase or reformulate my queries to ChatGPT to obtain more accurate and relevant responses. Additionally, I adjust the wordings of my questions to help clarify the information and reduce uncertainties).

Consulting Peers and Others. This is the third code for the second probed issue. When encountering uncertainties or doubts about the information provided by ChatGPT, participants adopted various strategies to address them. By employing these measures, participants were able to verify the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained from ChatGPT, allowing them to make informed decisions

about its usage.

Similarly, participants expressed instances where they experienced uncertainty or doubt regarding the information provided by ChatGPT. To mitigate these uncertainties, they sought assistance from peers, searched for supplementary sources, and cross-checked the information with their own understanding of the subject matter. This multifaceted approach enabled them to validate the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained through ChatGPT, ensuring a more informed utilization of the platform. As what Participant stated that:

“Yes, I have felt uncertain or doubt about information provided by ChatGPT. To address these uncertainties, I have consulted with my peers, searched for additional sources, and cross-referenced the information with my own knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. This approach has helped me verify the accuracy and reliability of the information provided by ChatGPT.” (IDI-01)

(Yes, I have felt uncertain or doubtful about the information provided by ChatGPT. To address these uncertainties, I have consulted with my peers, searched for additional sources, and cross-referenced the information with my own knowledge and understanding of the subject matter. This approach has helped me verify the accuracy and reliability of the information provided by ChatGPT).

In connection to that, users expressed apprehension regarding the security of their account and personal information, prompting them to seek reassurance from peers who also use ChatGPT. Upon receiving confirmation that their classmates hadn't encountered issues with personal information being compromised, they continued to utilize ChatGPT. As what Participant 3 said that:

“Nag doubt sad ko na basin ma hack akong account or ma access akong mga personal information and before ko nag log in aning ChatGPT nag ask sajd ko first sakong mga classmates ug sa uban nga nagagamit ug ChatGPT kong naga kuha ba sila ug personal information, so ana sila dili daw. So until now ginagamit najd nako ang ChatGPT.” (IDI0-3)

(Additionally, I have reservations about the security of my account and personal information. Before logging into ChatGPT, I asked my classmates and other users if they had encountered issues with personal information being accessed. They assured me that it hasn't been a problem for them. Hence, I continue to use ChatGPT).

Essential Development of ChatGPT for its Efficiency and Efficacy. Based on the information gathered from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, it is asserted that elementary education students engage in advocating for the essential development of ChatGPT to enhance its efficiency and efficacy in educational contexts. Students emphasize the need to improve its accuracy and reliability, ensuring that the information provided aligns closely with educational standards and requirements. Additionally, they highlight the importance of developing its user interface and database to make it more user-friendly and comprehensive. By advocating for these enhancements, students aim to optimize their learning experiences and maximize the potential benefits of using ChatGPT as an educational tool.

Improve Its Accuracy and Reliability in Educational Context. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participant's proposed various suggestions to enhance the accuracy and reliability of ChatGPT in educational settings. They emphasized the importance of improved fact-checking tools and a better understanding of context to ensure the provision of accurate information. By implementing these improvements, ChatGPT can enhance its utility and reliability, providing students with more dependable assistance in their academic pursuits.

In connection to that, participant recommended specific improvements and features for ChatGPT. These suggestions include enhancing accuracy and reliability by implementing measures such as improved fact-checking mechanisms and better contextual understanding. By incorporating these enhancements, ChatGPT can better serve students in their academic pursuits, providing them with more dependable assistance and contributing to a more effective learning experience.

(Based on my experiences, I would suggest the following improvements and features for ChatGPT to enhance its utility and reliability in educational contexts; Just like to Improved accuracy and reliability in order to provide more accurate and reliable information). (IDI-01)

Similarly, participant emphasized the importance of improving ChatGPT's fact-checking tools and understanding of context to enhance its utility and reliability in educational settings. By implementing these improvements, ChatGPT can become a more valuable and reliable AI tool for students in their educational journey. The need for accurate and reliable information is crucial in educational contexts, and AI tools like ChatGPT must prioritize this in order to be useful and trustworthy for students. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“So as a student, I would suggest several improvements to enhance ChatGPTs' utility and reliability in the educational context just like to improve their fact-checking tools as well as to enhance their understanding of context, with that by implementing these improvements, ChatGPT can become a more valuable and reliable A.I tool from for the future and for the students for the educational journey”. (IDI-06)

(As a student, I would like to suggest several improvements to enhance ChatGPTs' utility and reliability in the educational context, such as improving their fact-checking tools and enhancing their understanding of context. By implementing these improvements, ChatGPT can become a more valuable and reliable AI tool for future students and their educational journey).

Moreover, to improve ChatGPT's fact-checking tools for educational settings, several suggestions have been proposed. One of the most important improvements is to enhance its understanding of context. This can be achieved by training the model on a diverse range of educational materials, including textbooks, academic papers, and other educational resources. By doing so, ChatGPT can better understand the nuances of different subjects and provide more accurate and relevant responses. As what Participant 6 stated that:

“Sa ChatGPT dapat mag provide silag updated na answer na relevant karon sa atoa as a student.” (FGD-06)

(In ChatGPT, they should provide updated answers that are relevant to us as students).

Development of Its User Interface and Database. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Participant's highlighted the need to enhance ChatGPT's user interface for better intuitiveness and user-friendliness, as well as to expand its knowledge base to cover a broader range of subjects and topics. Moreover, there's a desire to improve language support, particularly for Filipino and other regional languages. Additionally, there's an emphasis on increasing reliability in educational contexts by engaging with authoritative authors and ensuring the credibility of sourced information, especially for academic research purposes. These suggestions aim to elevate ChatGPT's utility and reliability, making it more effective and valuable for users in educational settings.

Similarly, as for expanding the knowledge base, ChatGPT can cover a wider range of subjects and topics to cater to the diverse needs of users. This can be achieved by integrating more data sources and using advanced algorithms to process and analyze the information. By doing so, ChatGPT can provide more accurate and relevant answers to a broader set of questions. As what Participant 1 said that:

“Improve the user interface to make it more intuitive and user-friendly and also expanded knowledge base para mas ma cover ang mga wider range of subjects and topics.” (IDI-01)

(Improve the user interface to make it more intuitive and user-friendly, and also expand the knowledge base to cover a wider range of subjects and topics).

Moreover, to have better language support for non-English speaking users, particularly in the Philippines where Filipino is widely spoken. Participant suggests improving the language capabilities of ChatGPT, particularly in Filipino, to cater to the needs of Filipino users and make it more reliable in the Philippine context. It also emphasized the importance of improving the AI's ability to provide concrete and reliable information from authors, which is crucial in academic and research contexts. As what Participant 7 stated that:

“I want to improve ChatGPT kanang mga language especially kanang mga Filipino to have a context na makasabot na siyag tagalog or other language na ma rely sa atoa sa Pilipinas. And I hope na mas mapa improve pa enhancing its utility reliability in educational context, ang isapa sa akoo is that sa mga authors pud, dili man gud kaayu siya usually maka kita concrete na information na ma search sad gani nimo sa lain website ana gud, unta mas mo engage pa pud sya nga makakita ug author na in line ana nga kuan kay lisod kaayu mangita, specially sa RRL so mao to so i try nako na next if naa naba sya.” (IDI-07)

(I want to improve ChatGPT's language capabilities, especially in Filipino, to understand Tagalog and other languages commonly used in the Philippines. I also hope to enhance its utility and reliability in educational contexts. One of my concerns is that, unlike other websites where you can find concrete information through search, ChatGPT sometimes struggles in this regard. I hope it can become more engaging and provide access to authors who specialize in relevant topics. This would be particularly helpful in conducting literature reviews.)

Development of its Features and Algorithms. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses from in-depth interviews and focus grouped discussion, it is claimed that elementary education students engage in advocating for the development of ChatGPT's features and algorithms. This emerging theme highlights students' desire for ChatGPT to evolve to better suit their educational needs. Students express interest in features such as generating pictures alongside text, providing hyperlinks and references, and improving the overall functionality of the tool. By incorporating these enhancements, students anticipate a more enriched learning experience, enabling them to access diverse forms of information and resources seamlessly.

Generate Pictures Alongside with Text. This is the third code for the third probed issue. The participant's suggested enhancing ChatGPT's utility by integrating picture generation alongside text. It was emphasized by the that having visual aids such as images, graphs, or 3D objects would significantly improve comprehension and retention of information, especially in educational settings. By providing visual representations alongside textual content, ChatGPT could help users grasp concepts more easily and make learning more engaging.

In a similar vein, the participant expressed a desire for ChatGPT to have the capability to generate images alongside textual information. Users believed that the addition of visual elements would enhance comprehension, as certain concepts or ideas might be more easily understood through images rather than text alone. By providing images that correspond with verbal explanations, ChatGPT could bridge comprehension gaps, particularly when dealing with complex topics or when differentiating between concepts that are verbally similar yet distinct in meaning. This capability would not only make the learning process more engaging but also more effective, allowing users to grasp and retain information with greater ease. The suggestion highlights a desire for a more multimodal approach to information retrieval and learning, acknowledging the diverse ways in which people process and understand new information. As what Participant 2 stated that:

“Seguro sir kay diba ang ChatGPT is language base mn sya po , maybe ang akoa lang ani ma ano is ma generate nila ang picture sir , kay kanang mas okay man gus sya sir na naa na siyay language at the same time naa pud syay image mapakita kay mas dali lang sya ma gets nimo, kay naay mga words sir na same-same gani ug thought sir but ug naa siyay mahatag na picture maka ingun ta na lahi d i iyang pasabot so mas ma grasp nato ug tarong atong mga content or ang mga ideas na gina search po sa ChatGPT.” (IDI-02)

(I think ChatGPT is language-based, but what I suggest is that they can also generate pictures. It would be better if they can show images while also having language capabilities because it would be easier to understand and grasp the content or ideas being searched on ChatGPT. There are words and thoughts that are the same, but having a corresponding picture can help clarify and distinguish the meaning, making it easier to understand).

In connection to that, another participant emphasizes the potential benefit of ChatGPT generating visual content such as pictures or illustrations to accompany its textual data. This capability would be particularly valuable when the need arises to visualize complex ideas or data, enhancing the user's ability to grasp and interpret information more effectively. By providing a visual representation, ChatGPT could significantly aid in the comprehension of concepts that are difficult to understand through text alone. This suggestion points towards a growing demand for AI tools that cater to a wider range of learning preferences, incorporating visual aids to facilitate a more holistic understanding of the content being explored. As what Participant 3 said that:

“For me I would suggest sa utility kay mag provide or mag generate na si ChatGPT ug pictures or illustration sa data kay there are times man gud na need nakog illustration sa data or pictures, para ma visualize nako ang mga idea na in anion d i sya”. (IDI-03)

(For me, I would suggest improving the utility of ChatGPT by having it provide or generate pictures or illustrations for the data. There are times when an illustration or picture is needed to visualize the ideas or data, and ChatGPT can help with that.”

Moreover, building on the theme of enhancing ChatGPT's utility for educational purposes, the perspective of an elementary education student brings a unique dimension to the conversation. This participant underlines the significant potential of integrating visual aids, such as images, graphs, and 3D objects, into ChatGPT's functionalities. They articulate a specific need for these tools, grounding their argument in the context of preparing for demo teaching sessions, a critical component of their training as future elementary educators. The emphasis on creativity and the necessity to make instructional materials both engaging and colorful speaks to the broader educational mandate of fostering stimulating learning environments. By integrating such features, ChatGPT could significantly enhance its appeal and utility for students in education-related fields, empowering them to create more dynamic and effective teaching materials. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“As an education student, I would like to ChatGPT to install images, graphs or 3D objects, because those tools have mentioned are very useful to me since I am elementary education student, and it is because we are obliged to conduct our demo teaching since I am an elementary in the making so it is label to us should our IM'S should be creative and colorful so I would like to ChatGPT to install those mentioned above, because those are very useful to me in the future.” (IDI-05)

(As an education student, I would like ChatGPT to include images, graphs, or 3D objects because those tools are very useful for me as I am an elementary education student. We are required to conduct demo teaching, and it is essential for our instructional materials to be creative and visually appealing. Therefore, I recommend that ChatGPT incorporate those features to help me in the future).

Furthermore, ChatGPT represent a significant step towards making the AI tool more interactive, versatile, and personalized. By enabling ChatGPT to understand and generate visual content, such as images and illustrations, alongside text, users could benefit from a more immersive and comprehensive experience. This functionality would not only aid in educational tasks but also enhance creativity and problem-solving capabilities. Additionally, allowing users to upload personal files and ask questions related to them adds a layer of customization and specificity to the interaction, catering to individual needs and preferences. These improvements would elevate ChatGPT from a text-based assistant to a more dynamic and adaptive tool, capable of supporting a wide range of tasks and facilitating deeper engagement and understanding. As what Participant 1 stated that:

“So again akong e-suggest for the feature ChatGPT to be able to read ka ng image gud and to be able to generate image pud according sa prompt nga akong gihatag, another one is hopefully sunod is to be able napod na maka-upload na ko sa akong own files and then maka ask nako ug questions acording to those files na gi upload nako ana gud siya na features”. (FGD-01)

(So, my suggestions for enhancing ChatGPT include the ability to read and generate images based on prompts provided. Additionally, I would like to see a feature where users can upload their own files and ask questions related to those files. These features would greatly expand ChatGPT's functionality and make it even more useful for various tasks).

Subsequently, integrating image recognition capabilities into ChatGPT would greatly enhance its utility. This ability to process and respond to images would streamline the utilization of ChatGPT, allowing for more efficient and effective communication of information. By being able to incorporate visuals into their queries and explanations, would not only simplify complex concepts but also cater to different learning styles and enhance overall comprehension. This feature would undoubtedly enrich the educational experience for both educators and learners alike, fostering more engaging and interactive interactions within the learning environment. As what Participant 3 stated that:

“So my suggestion to the ChatGPT as a future educator soon, unta ma integrate na ang naay image ang ChatGPT para mas mapadali ug ma utilize ang akong answers kong naay image”. (FGD-03)

(As a future educator, my suggestion for ChatGPT is to integrate the ability to read and generate images, which would make it easier and more efficient to utilize answers with images).

Lastly, the participant suggested that in incorporating the ability to generate images based on the addressed question would be valuable. This feature would facilitate easier understanding of the information presented, aligning with participants' feedback on enhancing comprehension through visual aids. By providing diverse ways of presenting data and concepts, ChatGPT can cater to different learning styles and preferences, thereby improving the overall user experience and effectiveness of the tool in educational contexts. As what Participant stated that:

“Interms of suggestion naman or features for this is it can generate pud ug mga graphs or mga tables, and also sama sa ilang ingun na it can generate also a images base satong gi address na question para mas masabtan lan nato niya’g dali”. (FGD-07)

(In terms of suggestions or features for this, it can also generate graphs or tables, and just like before, it can generate images based on the addressed question to make it easier for us to understand).

Provide Hyperlink and Its References. This is the fourth code for the probed issue. Participant’s highlighted the importance of privacy and security features in ChatGPT to ensure the safety of users' information and usage of the platform. They suggested implementing measures to safeguard users' privacy by ensuring that their information is not publicly posted and enhancing security protocols to protect users' data. This recommendation underscores the need for ChatGPT to prioritize user privacy and security, fostering a safe and trusted environment for users to interact with the platform. By addressing these concerns, ChatGPT can enhance user confidence and promote a more secure user experience.

In connection to that, the participant suggested that ChatGPT could enhance its utility by providing links or citations alongside its responses. This feature would enable users to verify the credibility and validity of the information provided. Such a capability would not only support users in cross-checking facts but also in assessing the sources of information, fostering a more informed and critical approach to learning and research. This recommendation highlights the importance of transparency and accountability in AI-generated content, emphasizing the need for tools like ChatGPT to facilitate easy access to source material for verification purposes. As what Participant 2 said that:

"Siguro ang ma-suggest lang na ako sa ChatGPT is that kanang dapat mag-provide sila ug link or citation in order for us, so as a user para ma-identify if credible ba or valid ba iyang mga information na iyang gina hatag." (FGD-02)

(I suggest that ChatGPT should provide links or citations to enable users to determine the credibility and validity of the information it provides).

Furthermore, the participant recommends enhancing ChatGPT's performance by ensuring its responses include references, making it easier for users to ascertain the reliability and credibility of the information provided. This suggestion underlines the need for ChatGPT to not only deliver answers but also to offer evidence of where those answers come from. By integrating references directly into its responses, ChatGPT could significantly aid users in verifying the authenticity and accuracy of the information, thus fostering a more trustworthy and dependable interaction with the AI. As what Participant 5 stated that:

“So, ang akona lang ma-suggest no sa ChatGPT para ma-improve ang iyahang performance kay ang when it comes sa iyahang reliability ang akoang ma suggest nga if mag search gud ko ug kanang questions nya ang iyang information na iyang mahatag unta is kanang naa nay reference para makabalo ko na kaning information na iyang gi hatag is reliable and credible ug naga exist jud siya dili lang kay buhat-buhat sa ChatGPT." (FGD-05)

(My suggestion for improving ChatGPTs’ performance is that when it comes to its reliability, it should provide references when I search for its answers. The information it provides should have references so that I can verify if it is reliable and credible, and not just generated by the model itself).

Ensure the Data Privacy and Security. This is the fifth code for the third probed issue. Participants highlighted the importance of ensuring privacy and security measures to safely utilize the AI. This includes safeguarding personal information and ensuring that students can use ChatGPT without fear of their data being compromised or misused. Moreover, there were calls for implementing robust security measures for each user, emphasizing the need for individualized protection against potential threats or breaches. These concerns underscore the necessity for comprehensive data privacy policies and security protocols to safeguard users' information and provide a safe and secure environment for utilizing AI technologies in educational settings.

Similarly, in line with previous suggestions, users emphasized the significance of privacy and security features within ChatGPT to ensure a safe and secure user experience. This emphasized the sentiment that enhancing privacy measures is crucial for users to feel confident and comfortable utilizing the platform. By prioritizing privacy and security, ChatGPT can foster trust among its users and promote responsible usage of its services. As what Participant 3 said that:

“Kuan pud privacy and security para ma safe and ma utilize nako ang paggamit sa ChatGPT.” (FGD-03)

(Also, what are the privacy and security measures I can take to safely and effectively use ChatGPT).

In connection to that, users, advocated for ChatGPT to prioritize user privacy by ensuring that personal information remains private and not posted publicly. This aligns with the broader call for enhanced security measures within the platform to safeguard user data. By emphasizing the need for privacy and security, users are highlighting the importance of trust and confidentiality in their interactions with ChatGPT, underlining the responsibility of AI platforms to prioritize user protection and data security. As what Participant 4 stated that:

“So my suggestion to ChatGPT is to provide privacy on its users, for the users for each information would not be post in public and for it's security for the users of ChatGPT.” (FGD-04)

(My suggestion for ChatGPT is to prioritize user privacy, ensuring that each users information is not made public, and to strengthen security measures to protect the users of ChatGPT).

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Finding

The present study on delving user trust in utilizing ChatGPT in learning among elementary education students in a local college carries out a mixed methods approach employing convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 4 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect or focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration, and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in preceding columns.

Table 4.

<i>Aspect or Focal Points</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implication</i>
Level of User Trust in terms of Trust	Table 1 on the level of user trust among elementary education students in Utilizing ChatGPT in learning in item no. 2 being reliable in providing consistent and dependable information. (M=3.50)	Table 2.1 on the experiences shared by students with regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in learning under the essential theme essential resource in learning with a code reliable source of information and a core idea information given is well-constructed.	Merging-Converging	Students used ChatGPT in learning as they trust this AI tool in completing and doing their various and varied learning tasks. Additionally, students have witnessed the different benefits and essentials of ChatGPT especially in giving credible and authentic information with a responsibility of validating all of these to other reliable learning resources and websites.
	Table 1 on the level of user trust among elementary education students in Utilizing ChatGPT in learning in item no. 3 being trustworthy in the sense that it is dependable and credible. (M=3.42)	Table 3 on the insights shared by students with regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in learning under the essential theme building trust in the utilization of ChatGPT with a code high level of trust in using ChatGPT with a core idea having trust and confidence in the ability of ChatGPT in helping students’ academic pursuit with varying degree of reliance and verification.	Merging-Converging	
Level of User Trust in terms of Intent to Use	Table 1 on the level of user trust among elementary education students in Utilizing ChatGPT in learning in item no. 4 using ChatGPT as an educational tool in making my learning tasks to enhance my overall productivity and performance. (M=3.54)	Table 2.1 on the experiences shared by students with regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in learning under the essential theme essential resources in learning with a code making learning tasks convenient and simple with a core ideas making the learning tasks and activities easy and simple and finishing the tasks ahead of time.	Merging-Converging	
	Table 1 on the level of user trust among elementary education students in Utilizing ChatGPT in learning	Table 2.1 on the experiences shared by students with regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in learning under the essential theme	Merging-Converging	

	in item no.5 using ChatGPT whenever I need more explanation to a certain topic. (M=3.73)	development of students' personal skills with the code assist in understanding the concepts and core ideas helping in grasping the content and ideas of the topic and getting easily all the information related to the content.	
Level of User Trust in terms of Actual Use	Table 1 on the level of user trust among elementary education students in Utilizing ChatGPT in learning in item no.2 using ChatGPT for creative writing or brainstorming. (M=3.31)	Table 2.1 on the experiences shared by students with regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in learning under the essential theme develop one's writing skills with the code enhance writing skills and core idea learning new writing styles and conventions.	Merging-Converging
	Table 1 on the level of user trust among elementary education students in Utilizing ChatGPT in learning in item no.4 using ChatGPT for academic discussions or collaborative projects with classmates or colleagues. (M=3.42)	Table 3 on the insights shared by students with regards to the utilization of ChatGPT in learning under the essential theme the need of becoming responsible user of ChatGPT with the code peer discussion on the proper navigation of ChatGPT and a core idea collaborating with other students in discussing the potential benefits of ChatGPT in learning.	Merging-Diverging

Level of User Trust in terms of Trust. From item no. 2 in the quantitative phase, the specific item was rated by the participants as high being reliable in providing consistent and dependable information. Also, the item no.3 being trustworthy in the sense that it is dependable and credible are both rated as high. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as reliable source of information and high level of trust in using ChatGPT, specifically in the core idea information given is well-constructed and having trust and confidence in the ability of ChatGPT in helping students' academic pursuit with, under the essential theme essential resource in learning and building trust in the utilization of ChatGPT. It is then safe to say that the quantitative result merges the qualitative findings.

Level of User Trust in terms of Intent to Use. From item no. 4 in the quantitative phase, the specific item was rated by the participants as high using ChatGPT as an educational tool in making my learning tasks to enhance my overall productivity and performance. Also, the item no.5 using ChatGPT whenever I need more explanation to a certain topic are both rated as high. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as making learning tasks convenient and simple, and assist in understanding the concepts, specifically in the core idea making the learning tasks and activities easy and simple and finishing the tasks ahead of time and helping in grasping the content and ideas of the topic and getting easily all the information related to the content, under the essential theme, essential resources in learning and development of students' personal skills with the code assist in understanding the concepts. It is then safe to say that the quantitative result merges the qualitative findings.

Level of User Trust in terms of Actual Use. From item no.2 in the quantitative phase, the specific item was rated by the participants as high using ChatGPT for creative writing or brainstorming and using ChatGPT for academic discussions or collaborative projects with classmates or colleagues. Also, the in item no.4 using ChatGPT for academic discussions or collaborative projects with classmates or colleagues are both rated as high. This results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is categorized as enhance writing skills and peer discussion on the proper navigation on ChatGPT, specifically in the core idea learning new writing styles and conventions and collaborating with other students in discussing the potential benefits of ChatGPT in learning, under the essential theme of develop one's writing skills with the code enhance writing skills and the need of becoming responsible user of ChatGPT with the code peer discussion on the proper navigation of ChatGPT. It is then safe to say that the quantitative result merges the qualitative findings.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The level of user trust among elementary education students in utilizing ChatGPT for learning purposes is high in terms trust, actual use and intent to use. Hence, this indicates that the indicators of user trust are always manifested by the elementary education students.

The thematic analysis of the qualitative data was conducted based on the responses gathered through in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD). The results provided deeper insights into the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of elementary education students as they trust ChatGPT in utilizing and facilitating a smooth learning process that accommodates diverse needs and preferences. Qualitatively, elementary education students have encountered various situations that influence their utilization of

ChatGPT in learning. The following themes were emerged: Essential Resources in Learning and Being User Friendly, Accessible, and Convenient to Use, Becoming a Responsible User of AI, Develop One's Writing Skill, Development of students' Personal Skills and Degrading Higher Order Thinking Skills, Enhancing Comprehension and Cultivating the Habit of Reading and Validating the Given Information, Technology-based Concerns

From the participants' responses, other themes are identified which show the insights share of elementary education students as to their utilization of ChatGPT in learning and overall educational journey. The following are the themes: ChatGPT as Essential Resource for Learning, Building Trust in the Utilization of ChatGPT, The Need of Becoming a Responsible User of ChatGPT, Techniques in Using ChatGPT as Learning Resource, Essential Development of ChatGPT for its Efficiency and Efficacy, and Development of its Features and Algorithms.

To better understand the impact of students' level of user trust towards utilizing ChatGPT in learning, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the qualitative results of the study. Both the findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The level of user trust (US) of the participants were based on the quantitative results, showed that if converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both qualitative and quantitative data highlighted that while there exists a high level of trust in ChatGPT, there are also discernible negative side effects, alongside notable positive effects and benefits, associated with incorporating ChatGPT into their learning endeavors.

References

- A. El-Seoud, S., Ayman, S. E., Nagaty, K., & H. Karam, O. (2023). The Impact of ChatGPT on Student Learning/performing. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4532913>
- Agarwal, S., Agarwal, B., & Gupta, R. (2022). Chatbots and virtual assistants: a bibliometric analysis. *Library Hi Tech*, 40(4), 1013–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1108/lht-09-2021-0330>
- Ahuja, A. S. (2019). The impact of artificial intelligence in medicine on the future role of the physician. *PeerJ*, 7(7702), e7702. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.7702>
- Aljanabi, M., & ChatGPT. (2023). ChatGPT: Future Directions and Open possibilities. *Mesopotamian Journal of Cyber Security*, 16–17. <https://doi.org/10.58496/mjcs/2023/003>
- Alonso-Fernandez, C., Calvo, R. A., & Ghinea, G. (2018). Accessible MOOCs through AI-driven assessment and feedback. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 11(2), 207-219.
- Alshater, M. (2022). Exploring the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing academic performance: A case study of ChatGPT (December 26, 2022). Available at SSRN.
- Angelis, LD., Baglivo, F., Arzilli, G., Privitera, PG., Ferragina, P., Tozzi, AE., & Rizzo, C. (2023). ChatGPT and the rise of large language models: the new AI-driven infodemic threat in public health. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1166120>
- Aydın, Ö., & Karaarslan, E. (2023). Is ChatGPT leading generative AI? What is beyond expectations? *Academic Platform Journal of Engineering and Smart Systems*.
- Aydın, Ö., Karaarslan, E. (2022). OpenAI ChatGPT Generated Literature Review: Digital Twin in Healthcare. In Ö. Aydın (Ed.), *Emerging Computer Technologies 2* (22-31). İzmir Akademi Dernegi
- Bringman-Rodenbarger, L., & Hortsch, M. (2020). How students choose E-learning resources: The importance of ease, familiarity, and convenience. *Faseb Bioadvances*, 2(5), 286.
- Browne, R. (2023). All you need to know about ChatGPT, the A.I. chatbot that's got the world talking and tech giants clashing. *CNBC*. <https://www.cnbc.com/2023/02/08/what-is-chatgpt-viral-ai-chatbot-at-heart-of-microsoft-google-fight.html>
- Bryman, A. (2007). Barriers to Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*.
- Castelvecchi, D. (2022). Are ChatGPT and AlphaCode going to replace programmers? *Nature*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-04383z>
- Caulfield, J. (2023, April 28). What Is ChatGPT? | Everything You Need to Know. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/ai-tools/what-is-chatgpt/>
- Chi, C. (2023). Should ChatGPT be banned in schools? UP crafts “responsible” AI use guidelines. *Philstar.com*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/07/19/2282226/should-chatgpt-be-banned-schools-crafts-responsible-ai-use-guidelines>
- Choudhury, A., & Shamszare, H. (2023). Investigating the impact of user trust on the adoption and use of ChatGPT: Survey analysis. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 25, 47184. <https://doi.org/10.2196/47184>

- Cotton, D., Cotton, P., & Shipway, J. (2023). Chatting and cheating: Ensuring academic integrity in the era of ChatGPT. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2190148>.
- De Angelis, L., Baglivo, F., Guglielmo Arzilli, Gaetano Pierpaolo Privitera, Paolo Ferragina, Alberto Eugenio Tozzi, & Rizzo, C. (2023). ChatGPT and the rise of large language models: the new AI-driven infodemic threat in public health. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1166120>
- Demir, S. B., & Pismek, N. (2018). A Convergent Parallel Mixed-Methods Study of Controversial Issues in Social Studies Classes: a Clash of Ideologies. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2018.1.0298>
- Dempere, J., Modugu, K., Hesham, A., & Ramasamy, L. (2023). The impact of ChatGPT on higher education. *Frontiers in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1206936>.
- Dilmeani, C. (2023). ChatGPT Education Use Cases, Benefits & Challenges in 2023. AIMultiple. Retrieved from <https://research.aimultiple.com/chatgpt-education/#top-7-chatgpt-education-use-cases>.
- Ding, L., Li, T., Jiang, S. et al. Students' perceptions of using ChatGPT in a physics class as a virtual tutor. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 20, 63 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00434-1>
- Duong, D., & Solomon, B. D. (2023). Analysis of large-language model versus human performance for genetics questions. *European Journal of Human Genetics*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-023-01396-8>
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Kshetri, N., Hughes, L., Slade, E. L., Jeyaraj, A., Kar, A. K., ... & Wright, R. (2023), "So what if ChatGPT wrote it?" Multidisciplinary perspectives on opportunities, challenges and implications of generative conversational AI for research, practice and policy. *International Journal of Information Management*.
- Feng, Y., & Wang, X. (2023). A comparative study on the development of Chinese and English abilities of Chinese primary school students through two bilingual reading modes: human-AI robot interaction and paper books. *Frontiers in Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1200675>
- Fijačko, N., Gosak, L., Štiglic, G., Picard, C. T., & John Douma, M. (2023). Can ChatGPT pass the life support exams without entering the American heart association course? *Resuscitation*, 185, 109732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resuscitation.2023.109732>
- Gause, S. (2023). Building Skills in Students in Preparation for an AI-Centered Future. *Www.linkedin.com*. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/building-skills-students-preparation-ai-centered-steven-gause-mpa>
- Gilson, A., Safranek, C. W., Huang, T., Socrates, V., Chi, L., Taylor, R. A., & Chartash, D. (2023). How Does ChatGPT Perform on the United States Medical Licensing Examination? The Implications of Large Language Models for Medical Education and Knowledge Assessment. *JMIR Medical Education*, 9, e45312. <https://doi.org/10.2196/45312>
- Gupta, M., Akiri, C., Aryal, K., Parker, E., & Praharaj, L. (2023). From ChatGPT to ThreatGPT: Impact of Generative AI in Cybersecurity and Privacy. *IEEE Access*, 11, 80218–80245. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3300381>
- Halaweh, M. (2023). ChatGPT in education: Strategies for responsible implementation. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 15(2), ep421. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/13036>
- Halcomb, E., & Hickman, L. (2015). Mixed methods research. *Nursing Standard*, 29(32), 41–47. <https://doi.org/10.7748/ns.29.32.41.e8858>
- Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). Artificial intelligence in education: Promises and implications for teaching and learning. *The Center For Curriculum Redesign*.
- Howard, A., Hope, W., & Gerada, A. (2023). ChatGPT and antimicrobial advice: the end of the consulting infection doctor? *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099\(23\)00113-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1473-3099(23)00113-5)
- James, D. (2017). 360 Learning Team. (n.d.). What Is Connectivism Learning Theory and How Can You Apply It in Learning and Development? 360Learning. <https://360learning.com/guide/learning-theories/connectivism-learning-theory/>
- Jovanović, M. (2023). Generative Artificial Intelligence: Trends and Prospects. <https://www.computer.org/csdl/magazine/co/2022/10/09903869/1H0G6xvtREk.0.1109/MC.2022.3192720>.
- Kung, T. H., Cheatham, M., Medenilla, A., Sillos, C., De Leon, L., Elepaño, C., Madriaga, M., Aggabao, R., Diaz-Candido, G., Maningo, J., & Tseng, V. (2023). Performance of ChatGPT on USMLE: Potential for AI-assisted medical education using large language models. *PLOS Digital Health*, 2(2), e0000198. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000198>
- Lo, C. K. (2023). Exploring the Potential of ChatGPT in Education: A Qualitative Study. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 15(1), 1-20.

- Lo, C. K. (2023). What Is the Impact of ChatGPT on Education? A Rapid Review of the Literature. *Education Sciences*, 13(4), 410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13040410>
- Lund, B. D., & Wang, T. (2023). Chatting about chatgpt: How may AI and GPT impact academia and libraries? *Library Hi Tech News*, 40(3), 26–29. <https://doi.org/10.1108/lhtn-01-2023-0009>
- Lyons JB, Hobbs K, Rogers S, Clouse SH. Responsible (use of) AI. *Front Neuroergon*. 2023 Nov 20; 4:1201777. doi: 10.3389/fnrgo.2023.1201777. PMID: 38234494; PMCID: PMC10790885.
- Mahapatra, S. (2024). Impact of ChatGPT on ESL students' academic writing skills: A mixed methods intervention study. *Smart Learning Environments*, 11(9). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-024-00295-9>
- Mantula, F., Chauraya, Y., Danda, G., Chaibva, C. N., Ngwenya, T., Gwatinga, C., & Chamisa, J. A. (2023). Perspective Chapter: Sexual Health Interventions for Adolescents. *Www.intechopen.com*; IntechOpen. <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/1137866>
- Marique, JM. (2023). Building trust in AI is a shared responsibility. *KPMG*. <https://kpmg.com/ph/en/home/insights/2023/04/building-trust-in-ai-is-a-shared-responsibility.html>
- Mbakwe, A. B., Lourentzou, I., Celi, L. A., Mechanic, O. J., & Dagan, A. (2023). ChatGPT passing USMLE shines a spotlight on the flaws of medical education. *PLOS Digital Health*, 2(2), e0000205. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000205>
- McLean, D. (2023, May 27). What is ChatGPT & 10 Creative Ways To Use It. *Elegant Themes Blog*. <https://www.elegantthemes.com/blog/business/what-is-chatgpt>
- Montemayor, C., Halpern, J., & Fairweather, A. (2022). In principle obstacles for empathic AI: why we can't replace human empathy in healthcare. *AI & Society*.
- Nikitas, A., Michalakopoulou, K., Njoya, E. T., & Karampatzakis, D. (2020). Artificial intelligence, transport and the smart city: Definitions and dimensions of a new mobility era. *Sustainability*.
- Nisar, S., & Aslam, M. S. (2023). Is ChatGPT a Good Tool for T&CM Students in Studying Pharmacology? *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4324310>
- O'Connor, S., & ChatGPT. (2023). Open artificial intelligence platforms in nursing education: Tools for academic progress or abuse? *Nurse Education in Practice*, 66, 103-537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2022.103537>.
- Ofosu-Ampong, K. (2020). The shift to gamification in education: A review on dominant issues. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*.
- Ofosu-Ampong, K., Acheampong, B., & Kevor, M.-O. (2023, July 31). Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT) in Education: Trust, Innovativeness and Psychological Need of Students. *Social Science Research Network*. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4541108
- Ortiz, S. (2023). What is ChatGPT and why does it matter? Here's what you need to know. *ZDNET*;ZDNET. <https://www.zdnet.com/article/what-is-chatgpt-and-why-does-it-matter-heres-everything-you-need-to-know/>
- Osorio, J.A.C. (2023). Explorando el potencial de ChatGPT en la escritura científica: Ventajas, desafíos y precauciones. *Sci. Et Tech*.
- Patel, S. B., & Lam, K. (2023). ChatGPT: the future of discharge summaries? *The Lancet Digital Health*, 5(3), 107–108.
- Pavlik, J. V. (2023). Collaborating With ChatGPT: Considering the Implications of Generative Artificial Intelligence for Journalism and Media Education. *Journalism & Mass Communication Educator*, 78(1), 107769582211495.
- Prananta, A., Susanto, N., Purwantoro, A., & Fuadah, N. (2023). ChatGPT Artificial Intelligence Integration in Science Learning Media: Systematic Literature Review. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jppipa.v9i7.4386>.
- Qadir, J. (2022). Engineering Education in the Era of ChatGPT: Promise and Pitfalls of Generative AI for Education. *Www.techrxiv.org*.
- Qadir, J. (2022). Engineering Education in the Era of ChatGPT: Promises and Pitfalls of Generative AI for Education. *TechRxiv*.
- Rao, A., Kim, J., Kamineni, M., Pang, M., Lie, W., & Succi, M. D. (2023). Evaluating ChatGPT as an Adjunct for Radiologic Decision-Making. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.02.02.23285399>
- Renti Oktaria, Ali, I., & Putra, P. (2023). The Potential Utilizing ChatGPT for Education and Teaching Students: Understanding, Prospects, Challenges, and Utilization". *Educative Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*, 1(2), 87–94. <https://doi.org/10.37985/educative.v1i2.75>
- Rusandi, M., Saripah, I., Khairun, D., & M. (2023). No worries with ChatGPT: Building bridges between artificial intelligence and education with critical thinking soft skills. *Journal of Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdad049>

- Sachs, A. (2023). Here is why ChatGPT raises issues of trust. LinkedIn. https://mu.linkedin.com/posts/andrewsachs1_heres-why-chatgpt-raises-issues-of-trust-activity-7029584510384001024-w3A0
- Sallam, M. (2023). ChatGPT Utility in Healthcare Education, Research, and Practice: Systematic Review on the Promising Perspectives and Valid Concerns. *Healthcare*, 11(6), 887. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11060887>
- Sánchez, O.V. (2023). Uso y Percepción de ChatGPT en la Educación Superior. *Rev. De Investig. En Tecnol. De La Inf.*
- Schoonenboom, J., & Johnson, R. B. (2017). How to Construct A mixed Methods Research Design. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift Für Soziologie Und Sozialpsychologie*, 69(2), 107–131. NCBI. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-017-0454-1>
- Shneiderman, B. (2020). Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence: Three Fresh Ideas. *AIS Transactions on Human-Computer Interaction*, 12(3), 109–124. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1thci.00131>
- Sofi. (2023). Building User Trust with UX Design: 15 Effective Strategies. Thoughts about Product Adoption, User Onboarding and Good UX | Userpilot Blog. <https://userpilot.com/blog/user-trust/>
- Takyar, A. (2023, April 19). Benefits and use cases of AI in education. LeewayHertz. <https://www.leewayhertz.com/ai-use-cases-in-education/>
- Tapalova, O., & Zhiyenbayeva, N. (2022). Artificial Intelligence in Education: AIED for Personalised Learning Pathways. *Electronic Journal of e-Learning*.
- Thompson, P. (2019). Technology Acceptance Model. Open.library.okstate.edu; Oklahoma State University Libraries. <https://open.library.okstate.edu/foundationsofeducationaltechnology/chapter/2-technology-acceptance-model/>
- Wang, T.; Lund, B.D.; Marengo, A.; Pagano, A.; Mannuru, N.R.; Teel, Z.A.; Pange, J. (2023). Exploring the Potential Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on International Students in Higher Education: Generative AI, Chatbots, Analytics, and International Student Success. *Applied Science*.
- Williams, D. (2022). The importance of cognitive load theory. Society for Education and Training. Set.et-Foundation.co.uk. <https://set.et-foundation.co.uk/resources/the-importance-of-cognitive-load-theory>
- Zhai, X. (2023). ChatGPT for Next Generation Science Learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4331313>
- Zhang, R., Guo, J., Chen, L., Fan, Y., & Cheng, X. (2021). A review on question generation from natural language text. *ACM Transactions on Information Systems*.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Christian Jay B. Martinez

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Onorio P. Cagoco Jr., MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines